

Impact of social media marketing on small and medium-sized restaurants in London, UK

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Declaration

I declare that the thesis “Impact of social media marketing on small and medium-sized restaurants in London, UK” is my own work and the sources which I used are properly quoted and credited to the author for reference.

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List of Abbreviations

CRM	Customer relationship management
GDP	Gross domestic product
IT	Information technology
PwC	PricewaterhouseCoopers
ROI	Return on investment
SET	Social exchange theory
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
SNS	Social network site
WOM	Word of mouth
Apps	Applications

Publications

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Abstract

This study is about determining and evaluating the use of social media applications for marketing purposes across the restaurant industry of the UK. The specific context chosen in this study is small and medium-sized restaurants operating in London because London is the hub of tourists and serves a large number of diverse customers regularly. Small restaurants were selected because these are more vulnerable to external forces of change, especially a crisis such as COVID-19; moreover, these restaurants have limited budgets to develop and use marketing strategies to survive and grow. Overall, the market dynamics for small restaurants (that exist in large numbers across London) are complex and volatile, which makes them an interesting subject to study. An increasing number of customers use smartphones, the internet and social media apps for shopping and buying. Therefore, the intention was to explore and critically evaluate how consumer buying behaviour can be influenced by the marketing practices of restaurants on social media platforms, such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, branded applications and WhatsApp. The methodology adopted in this study was qualitative and inductive in nature because the goal was to gather the subjective opinions and perceptions of the managers and owners of small and medium-sized restaurants on their marketing strategies. An interpretivist philosophy was adopted for this study to complement the subjective views of reality. This was suitable because the research objectives required getting the opinions of restaurant respondents as per their unique experiences. Using purposive sampling technique, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 20 respondents who were either owners or managers of small and medium-sized restaurants. Thematic analysis was used to present the analysis and to identify key themes and sub-themes. This study found that social media apps are an effective source of marketing for small and medium-sized restaurants in London. With the help of social media marketing, via apps, restaurants improved their brand visibility and brand image and in some cases sales as well. Friends and family were identified as valuable sources of customer attraction in this regard. Instagram was the most popular and effective social media platform for marketing for the restaurants and for influencing consumer behaviour. Using paid and original content advertisements, improving skills to use social media apps and IT, being more adaptable and proactive towards the business environment, improving social media marketing content and pages and then linking them to websites' contacts, integration of delivery apps, like Uber Eats, Deliveroo and Just Eat, and willingness to integrate social media marketing strategy are some of the recommendations provided to small and medium-sized restaurants as a result of this study.

Contents

1. Introduction	10
1.1 Context of COVID-19 Crisis.....	11
1.2 Research Rationale and Industry Issues.....	12
1.3 Research Background.....	15
1.4 Research Motivation	17
1.5 Research Aim	18
1.5.1 Research Questions.....	18
1.5.2 Research Objectives.....	18
1.6 Proposed Methodology	18
1.7 Outline and Structure of Thesis	19
2. Literature Review	20
2.1 Introduction	20
2.2 The Concept of Social Media	21
2.2.1 Definition and Purpose	21
2.2.2 Benefits and Limitations	22
2.2.3 Evolution and Trends in social media	24
2.3 Consumer Behaviour Concept	30
2.3.1 Purpose and Definition	30
2.3.2 Critique of Consumer Behaviour Models.....	32
2.3.3 The Four Types of Buying Behaviours.....	34
2.3.4 Theoretical Perspectives of Consumer Behaviour.....	35
2.4 Concept of Mobile Apps.....	40
2.4.1 Purpose and Definition	40
2.4.2 Benefits and Limitations	43
2.4.3 Understanding the Importance of Branded Mobile Apps for Businesses	44
2.4.4 Understanding Branded Applications	49
2.5 Social Media Marketing Dynamics.....	55
2.5.1 Social Media Marketing and Online Brand Communities.....	55
2.5.2 Facebook, Twitter and Instagram	57
2.5.3 The Emergence of Social Media Influencers as a Marketing Tool	58
2.6 Marketing in SMEs	61
2.6.1 The Context of SMEs.....	61
2.6.2 Customer relationship management (CRM)	63

2.6.3	Viral Marketing	65
2.6.4	Smartphones, SMEs and Security Challenges	67
2.7	Dynamics and Typology of Restaurants in the UK	68
2.7.1	Competitiveness, Demographics and Performance.....	70
2.7.2	Restaurant Image	72
2.8	Thematic Evaluation of Literature	74
2.9	Conceptual Framework.....	75
2.9.1	Social Impact Theory and Social Media Marketing.....	75
2.9.2	Social Media Apps and Consumer Behaviour	76
2.9.3	Mobile Apps and Consumer Behaviour	82
2.9.4	Social Media Influencers	83
2.10	Chapter Summary	86
3.	Research Methodology	87
3.1	Introduction	87
3.2	Ontology and Epistemology	87
3.3	Research Philosophy	88
3.4	Deductive, Inductive and Abductive Approaches	89
3.4.1	The Deductive Approach.....	90
3.4.2	The Inductive Approach.....	91
3.4.3	The Abductive Approach.....	92
3.5	Research Design	93
3.5.1	Adopting the Qualitative approach.....	95
3.6	Sampling Approach	95
3.7	Using Thematic Method of Data Analysis.....	96
3.8	Reliability and Validity.....	97
3.8.1	Content Validity	99
3.8.2	Face Validity	100
3.9	Ethical Considerations.....	100
4.	Results	102
4.1	Introduction	102
4.2	Interpretation and Presentation of Results	103
4.3	Chapter Summary	116
5.	Discussion	117
5.1	Introduction	117

5.2 Thematic Table with Experts' Quotes	117
5.3 The Use of Social Media Platforms and Consumers.....	122
5.4 Brand Visibility and Awareness.....	129
5.5 Pandemic Crisis and Challenges for Restaurants	133
5.6 Suggestions for Improvements.....	136
5.7 Discussion on Themes and Sub-themes	138
5.8 Chapter Summary	146
6. Conclusion and Recommendations.....	147
6.1 Conclusion.....	147
6.2 Recommendations	148
6.3 Contribution to Knowledge.....	153
6.4 Research Limitations.....	156
6.5 Future Research Directions.....	158
6.6 Research and Managerial Implications.....	159
7. References	162
8. Appendices A	197
8.1 Smash Burgers & Co (Owner as Respondent).....	197
8.2 Kofi & Co (Owner as Respondent)	198
8.3 Burgo Town (Owner as Respondent).....	199

1. Introduction

Advances in technology have improved and enhanced smartphones and wireless and connectivity options. Personalised identification systems over networks have made a greater quantity of data accessible, with faster access times, to consumers and firms (Pantano, 2014; Pantano and Viassone, 2015). Through the development of hand-held devices, such as smartphones and laptops, people are a tap away from accessing information via the internet. These advances have changed the information landscape; consumers now have greater access to information and a greater knowledge base.

In today's world, consumers rely heavily on the internet to find the information they need, for example, on food and related matters. They make informed food purchase decisions by comparing and analysing the information they obtain (Cartwright et al., 2021). Consumers can share comments, opinions and information reviews on food and food quality and arrive at a rational knowledgeable food purchasing decision (Elghannam et al., 2017; Fazzam, 2021;) Bilgihan et al., 2014. This has made the world a global village as people from completely different backgrounds are able to provide their opinions and hence influence the decision-making process of others, including food purchasing decisions (Hofacker et al., 2020). As a result, identifying credible and reliable information on food quality becomes challenging.

The physical and social environments surrounding consumers play a vital role in influencing their purchasing decisions and the final outcome, and they have an impact on consumers' satisfaction.

The number of users of social media has increased. In response to this increase, the food industry has started using social media as a marketing tool, because it considers social media users to be a potential market. Organizations have not only changed the way they market their products, but also changed the way they approach their customers and make available their services to them (Shemi and Procter, 2018).

The increased use of advanced smartphones, greater connectivity and a universal network has led to mobile marketing (Gao et al., 2013; Kaplan, 2012; Strom et al., 2014), which distributes information that is interactive and personalized. In the current age of technological advances,

computer systems can detect an individual consumer's behaviour and preferences and make suggestions accordingly. The computer system can track the geographical location (through GPS) of an individual and make recommendations, such as tourist spots in that area. These technological advances are eliminating the time and space boundaries that were characteristic of the traditional retail setting (Demirkan and Spohrer, 2014; Lashgari et al., 2018; Pantano, 2014). On the other hand, retailers have been pushed to adapt to these particular changes and modify their business models to incorporate technology-based channels and practices, including the impact of smartphones.

1.1 Context of COVID-19 Crisis

The COVID-19 pandemic hit the global community really hard and has had a very grave impact on people's lives with some sudden and immediate changes in social interactions, such as the wearing of face coverings, social distancing and the banning of large events, including sporting events and religious congregations. At the same time, some developments and aspects of life that were gradually gaining popularity quickly became an essential part of people's lives, such as the use of hand sanitizers (especially in developing countries), the use of digital forums for shopping and the use of digital banking (Kim et al., 2021). Market dynamics were completely overturned by the enormous impact of the pandemic on individuals and organizations, and new business transaction modes were developed to respond to the unusual market conditions (Hartwig and Jacob, 2021).

The traditional consumer-seller relationship was affected by the COVID-19 protocols of lockdowns and requirements of social distancing. Consumer behaviour in the new market dynamics changed greatly, for example, consumers used delivery facilities and shopped online to follow COVID-19 protocols. This change in behaviour was helped by the fact that relatively new technologies, like smartphones and mobile applications, are increasingly developed and used. The charm and ease of online shopping encouraged consumers to stay with these innovative ways of buying (McKinsey & Company, 2021). Business transactions are being carried out by organizations in a new and innovative manner. At the same time, sellers also adapted to the changes in market dynamics by combining technology and marketing to respond to the market shift. As the world battles with the pandemic and moves into a post-pandemic era, some of these changes in the marketplace will remain, while others may be dropped and replaced with the ways used before the pandemic (Sheth, 2021).

Marketing models need to be informed and sustainable; therefore, changes in consumers' behaviour and needs need to be explored (Mehta et al., 2020). Traditionally, consumer behaviour was heavily impacted by location and time. The behaviour of consumers at one location differed from the behaviour of consumers at another location due to their geographical location, religious inclination, culture and so on. However, the pandemic has affected customers' behaviour. An example of this would be the fact that consumers are increasingly, and very swiftly, shifting towards online channels where they are greeted with new and different influences (Jagdish, 2021). The traditional methods of modelling consumer behaviour do not work in such circumstances and now require a dynamic approach.

New environments have an impact on behaviour and habits change. As per research, on average it takes 66 days for a person to form a new habit (Lally et al., 2009). Any habit that does not greatly impact existing routine is easily and quickly adopted. In current times of wave after wave of new variants of coronavirus and consequent pandemic-related measures, consumers are forming new patterns of behaviour and getting used to them. In cases where consumers' experience of changing their behaviour is positive, such as changing from conventional banking to digital banking, the changes are likely to last longer. This is especially true for changes that are perceived as convenient or as leading to well-being (Palau-Saumell et al., 2021).

1.2 Research Rationale and Industry Issues

Due to changes in the current marketing arena, there is an understanding in the business and marketing world that it is necessary to prepare and implement new marketing strategies based on smartphone and mobile applications (Walker et al., 2019). Improved retailing options are available to consumers due to the development of new technologies and platforms in the digital arena, which has caused fierce competition among businesses (Wang et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2017). As smartphones and mobile applications are gaining popularity and becoming part of everyday life, the retail business and its related concept of space are also evolving. For example, small and medium-sized restaurants that could not operate during COVID-19-related lockdowns are now doing business using a digital identity (Bolden et al., 2017). Buyers and

sellers are readily accessible on digital platforms; this also applies to restaurants that have to maintain their online presence. These technology-related trends, social trends and competition-related trends make it imperative to conduct this study to give small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the restaurant industry a concrete understanding, and awareness of, the role of social media marketing. The rationale for conducting this study in the UK is that a very high proportion of UK consumers use information technology (IT) and IT-related tools on digital platforms.

As these developments continue to have an impact on consumers, consumers' experiences might change over time. This may happen due to the availability of several mobile channels, which in turn have an impact on consumers' buying behaviour with respect to their search for and identification of a product, purchase of the product, which may involve digital means, consumption of the product and after sales behaviour and experience (Dennis et al., 2016). The rationale for conducting a study of UK restaurants is the lack of evidence or understanding of how mobile applications could be utilized to identify consumers' consumption patterns and buying behaviour in order to market effectively to attract them and retain their loyalty towards a restaurant.

It has been noted that practitioners' and scholars' interest in using innovation for enhanced retailing has increased, but there are still gaps in the literature in relation to the new dynamics of consumer behaviour. The literature has emphasized enriching customer experience using mobile applications, especially in the context of restaurants (Foroudi et al., 2018; Deloitte, 2019). Previous studies focused on consumers' acceptance of new systems by studying consumers' usage and attitude (Pantano and Viassone, 2015; Zahid et al., 2017). Researchers have also focused on retailers' management of technological innovation, but they have not considered the impact of technological innovation on the experience of consumers, particularly from a cognitive perspective or in the context of mobile applications that provide brand image or brand presence for small and medium-sized restaurants (Wang, 2018). Therefore, the research focus and emphasis of this study is to identify, understand and provide probable solutions to the complexities of consumer behaviour in today's digital age.

Narang and Shankar (2019) stated that mobile marketing has recently reached new heights in terms of the use of technology in the form of mobile apps. These apps provide convenience to consumers in finding, comparing and ordering products alongside accessing news relevant to products/services, the creation of shopping lists and locating products/stores near them. It is

thought that people may start trusting technology over time and that marketing through mobile apps will pose unique challenges and opportunities for SMEs in terms of creating an impact on their consumer base (Ramos-de-Luna et al., 2015; Shakaridevi et al., 2015; Zhao et al., 2015).

These developments and trends lead to changes in the way consumers behave while using digital tools and mobile applications; therefore, the rationale behind this study is that restaurants in the UK need to be aware of how their branded mobile applications are performing and of the importance of the role of their unique mobile applications in positively influencing consumer buying behaviour. Insights into the restaurant industry of the UK can be gained by analysing themes and trends that cause changes in businesses in the industry. A significant proportion of changes in consumer buying behaviour is due to the changing tastes and preferences of customers (Deloitte, 2017). This study therefore seeks to clarify how small and medium-sized restaurants in the UK are managing changing trends in consumer behaviour in mobile applications usage.

As the restaurant industry is very competitive, one of the major challenges faced by restaurants today is communicating their point of differentiation from competitors; mobile applications help them to achieve this (Berezina et al., 2019). Customers in the UK have become cautionary in their approach to spending on extras, including dining out. This highlights that the point of differentiation has become even more important for restaurants to ensure their survival. This is the rationale behind examining how small and medium-sized restaurants in the specific context of London are keeping pace with this challenge.

Rogers (2018) stated that customers today are more aware about the innovative measures businesses use, and this marks their expectations from particular brands. Consequently, many businesses in the food and restaurant industries are under persistent pressure to keep up with the changing expectations and needs of consumers. Innovation has not become important for its own sake, the end objective is to improve the delivery of goods and services by using better technology (CGA, 2017).

Almost every business today acknowledges the power of effective marketing strategies as the foundation of an enterprise. However, competitors also use marketing; differentiating one's marketing from competitors in the restaurant industry is difficult, particularly when brands rely on digital marketing only. Restaurants also focus on traditional marketing, which can help to distinguish them from their competitors (Mullen, 2018).

1.3 Research Background

The restaurant industry, in terms of revenue, is worth more than GBP 38 billion and comprises more than 86,000 restaurants, highlighting its significance. In addition, individuals in the UK spend, on average, GBP 18 on eating out and an average of 1.7 million individuals in the UK eat out at least once a week; this highlights the reasons behind the persistent growth of the restaurant sector during difficult times. With 988,000 people employed in the sector, the restaurant sector is one of the notable employers in the UK and contributes significantly to the economy of the country (RG Group, 2019).

Growth in the leisure industry has persisted in recent times and consumer expenditure on restaurants, including cafés, reached nearly GBP 88 billion in 2017. The number of restaurants has also increased persistently with the sector contributing GBP 17.9 billion to the non-financial economy of the UK in 2016. Restaurants and other food service providers are the largest segment of the leisure industry as eating out is considered a leisure activity in the UK. Deloitte estimated the numbers for the restaurant sub-sector to be GBP 29.3 billion in 2014. Furthermore, in 2017, an average household spent GBP 19 a week on meals outside home and this increased for the age group between 30 and 64 (Statista Research Department, 2018). The quick service restaurant (QSR) sector, such as Burger King, KFC and McDonald's (Elo, 2016), forms a notable part of spending by households: 44% of consumers visited a fast food or quick food service at least once a week in 2015.

Branded restaurants are more popular among UK consumers. Visits to non-branded restaurants showed a decline from 2008 to 2016, whereas branded restaurants observed an increase during the same period. Brands are more dominant in the casual dining sector, brands such as Pizza Express and Nando's that have 441 and 395 outlets in the UK, respectively. Spending on casual dining in the UK was measured to be worth more than GBP 4.7 billion in 2017 and is expected to rise in the years to come. Pub food has become another popular dining option for casual dining with the chain reporting an increase in food sales since the start of twenty-first century (Statista Research Department, 2018).

Over time, smartphones have changed every industry, including the way food is ordered. In the 2010s, people started using technology to book a taxi or order food from restaurants with the ease of a few clicks. These few clicks can assure a taxi or desirable food at their doorsteps. Food delivery has emerged in line with technology as several restaurants have developed their

own apps and streamlined the process of delivering food while ensuring the satisfaction of their customers. Furthermore, the restaurants of today are also trying different third-party solutions for delivery, such as Uber Eats and Grubhub in the UK and similar applications in other countries.

Recently, there has been impressive growth in the usage of food and restaurant apps, especially among food lovers. The usage of apps relating to food and restaurants has increased by 70% as compared to 2014 (Chung et al., 2017). Platforms reviewing restaurants, like Yelp and Zomato, are also important for the industry as foodies are more likely to read reviews and go to restaurants in the light of the reviews, especially if they want to try new places. In addition, applications like Deliveroo and Postmates (food delivery services) help to generate revenues in Western markets. These companies create new markets for easy and convenient food delivery, particularly in urban areas. Such platforms allow restaurants to get in touch with more consumers (Jalilvand et al., 2018). Restaurants and mobile food services in the UK had a good year in 2017 as they generated a revenue of more than GBP 37.5 billion, which was the highest in history, and an improvement of 6.55% as compared to 2016 (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Annual turnover of restaurants and mobile food services in the UK from 2008 to 2017* (in million GBP)

Source: Statista (2017)

Some applications are used more than others; the most used application types in the UK as of 2015 included retailer apps, such as eBay, Amazon and Tesco (Statista, 2014). Statista (2019) reported that mobile food service enterprises and the restaurants industry in the UK contributed approximately GBP 18.9 billion to the UK economy, which is a significant amount and reflects the importance of this industry.

1.4 Research Motivation

There are some vital motivational factors behind the undertaking of this research study. A key personal motivation is the researcher's own interest in the restaurant industry (i.e., having a background of working in this industry gave significant motivation to conduct a research investigation). Personal and professional development is another key motivation behind this study because with the goal of working in this industry in the long run, pragmatic understanding needs to be developed which this research experience can provide. Moreover, as a business management learner and researcher, the research problem and topic grabbed attention because they involve consideration of some key factors, such as social media platforms, branded apps used by companies, the world of online customers and capability to improve competitiveness. A key motivation in this regard is the urge to improve understanding of how small and medium-sized restaurant businesses can be optimally managed with limited resources and capacity. Therefore, determining the strategic elements embedded in the use of social media platforms for marketing purposes motivated the undertaking of this study; this would enable the researcher to improve knowledge and understanding in a specific context, which would help in future professional prospects. The use of social media to attract and retain customers is certainly posing challenges for companies because the intensity of competition has increased and because of the frequent changes to consumer behaviour across markets (Wu and Li, 2018; Casalo et al., 2018). Therefore, as a business management learner who aspires to be a manager in the restaurant industry, understanding the role of social media in the marketing arena and understanding consumer behaviour motivated the conducting of this research study.

1.5 Research Aim

To investigate the impact of social media applications on consumer buying behaviour in small and medium-sized restaurants in London.

1.5.1 Research Questions

- Why are social media apps important for small and medium-sized restaurants?
- What kind of benefits do consumers look to draw from social media apps?
- What kind of social media marketing tools are being used currently in small and medium-sized restaurants in London?
- What benefits and uses can social media marketing offer to small and medium-sized restaurants in London?
- How can restaurant managers better prepare and equip themselves for developing and extracting benefits from social media apps?

1.5.2 Research Objectives

- To review and discuss the theoretical concepts of social media marketing in the business context.
- To evaluate the effectiveness and benefits of social media apps as a marketing tool.
- To analyse and discuss the features of social media apps that affect consumer buying behaviour.
- To devise a set of recommendations to improve the adoption and implementation of social media apps in small and medium-sized restaurants in London.

1.6 Proposed Methodology

This research study has proposed to use qualitative methodology for collecting and analysing the data. It has been proposed to make use of subjective views and opinions of carefully selected respondents from within the restaurants industry of the UK. The proposed methodology is intended to be in line with the scope of research objectives and the rationale established behind this research study. Purposive sampling is proposed to be used for selecting the respondents from small and medium sized restaurants in the UK. A comprehensive research

design will be presented in the research methodology chapter after completing the literature review and conceptual framework chapters.

1.7 Outline and Structure of Thesis

This research study consists of six distinct and interrelated chapters with each chapter offering unique insights. The first chapter outlines the research aim and objectives to establish the route of the study; all the other chapters have to be aligned with the research direction established by the aim and objectives. Motivations and reasons behind undertaking this research study are presented in the first chapter against a backdrop of facts, arguments and assumptions. After describing the context of this study in Chapter 1, the second chapter summarises a literature review of the concepts and factors embedded in the research aim and objectives. Different theoretical perspectives and empirical-based understanding published by research scholars are presented in the literature review chapter.

The second chapter is also about developing and explaining conceptual framework which is in line with the research objectives and literature review findings presented in the first two chapters. Conceptual framework is presented in the form of a graphical picture and textual description has been provided. Chapter 3 is about developing the research methodology with the help of which data has to be collected and analysed. This chapter discussed the chosen methodology and approach of research along with presenting the justifications and reasons behind the selection. Tools of data collection and methods of analysis have been presented in this chapter, which are aligned with the scope and direction of the research objectives. Chapter 4 presents the results gathered after the application of the chosen methodology. Chapter 5 contains the interpretations and findings extracted from the results in the light of a critical discussion. Themes and sub-themes are also presented in this chapter, which highlights the key findings. Chapter 6 concludes the research by providing concluding remarks and by presenting the contributions and recommendations made by this study. Research limitations are discussed, future research directions are described, and the research and managerial implications of this study are summarized.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The theories and arguments of different scholars and researchers will be discussed in this chapter. Secondary data sources including journal articles, textbooks and industry reports will be used for this purpose. The literature reviewed was published in the last 3–5 years with exception given to definitions and theories.

The internet, specifically social media, has changed communication between consumers and marketers. Changes in consumer conduct have led companies to reconsider their market policies in the digital sphere (Trusov et al., 2014). At the present time, an essential part of associated research is comparatively more engrossed in the client than in the company. The second generation of internet-based applications changed marketing endeavours because they enabled companies to use creative forms of communication through which content can be co-created with clients (Tiago and Verissimo, 2014). The significant advantage of the internet is that it has facilitated businesses to approach customers all over the world. Resultantly, customers feel comfortable about examining, opt as well as purchasing commodities from around the world (Blazquez, 2014). Specifically, the emergence of a new form of consumer socialization, namely peer communication via the internet, has had a strong effect on consumers' decision capabilities and business's marketing policies. Consumer socialization theory anticipates that communication among purchasers influences their mental, emotional and behavioural perspectives (Ward, 1974).

People are being facilitated with effective area through social media, specifically social networking sites in order to have communication via internet. Which perhaps poses as a significant agent of consumer socialization. Literature on social media and online consumers' behaviour is reviewed in the next two sections (Vinerean et al., 2014). Numerous advanced countries have rapidly headed towards digitalization during the previous decade. People can quickly and easily interact with each other due to the existence of social media platforms. Firms are required to participate in this connectivity to enhance brand and commodity awareness. Careful examination of consumer conduct is central to marketing success. Particularly because large numbers of consumers use socializing tools over the internet (Iankova et al., 2018).

The online audience is a flourishing market around the globe; however, a cross-cultural dissection is needed despite its globalized nature. This literature review will pave the way to the study of internet marketing in relevance to educational consequences.

2.2 The Concept of Social Media

2.2.1 Definition and Purpose

According to the *Cambridge Dictionary*, fundamentally, social media are websites and applications that allow the masses to create and share content as well as participate in social networking. However, this Definition could apply to many of today's websites (Kane et al., 2020). Consequently, a small number of people seem to believe in a narrower definition of social media and think of it as identical to social networking. Moreover, some people do not regard blogs as a component of social networking. This conflict in opinions can rapidly lead to confusion. To find a clear meaning of social media each word can be examined thoroughly. First, "social" refers to communicating with others for the purpose of exchanging information with them (Levy et al., 2020). Second, media denotes the tools through which communication is possible. Taking into account the above two mentioned definitions, it can be concluded that social media refers to a range of web-based communication tools through which consumers interact with others for the purpose of exchanging and receiving information. TV and newspapers are part of traditional media. These are not regarded as components of social media (Muller et al., 2018).

However, the continuing evolution of this new form of network increasingly blurs the boundaries between social media and traditional media (Aloini et al., 2021). One may ask what is the difference between social networking and social media? As mentioned above, social media is interpreted as identical to social networking by a small number of people. There is a minor distinction between social media and social networking: social networking can be defined as a component of social media. It is understandable why the author considers social media as relating to people's sharing of content, such as videos, music, photos and opinions. Social media alludes to the idea of Web 2.0, which includes open-source, interactive and client-controlled online applications that assist clients to share their experiences as members of business and social circles. The formation of clients' informal networks along with the diffusion of user-generated content, which provides a flow of information and knowledge, is

backed by Web 2.0 applications. Social media has been identified as a significant channel that businesses can access to approach the market and achieve business objectives (Bones et al., 2018; Lamberton and Stephen, 2016). Social media enables companies to acquire numerous objectives that go beyond commonly possessing a direct connection with users. These include, for instance, identification of recent business platforms, conveyance of commercial and institutional content, reserve of customer responses and the formation of communities (Foss and Saebi, 2017; Ritz et al., 2019).

Social media and social networking have gained popularity during recent years. For example, it is said that there are more than one billion active Facebook users. They have gained recognition as friendly networks for both professional and social communications (Ghobakhloo, 2020). Social networks not only help users to propagate information, but also help users to digest the information shared on the internet (Gupta, 2018). The unique characteristics associated with social media have also helped to revolutionize marketing practices, such as promotions and advertising (Hanna et al., 2011). In addition, online social networks make it extremely easy to exchange and access information on the internet (Akrimi and Khemakhem, 2012). Marketing exercises, for instance publicizing and encouragement, have been transformed with the help of the distinctive features of social media and its massive popularity (Hanna et al., 2011). The interaction of a company with customers has also been extended from data gathering to post-buy conduct for instance disappointment proclamations or conducts (Mangold and Faulds, 2013) and trends of internet utilization (Jeschke, 2017). Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) pointed out the numerous merits of social media, such as it helps link businesses with clients, and it initiates and encourages connections in a punctual way and at a cheap cost.

2.2.2 Benefits and Limitations

Influencing and dominating interpretations, perspectives and end conduct are incorporated in the other purposes of social media, while carrying together various similar-minded individuals (Bocconcelli et al., 2017). Drummond et al. (2018) stated that many individuals like to be members of an online community because it fulfils their needs for belongingness, being socially related and identified, or, commonly, having the pleasure of relationships with other similar-minded members. The number of facilities that are offered by social media encouraged businesses to take up new channels, such as Twitter, Facebook and Myspace, for the purpose

of succeeding in online surroundings (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010; Cartwright et al., 2021). Nunan et al. (2018) indicated that a large number of industries strive to take advantage from social media as they can be utilized to evolve plan, admit their characters in handling others' plan or accompany others' ways.

Social media channels also provide opportunities for firms to be in contact with possible and recent clients, and to enhance clients' sense of closeness to the firm, which is important because clients' loyalty can be lost if there is a service failure and clients can communicate their unfortunate experience with other people in the community through online channels (Felix et al., 2018). On some corporate social networking websites, clients can not only share information regarding commodities or services, but also be involved in co-forming through interaction on online as well as offline channels (Iankova et al., 2018).

Social media is not suitable for all businesses. Extra resources may be required to handle a company's online existence; social media is instant and requires daily monitoring. Monitoring is necessary because there is a possibility of undesirable or unsuitable conduct on companies' sites, including bullying and harassment (Hofacker et al., 2020). Risks can possibly be attracted by higher subjection online. Pessimistic response, revelation of information or hacking can be incorporated in risks. Managers and clients are subject to consumer law on making incorrect or deceptive claims on a company's social media channels (Hazzam, 2021). Clients' fan posts and recommendations that deceive or mislead other clients, specifically with respect to commodities/services, may lead to the imposition of penalties on the business (Rodrigues et al., 2021). However, possessing a social media strategy and constructing an organizational plan and method thoroughly before developing a social media presence can help companies manage the dangers (Mahdiraji et al., 2019).

Companies will require resources to handle their social media existence, including responding to content and creating new content. This can incorporate recruiting and instructing employees, spending money on publicity and the costs of creating video or image content (Sundstrom et al., 2017). While the return on investment (ROI) in respect of online sales produced by social media publicizing can be easily measured, there are other intangible benefits. Intangible benefits such as brand consciousness and fame on social media are not easy to quantify or financially value (Lashgari et al., 2018). Occasionally, social media cannot be utilized productively. For instance, utilizing social media to exert force for sales without engrossing with clients or failing to react to negative responses may harm a company (Cheung et al., 2021).

Marketers should locate and examine a connection between ROI and social media. The way-to-buy from social media, mostly utilized to enhance consciousness and instruct clients, is mostly not direct procedure and clients may have to be directed through well-recognized sales and marketing channels (Salo, 2017). A successful marketing campaign requires marketers to examine their data to discover the correct audience. These leads can be transformed into purchases in the long term (Ma et al., 2021).

2.2.3 Evolution and Trends in social media

The way how businesses function, people reside, and clients' store has varied due to advancement in technology. According to World Internet Stats (2014), around 45% of the world's population (nearly 3.1 billion people) are online users. The British government predicted that there would be more interrelated electronic gadgets than residents by 2015 (UK Government, 2010). Significant changes have been noted in businesses that provide monetary and other services as a reaction to advanced internet technologies and web-based services. The internet has become a monetary communication channel between consumers and businesses (Chaffey and Smith, 2019). Consumer satisfaction and uncertainty are two of the variables that have affected the adoption of e-banking (Felix et al., 2017). It has been observed that the adoption of online banking and commerce has not grown at the same pace as the online sharing of knowledge and social media interactions.

Social media are dependent on cell phone and web-based technologies that enable the co-creation, exchange, examination and modification of content by people and communities. Innovations emerge every day; the outcome is that social media is in a position of rapid development. Innovations change the ways in which different entities interact, such as communities, individuals, governments, colleagues and organizations (Li et al., 2021).

Social media is also seen as an instrument of dialogue that allows the sharing of a variety of resources to a number of receivers, whereas traditional media acted in a monologue form where the same message was conveyed to a number of receivers (Orji et al., 2020). Several models of management have developed through which patterns of social media management can be better understood. All members receive input from a variety of sources at the same time which provides a multidimensional variety of users. The online utilization of social network sites (SNSs) has seen a large increase (see Figure 2); it was estimated there were 1.40 billion users

of SNSs in 2012, 1.96 billion users in 2015 and 2.13 billion users by the end of 2016 (Statista, 2016).

Figure 2: Number of world users on social network sites from 2010 to 2018

Source: Statista (2016)

Another proof of the development of SNSs utilization signifies the significance of these networks is the link it carries with engagement and management where, huge and frequently various collections of people facilitating social support. People use SNSs to gather functional and useful knowledge, information, data and other resources (Allen et al., 2020). The merits of accessing SNSs include the development of social connections, interactions and societies, which may be described as the social capital results of SNS utilization (Rodrigue et al., 2021). Some researchers went beyond exploring the merits of SNSs and looked at elements through which enhanced results can be provided to parties of SNSs, which include consumers, governments and businesses (Siti-Nabiha et al., 2021). There is a need to examine how consumers utilize these instruments and combine them into their businesses and lives.

Use of social media as a Marketing Tool

Marketing can attract and gratify consumers and keep them faithful to a brand. The idea of marketing is strongly associated with the study of connection between brand and its possibilities with recent consumers. Some individuals interpret marketing as a process; others interpret it as an idea. Marketing was defined as “the exercise, collection of organizations, and procedures for forming, communication, conveying and sharing proposals that possess worth for consumers, partners and society” at large by the American Marketing Association (2013).

Kotler, in 2006, considered marketing a method of exchange, the aim of which is to fulfil an individual's requirements and desires. Theoreticians like Kotler and Keller described marketing as a method that incorporates market exploration, aiming and separation, unfolding of plans concerning pricing, encouragement and distribution, growing communication and advancement of long-lasting objectives (Gupta et al., 2021). However, these measures are continually developing as the market varies through the years.

The definitions of marketing given above describe it as a procedure. Marketing was first defined by Adam Smith (1776) as an idea in order to predict the requirements and desires of clients for the purpose of satisfying them better than contenders. Whether marketing is regarded as a procedure or as an idea, both doctrines express consent on the reality that marketing is directly related to clients' satisfaction and to recognizing their requirements and desires. Consequently, the author would like to emphasize the distinction between requirements and desires. Requirements refer to something that is essential for an individual's survival (*Cambridge Dictionary*, 2017). Non-fulfilment of a requirement, such as food and water, may contribute to dysfunction or demise. Desires, however, refer to something that people aspire to. Desires are not mandatory for survival (*Cambridge Dictionary*, 2017); they are frequently the outcome of a culture or a group association that is not anti-social.

Definitions of marketing vary because marketing constantly develops. In reality, a society varies through the years and marketing is adjusted to meet individuals' needs. Consequently, marketing, which was primarily regarded as an innovative offshoot, is currently regarded as a science, which needs studies and market exploration. With the development of marketing over time, distinct forms of marketing emerged. Digital marketing is one of the outcomes of those forms. More than 4 billion individuals are normally connected online for 6 hours every day (Statista 2018). Today, digitalization is an essential component of survival, and it helps people to connect with friends, track information and so on. Consequently, digital brands have to be well connected to be identified by consumers. Social media marketing comes under the domain of digital marketing. Digital marketing is utilized on social media for the purpose of enhancing brand consciousness, to commence and handle communications, and to share the perceptions of individuals or groups with various aims.

Social media marketing came into existence due to the creation of Web 2.0 and the expansion of social media consumers; the key aim behind social media marketing is to connect with the large number of users that are present online. The more valuable a directive is to a client, the

more the client shares it with their network. In accordance with this, social media marketing can be regarded as functioning as a huge word-of-mouth (WOM) procedure. Social media marketing permits firms to combine some present community by commencing communications and pay attention directly to their clients and possibilities. Social media marketing is utilized by numerous firms as a marketing tool. For instance, research signifies that 80% of destiny five hindered firms were not inactive on the key SNS sites, which include Twitter and Facebook, in 2013 according to marketing research carried out by University of Massachusetts in 2014.

Consequently, it is difficult to stand out from competitors. Due to the merits of social media marketing, it is utilized by numerous firms. In fact, social media marketing permits firms to accumulate clients' experiences with the help of review conversations and grading systems. Moreover, it is not difficult to recognize and approach emphasizes' groups and clients' communities, which can pose as brand diplomats and lead to the development of brand awareness. Additionally, a strong advantage of social media marketing is that the costs are not high. In reality, most social media channels are free; therefore, it is one of the cheapest ways to do marketing. However, it is not easy to assess the profitability of marketing conducted on social media. It appears that everyone is aware that there are numerous advantages for a brand of being active on social media stages; however, it is not easy to convert these advantages into measurable characteristics, for example, money.

A report was issued by BI Intelligence (2013) in which they assessed the possible advantages for brands to function on social media stages. Additionally, it stated which channels the brands used. To become well known and identified, a brand is required to approach many clients. Currently, where spectators make use of their time and pay concentration is the prime point of a sound communication plan. Consequently, brands that do not appear on social media cannot avail themselves of the opportunities to interact and share with their clients, which in some situations can contribute to a competitor's benefit. Moreover, brands are supposed to be attentive: social media marketing is not regarded as easy. Social media marketing requires the pursuit of a well-planned plan, and the conveyed directive is supposed to be vivid.

Common Pitfalls in Utilizing Social Media Marketing

Primarily, it is extremely important for a brand to utilize the correct social media platforms. Although social media marketing is not expensive, businesses should spend resources and time on it. If a brand is on the incorrect platform, it could incur financial losses and fail to achieve its objectives. A mistake that businesses frequently make is to commence their marketing on social media platforms with which they are familiar, but their account becomes inactive. Each marketer has a restricted amount of time to utilize for social media marketing, consequently it is recommended to choose two platforms and engage in interactions. “The truth is, it is better to not have a social media icon on your website if you are not going to actively engage it” (Hudson, 2017, p. 19).

It is important to understand that platforms differ from one another. Consequently, every platform has its own effect on marketing. In accordance with former research formulated by Harmony Digital in 2017, it seems that Interest is the social media website that is the finest extra commodity information giver. It signifies individuals are more probably to believe extra commodity information that derives from this stage instead of another. Twitter is the greatest as commodity finding instrument and Facebook as commodity sale or buy alert (Harmony Digital 2017). The social media platforms that are likely to affect purchase decisions are Facebook, YouTube and LinkedIn.

Another mistake that firms frequently make is to have conversations related to something that is important to them, instead of conversations about things that are of concern to their clients (Hudson, 2017). In fact, it is important to comprehend that social media marketing is highly related to sharing with the client instead of encouraging commodities. Social media marketing is based on interactions with customers and the forming of a picture of the brand to make clients feel close to the brand. In order to feel close to a brand, clients require to feel esteemed by the brand. Interrogating their perspectives and paying attention to their comments is one of the greatest ways to make clients feel esteemed. A firm that merely shares content on social media platforms is not fully competent. Moreover, brands are supposed to commence communication and respond to users’ remarks and requests (Kapferer, 2011). Firms should be active on social media on a daily basis; it is not merely a once in a while occupation.

The Impacts of social media on Societies and Customers

According to Muniz and O'Guinn, (2001), social media has a significant influence on the involvement and engagement of customers in purchasing decisions through different platforms. It converts marketing purpose and intention towards customer's involvement instead of communicating messages to receivers. Moreover, social media enables users to investigate information provided by marketers on products before they select a product. Muniz Jr. and Schau (2005) determined that WOM on social media has a positive impact on societies. They asserted that consumers gain information and knowledge regarding products from contributing to online communities. It encourages customers to involve in the projects through detailed information and understanding of tools and techniques used by business to convey message accordingly.

Lin and Lu (2011) also stated that social media has a significant impact on customers as it provides complete and relevant information to customers regarding products and services. Social media helps communities to make an effective purchasing decision while considering price ranges and quality of goods as compared to substitute products. However, it has a negative influence on the customer's mind depicting the marketing messages converted into different narratives or stories on social media platform. It involves a factor of understanding of messages and miscommunication of information i.e., how it has been perceived by users (Muntinga et al., 2011). Algesheimer et al. (2010) found that belonging to the eBay customer community exaggerated customers' behaviour and intentions on the website negatively; and a business cannot predict how it has been perceived. It depicts that continuous marketing of a product along with regular messages and reminders led customers to make a wrong decision involving a factor of time and offers provided by the business. Moreover, it also intends customers to leave the platform where continuous reminders are sent to purchase.

Wang and Fesenmaier (2003) also presented the consequence of online comments on customers through the usage of models designed to predict online behaviour that reflects on a company's performance in terms of sales. Empirical evidence exhibited that the impact on consumers' purchase decisions of online WOM is much greater than had previously been assumed (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004; Sonnier et al., 2011).

2.3 Consumer Behaviour Concept

2.3.1 Purpose and Definition

As per Ali (2021), the concept of consumer behaviour is explained as the process of buying, using disposing goods and service by customers and different organizations in order to meet their requirements. It usually studies actions performed by consumers in the marketplace along with their motive to perform an action such as extend in buying decision or habitual buying behaviour. Daroch et al. (2021) revealed that better understanding of user behaviour online can help in a number of domains, such as effective marketing decisions, selecting target users, helping managers, and designing and communicating effective marketing techniques. Consumer behaviour has changed rapidly in recent years, which also created the need to develop a marketing plan while keeping in view an understanding of consumer behaviour.

Aziz et al. (2018) explained that customers spend time and effort on research, comparing the quality and price range of multiple products, while making a decision. The ratings of products and services are also assessed and discussed with other buyers and business professionals. The process of a buying decision is dependent on the behaviour of customers. It is essential that businesses understand the behaviour of customers because it not only helps businesses to improve their sales performance, but it also helps them to improve the implementation and adoption of effective sale strategies in the future (Gok, 2020). Consumers' buying behaviour involves buying decisions for self and for friends and family members while analysing the provided information and comparing ratings with substitute products. Moreover, consumer behaviour is the intellectual and physical assessment of activities undertaken by individuals and business entities that result in decisions and actions to pay for, purchase, and use products and services offered on online platforms. Thus, consumer behaviour deals with the buying behaviour of consumers for both products and services through detailed analysis of information provided (Fazal e Hassan et al., 2020).

To create and retain customers, businesses analyse customers' needs and requirements and assess their attitude towards buying a product. The purpose of understanding a customer's behaviour is to find out how a customer usually behaves while purchasing a product or service so that their requirements can be met; this knowledge can be used to advertise products and share the information desired by customers when making a decision.

In the marketing context, the concept of “consumer behaviour” is not only related to the act of purchasing a product, but it also pertains to aggregate buying elements, which include pre-purchase and post-purchase activities by a customer (Guzel et al., 2021).

Pre-purchase activity is the first step of the buying process; it is the step in which customers identify and assess the options for purchasing the goods they desire. It consists of a growing awareness of goods and services and an evaluation of information about the products and brands that might satisfy their requirements. On the other hand, post-purchase activities are the last stage of the buying procedure; they include evaluation of the already bought item and determine the level of satisfaction and dissatisfaction (Liljedal and Berg, 2020).

Benefits and Limitations of Consumer Behaviour Concept

In the view of Kautish and Dash (2017), knowledge of consumer behaviour is important for business as it helps marketers to understand consumers’ thinking and attitude, how consumers evaluate and select products or brands, and how consumers are influenced by their environment, reference groups, family and salespersons. Understanding consumer behaviour can lead businesses to understand customers’ expectations and determine the factors that attract customers to purchase a product. Past studies showed that consumers’ buying behaviour is influenced by cultural, social, personal and psychological factors. The personal factors include stage of product life cycle, income and lifestyle along with their self-concept. The social factors include the role and status of friends and family groups as they play an essential role in purchasing choice and behaviour. Matharu et al. (2021) revealed that most of the affecting factors cannot be controlled by marketers, but the factors are considered essential to understanding the behaviour of consumers. The study of consumer behaviour concept is crucial in the context of marketing because it supports firms’ development of appropriate marketing strategies by giving an insight into the factors influencing the decision making of consumers. Understanding a consumer’s thinking and emotions enables marketers to attract the consumer to products or services (Ngarmwongnoi et al., 2020).

Solomon (2009) stated that the buying decisions of consumers are affected by various factors, such as education, status and lifestyle, income level and stage of economic development, information and size of family. Businesses’ understanding of consumer behaviour helps them to comprehend the factors related to product offerings and how a specific consumer or group reacts to decisions of buying a product. The main determination behind marketing a product is to advertise and communicate new offerings and satisfy the demands and needs of consumers.

In this regard, marketers' understanding of consumer behaviour concepts helps them to identify potential and targeted markets as per the nature of goods and services and offer goods accordingly. An analysis of customers' behaviour encourages business growth and boosts profitability (Temporal, 2015).

However, the concept of customer behaviour is limited to the attitude and belief of customers; the marketplace is not assessed in this technique, for example, external factors such as market demand for a product or price inflation is not assessed. Another limitation for marketers using the consumer buying behaviour model is that consumers sometimes are not involved in a lengthy purchase decision but make a rapid decision to buy a product (Zakaria et al., 2021). For instance, someone buying laundry detergent is generally less involved in the purchase than someone buying a car or washer and dryer. Thus, the ability of marketers to affect consumers by analysing buyer behaviour is limited. Consumers that are less involved spend less time seeking or viewing information about the purchase.

2.3.2 Critique of Consumer Behaviour Models

Research and literature on consumer behaviour have been conducted on a vast array of topics, which include research on psychometric scaling, buying decision processes, attitude research, post-purchase attitudes and other cognitive processes. Theories have also been developed on subtopics in these areas (Nicosia, 1982), such as diffusion of innovation theories, attribution theory and cognitive dissonance theory. However, models (or theories) of consumer (or buyer) behaviour are the most significant development in the field of consumer behaviour. Consumer behaviour models have been critically analysed; past critical evaluations were carried out on technical grounds (i.e., methodological), which covered the areas of legitimacy, quantification and provability of the concepts and variables in these models (Jacoby, 1978). The material and conceptual wholeness of these models shall be targeted with self-criticism efforts.

Models/theories are developed within a social context and time and are applicable under these. Applying models/theories to other contexts creates problems and difficulties. Context is critical as otherwise it causes imbalances. Consumer behaviour models face this developmental limitation. Such is the limitation that once the demand (or need) for a commodity is given, then only behaviour models can explain the decision process which takes place as a result (Belch and Belch, 2014; Sumi and Ahmad, 2021); therefore, the reallocation of resources due to a change in demand, which is itself due to product shortage, cannot be explained.

Due to this, in seller's market situation, an understanding or assumption has prevailed that the goods made will be sold whatsoever or even that they can be sold without any marketing measures.

Consumer behaviour models have been evaluated and criticized on four major points, namely variables, relationships and concepts that are required to be examined and researched so that an understanding and realization of social realities in consumption are assumed as given. In consumer research, technological-managerial orientation is more dominant than scientific orientation. The studies focus on buyers and do not consider them in the light of consumers as these studies develop only micro-theories (Markin, 1974; Kotler, 1973; Hansen, 1973). The "Five-stage model of the consumer buying process" (Figure 3) is the traditional model of consumer decision-making process. It depicts that a consumer takes five steps from start until finish when a product/service is consumed (Hawkins et al., 2013). Product marketing personnel have to take a grip of these five steps and guide the consumer through these five steps by communicating with them, resulting in finalization of sale.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Hawkins D.I., Mothersbauch D.L. & Best R.J. (2013) Consumer behaviour: Building Marketing Strategy, 10th ed., McGraw-Hill/Irwin.

Figure 3: Five-stage model of the consumer buying process

Source: Hawkins et al. (2013)

The modern concept of McKinsey's model (2009) has its basis in the traditional model elaborated above. It is relevant despite facing criticism. The "moments that matter" of the traditional model in decision making and factors were established and verified. These relationships can be researched and/or proved or rejected. Scholars have added to the traditional model. McAlister (1979) challenged the existing assumption of time in consumer behaviour that is the product is chosen separately from one another. The alternate model offered by him included a relationship/dependence of items pertain to a group.

Solomon et al. (2012) was critical of the fact that the traditional model has a rational perspective, whereas individuals do not behave rationally; they stated: “such a process is not an accurate portrayal of many of our purchase decisions”. Whenever a consumer is buying something, they do not follow a sequence. Solomon et al. (2012) elaborated on the theory of purchase momentum: an impulse or a sudden urge to buy a product does not lead to a planned purchase. Furthermore, they stated that consumers have several strategies in their kitty that they utilize based on the need of the situation and the amount of effort required, which is also known as constructive processing. They also discussed the influence of the experimental and behavioural viewpoint.

2.3.3 The Four Types of Buying Behaviours

As per T`et al. (2019, p. 10), customer behaviour can be explained as “all activities associated with the purchase, use and disposal of goods and services” and “the consumer's emotional, mental and behavioural responses that precede or follow these activities”. Four factors influence consumer behaviour; they are psychological, personal, cultural and social. There are many types of customer purchase decision behaviours. Kotler (2012) explained four types of decision behaviour that are based on the different levels of brand’s unique identification and customers’ attachment. The four types are habitual buying behaviour, dissonance-reduction buying behaviour, complex buying behaviour and variety-seeking buying behaviour (Mishra, 2015).

If the customer is extremely involved in the buying process, then it can be said that this is a complex buying behaviour phenomenon. The customer tries to make an effort and spend time gathering information about the product with respect to its functions and features. In complex buying behaviour, brand image is critical for the customer. (Mishra, 2015). This type of customer behaviour can be seen when the customer is buying a high value product, or the customer has the intention to use the product for a long period of time. A car is a good example of such a product. Dissonance-reduction buying behaviour is the second type of customer buying behaviour. Under such behaviour, the customer is extremely involved but, on the other hand, has very low brands differentiation (Zhang et al., 2020). The customer is highly vigilant when it comes to the product’s features and characteristics but does not delve into the practice of comparing and evaluating similar products offered by other brands/companies.

This type of behaviour can be observed when a customer is buying an easily available product. Another type of customer behaviour is variety-seeking buying behaviour. This behaviour is shown by customers when they are not very involved in the purchase process; however, at the same time, they effectively compare similar products offered by different brands. Such behaviour applies mostly in the case where the goods/services are in the low-price bracket (Rambabu and Porika, 2020). This type of customer behaviour is difficult for brands/companies to handle. There is always the threat that customers may switch brands if they are not satisfied. Habitual buying behaviour is the fourth and final customer behaviour. This covers the behaviour when normal day-to-day purchases of goods/services are being made (Close and Kukar-Kinney, 2012). The customers under this type are indifferent to the process as well as to the different products offered by competing brands. This Thesis is on chocolate factory where customers' variety-seeking buying behaviour may be observed. In this case the customer is not highly involved and does not even compare different options and brands. However, if the customer does not get the required satisfaction, they have the option to switch brands (Styven et al., 2017).

2.3.4 Theoretical Perspectives of Consumer Behaviour

This section is focused on theoretical aspects relating to this research. The aspects covered in the sub-sections revolve around two main theoretical areas, which are social exchange theory (SET) and social impact theory, as these are the two theories most relevant to the objectives of this research.

2.3.4.1 SET

SET states that social exchange occurs when more than one individual exchange tangible or intangible activities for different rewards or incurs different costs (Blau, 1964). SET focuses on different perspective to study human behaviour in interacting with others and defines how social stability can help social parties negotiate exchange (Ekeh, 1974; Cook and Emerson, 1978). SET is used by experts in different fields, including marketing. In marketing, SET is used as an additional way to study customer engagement with a brand and its potential impacts (Hollebeek, 2011). Based on the theory, it is predicted that customers can develop feelings and perceptions towards brands as per the benefits earned by them from the brand or costs incurred (Lin et al., 2014).

Therefore, a social exchange includes all unknown obligations that one marketer has towards the consumers. An example of such a relationship is that marketers can be motivated to provide high-quality products or services to their customers while expecting them to provide returns in future in the form of brand loyalty (Rousseau, 1989; Hollebeek, 2011). In the view of SET, customers have the option to take decisions to undergo specific acts or develop a positive attitude to a brand. WOM and electronic WOM have helped businesses develop social exchange relations with customers (Hollebeek, 2012).

It is further argued that when a product sells well, satisfied customers may become tools encouraging others through positive reviews to purchase this product. However, the dynamics of the impact of on developing purchase intentions of electronic WOM, knowledge related to the brand, and loyalty of the customer towards the services and products remains a hot topic for investigation (Cropanzano et al., 2017). Mainly, when dealing with SNS exchanges, it continues to be important to understand what impact the informational exchange has when it takes place directly among the members of a group or indirectly with friends beyond the group members, or with another group of members.

Debate and Criticism of SET

One of the most prominent aspects lying within the management is SET carrying a direct connection with social psychology and sociology. One of the key criticisms of SET is related to the absence of theoretical precision; for this reason, many scholars believe in its limited application (Cropanzano et al., 2016; Nguyen et al., 2016). Researchers utilizing SET in their research are certainly able to explain a particular phenomenon in a post-hoc manner; however, they face difficulties in making suitable predictions related to the organizational environment. The concepts linked with SET are quite complicated because of their subjective nature (Cropanzano et al., 2017). For instance, if an individual is rewarded for his performance, where it is annoying the other ones. Moreover, there is a quite limitation in SET related to the existence of different alternatives along with the costs and rewards element (Tanrikulu, 2021).

SET does not have a proper rationale for explaining the reason behind the ending of a relationship and it does not inform about the actual reasons for comparisons carried out with other people. This means that the perspective of SET lies heavily on the individual without taking care of the relationship's social aspects (Levine and Kim, 2010). The principles of SET are mainly only applicable to individualistic cultures.

SET also assumes that the individuals involved in a relationship reserve some profit and loss for themselves. Clark and Mills (2011) agreed with this notion; however, it is mainly acceptable in an exchange kind of relationship that exists between colleagues.

SET does not carry equal significance in the case of romantic relationships, where rewards are shared freely. Moreover, the research findings indicate that the relationship fairness delivers more happiness to the individuals instead of balance achieved by them in those relationships (Cropanzano et al., 2017). This implies that SET applies to a limited type of social relationship.

Another key issue with SET is related to the cause-and-effect assumption. For instance, some people start questioning their partners even before they are unsatisfied with their relationship (Argyle, 1987). This implies that the partners are mainly interested in their relationship fairness instead of worrying about the rewards. It contradicts the SET assumption by which the profits and losses are always taken into consideration by the individuals when making any decision related to their relationship (Mitchell and Cropanzano, 2010; Redmond, 2015).

However, it is important to mention that SET has some useful benefits. For example, Argyle (1987) informed about integrated behavioural couple therapy that encourages partners to increase the amount of exchange with each other to reduce the negative one's proportion and enhance the positive one's proportion. Christensen et al. (2004) reported that about two-thirds of couples make use of integrated behavioural couple therapy to have a positive impact on each other and make their lives happy. This means that it is possible to make use of SET for a positive purpose in relationships to achieve the best possible results.

One of the key criticisms of SET lies in the form of evaluating romantic relationships through a deterministic view. From a SET perspective, if an individual's costs for a relationship are higher than the rewards, then the individual would prefer to leave that relationship instead of living with the relationship that comes at a high cost to themselves (Cook et al., 2013). This means that SET comes with a limited predictive validity because it is unable to establish a certainty level related to the happiness or dissatisfaction of an individual with his or her relationship by merely focusing on costs and rewards (Christensen et al., 2004). It also contradicts one of the key claims of SET by which it claims to predict the behaviour of a human being as one of the psychological aspects.

SET is based on a quite complex phenomenon in which romantic relationships are associated with costs and benefits; it provides a limited number of real-time examples in this regard (Chuang, 2010). The theory also fails to provide a rationale for people staying in abusive relationships. This implies the need for a holistic approach to explain the level of complexity involved within the maintenance of romantic relationships.

SET mainly treats relationships as restricted or bilateral and generalized or multilateral exchanges delivering inappropriate results for making suitable conclusions. The behaviourist formulation of SET claims that a restricted exchange is always prioritized by individuals; where, on the ground level it indicates that mutual rewards are the key obligations motivating an individual to accept social norms (Blau, 1994; Homans, 1990). These limitations of the traditional SET contrast with the modern SET that focuses on exchange networks instead of dyads (Uehara, 1990; Bearman, 1997).

2.3.4.2 Social Impact Theory

Social impact theory, also known as the theory of social impact, is generally used to explain the impact of other people on the social behaviour of an individual (Rawhouser et al., 2019). In social impact theory, a social impact is created based on the interaction carried out between different people (Chuang, 2010). The theory proposes that when an individual is a target, where other people act as a source of impact, then it tends to create multiplicative functions based on the number, strength and immediacy of the people. The theory suggests that the behaviour and attitude of the targeted individual support in augmenting the social impact (Latane, 1981). Moreover, the impact on the individual is also increased as a result of a high number of people existing in the scenario. For instance, a person's mind is certainly influenced by viewing a large number of posts from other people in the same scenario over social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter. This means that the individuals' information collection and processing speed is paced up based on the information being shared with him through a large number of people magnifying the impact (Mir and Zaheer, 2012). It also justifies the usage of aggressive marketing by companies over social media to have a positive impact on customers' attention to boost sales.

One of the key implications of social impact theory is that presence of other people can have an impact on the behaviour and feelings of an individual (Chuang, 2010; Ham, 2017). This means that a group of several people carries the potential to impact multiple aspects within an

individual, including motives, subjective feelings, emotional state and beliefs, resulting in either positive or negative results (Latane, 1981). Social impact theory also has an explanation for categorizing different kinds of interactions as well as variables on the social extent as well as the direction of an individual. This theory certainly implies that many people can influence an individual; however, this theory also indicates that there are multiple general principles as well as variables that have a major impact on an individual (Kwahk and Ge, 2012).

Social impact theory can make use of equations for calculating the impact made by other people on the daily life of an individual (Vega et al., 2016). It is quite certain that an individual tends to experience a wide range of situations every day related to praise, dissatisfaction and happiness and is majorly being impacted by the existence of other people (Xiao and Hao, 2011). It can also apply to the online world as well, where individuals tend to communicate with each other regularly. Making use of social impact theory, three laws govern the impact of an individual; all of which can be expressed by making use of mathematical expressions like psychosocial law, social forces and division of impact (Xiao and Hao, 2011; Cook and Rice, 2016), where strength, number and immediacy are the key factors by an individual reply to the social impact being created by other people.

Debate and Criticism of Social Impact Theory

The number of scholars supporting social impact theory is generally increasing. For instance, the theory tends to offer wide value in studies carried out by different scholars, like Latane and Darley (1968) on the intermixing of responsibility, Tajfel (1970) on discrimination within intergroups and Miligram (1963) on obedience. All of these theories tend to evaluate the different perspectives of social impact. Some recent developments have also been made within the social impact theory. For example, Latane et al. (1996) processed dynamic social impact theory in relation to the impact made by majorities as well as minorities on each other as well as the change of perspective achieved by both communities because of each other.

It is necessary to mention that social impact theory mostly focuses on the individual responsible for giving the orders instead of the individual receiving the orders. For example, some personalities are quite rebellious in nature (Xiao and Hao, 2011); one person might be willing to follow orders if those orders are morally good and save them from any sort of perspective. Social impact theory tends to deal with individuals as passive (Basid et al., 2019; Line et al.,

2016), which means that a person will do any action if social force is exerted in the right direction. However, there are instances when people follow orders, but also subvert those orders at the same time.

Recently, many researchers attempted to evaluate social impact theory within the area of obedience and persuasion, within the core areas of social psychology. For instance, many researchers evaluated the effect of social impact on the behaviour of a consumer (Shaikh, 2016). For example, one research study varied the amount of presence existing within a store to evaluate the potential impact on the shopping behaviour of the consumer. Many key aspects of social impact theory also tend to predict the political involvement of an individual (Calvo Revilla, 2019). For example, the number of people who are eligible to vote is higher than the number of people who cast their votes. This behaviour tends to align with social impact theory by which the increasing margin of the social forces tends to impact the decision making of an individual (Chen and Sheng, 2013). Empirical as well as theoretical attention to social impact theory has increased massively leading towards the identification of interesting scientific phenomenon (Barua, 2013).

There is a lot of difference between social impact theory and other theories about social influence because social impact theory tends to adjust the immediacy as well as the strength of social influence instead of just focusing on the number of sources (Malter et al., 2020). There is a lot of criticism about social impact theory because of the way in which group influence tends to carry high implications (Calvo Revilla, 2019). For the same reason, the reformulation of social impact theory could be supportive in adjusting the influence of target sources leading towards the increased range as well as the validity of the targeted phenomenon (Shaikh, 2016). The integration of social impact theory with key areas of social psychology carries the potential to provide a contemporary perspective related to social influence.

2.4 Concept of Mobile Apps

2.4.1 Purpose and Definition

Advances in technology, the internet, and the development of smartphone technology and mobile applications has brought opportunities as well as challenges for organizations when it comes to the marketing of their products through this new channel.

But as the technology is still evolving, and on a daily basis, there is room for improvement as current branded apps are not perfect and well-established mobile and social features in these apps are next to non-existent (Pantano and Priporas, 2016). Chen et al. (2019) defined a (mobile) branded app as software that is downloaded to a smartphone from a platform that clearly displays its brand. Branding is done through the name of the app and the logo that appears on the app and the icon that appears while using the app. The advertising messages on apps are highly persuasive, which has resulted in their popularity (Beg et al., 2021).

In recent times, companies are aggressively pursuing mobile strategies and investing in portfolios of mobile phone applications. Caboni and Hagberg (2019) forecast that it would remain a challenge to develop mobile strategies and the popularity of branded apps would not diminish in the future. Companies have to embrace this new culture; the competencies and profiles of their marketing team have to be adjusted to this new consumer behaviour in the marketplace.

De Canio et al. (2021) determined that mobile marketing offers are accepted mainly based on the expected performance of the brand/app. Kanna and Li (2019) identified that customers'/users' primary reasons for using apps are the feature of learning, following a trend, functionality, entertainment, socialization, intellectual stimulation and information. But, to this day, there have been no studies that have found the features or characteristics that can be useful to brands/companies developing branded app strategies (Linnhoff and Smith, 2017; Sarkar et al., 2019). Companies have to clearly define business goals when deciding to create any mobile app(s); a single app may have multiple business objectives and a brand may opt for creating several mobile apps so that it can target and cater to different market niches, business goals and different products (Siregar and Kent, 2019).

Figure 4: Goals of branded apps

CRM, customer relationship management. Source: Zhao and Balagues (2015)

Figure 4 shows that branded apps have several goals with communication being their first goal. This goal can be further elaborated in that it includes, but is not limited to, communicating and informing about products, brand values and information, hence improving the brand image of the product and enhancing brand awareness among consumers and app users. Most companies make this goal the business objective incorporated in the app design (Zhao and Balagues, 2015). Customer relationship management (CRM) is the second goal of the branded apps' design as apps can be a vital and effective intermediary and link between brands and customers (Sprosen, 2014). The focus of the app is to communicate with existing customers as well as communicate with, and attract, new customers. The app is designed to collect user data and develop brand engagement with existing loyal and frequent consumers. Based on collected data, a branded app recommends products to existing customers and to new or possible customers.

Increasing revenue for the brand/company is the third goal of branded apps' design. By creating new purchasing experiences and new interaction mode for consumer/app user with the latest features of product customization, location awareness and context sensing in the app, companies intend to increase their overall sales (Zhao and Balagues, 2015). Innovation is the fourth goal. As technology is progressing and branded app design is based on technology, apps are a tool for innovation and allow open innovation. Apps may allow app users to propose new ideas for products or new brand strategies. Users can create a community or a group to share ideas, recommendations and ratings of products. The brand may adopt the most highly rated idea and the company/brand may reward the user for the idea (Tarute et al., 2017; Hussain et al., 2020).

Marketing research is the final goal of designing a branded app. Brands can build or link an external survey feature in an app and conduct surveys among its users. For example, in the shampoo industry some brands have enabled the feature of consumers posting their photos that they may upload after they have used the brand's products and share their good or bad experience on the app. This is value added and vital information that a brand's marketing team could use to improve their understanding of consumer behaviour (Zhao and Balagues, 2015).

2.4.2 Benefits and Limitations

As mobile devices have become more popular recently, firms have developed mobile applications as a new way to boost customer experience, revenue growth and eventually brand loyalty. In contrast to traditional advertising channels, the advertisements on mobile devices are interactive and have an immediate impact on customers. This highlights that firms can utilize app technology, which can allow customers to engage even when they are not at a particular place, such as home or office (Lee, 2018; Hesham et al., 2021).

As businesses observed the enhanced level of customer engagement with mobile devices, they developed apps of their own in a bid to communicate and advertise their offerings to attract new clients or engage with their current customers (Thakur, 2017). These apps allow customers to search, retrieve or share information within the application, pass time with the content available on the app, pay utility and other bills, and make purchases among other functions depending on the nature of brand (Amirkhanpour et al., 2014). For the shopping centres in specific, Olsson et al. (2013) studied the effectiveness of mobile apps and concluded that these apps are perceived by consumers to provide both cognitive and emotional benefits.

On the other hand, despite the widespread acceptance of mobile commerce, many firms have yet to adopt mobile applications and advertising. A survey of 445 business leaders found that the majority of the leaders agreed about the value and potential of mobile marketing, but only 45% of them acknowledged using mobile marketing and 37% stated that not having a mobile program already in place shows a lack of strategy (Wang et al., 2015).

A major reason for the short-term life of apps is that there are a lot of bugs in apps, which lead to abandonment of app. Perez (2013) reported that 79% of customers stated that they would not try an application more than twice if it failed during their first attempt. The way branded apps advertise products also changes the way consumers interact with the brand. As mobile devices are part of our daily use, brands' mobile applications can achieve objectives, which other advertising mediums cannot; for example, apps can actively prompt for frequent and immediate context-dependent recalls and alter the ways in which brand offerings are used by consumers. In summary, apps developed by brands are quite useful in persuading customers alongside ensuring their facilitation (Stocchi et al., 2019).

2.4.3 Understanding the Importance of Branded Mobile Apps for Businesses

This sub-section is focused on understanding the importance of branded mobile applications for businesses. Before understanding the nature of mobile applications and why these are important, it is important to explain the concept of mobile marketing. The concept is defined as “the two- or multi-way communication and promotion of an offer between a firm and its customers using a mobile medium, device, or technology” (Smith et al., 2021). Different tools of mobile marketing exist around the world today and persistent improvement in technology has extended its scope beyond Short Message Service, Multimedia Messaging Service and video marketing (Reade, 2020; Rietveld et al., 2020).

Mobile applications have been defined differently at technological and marketing/communication levels. The definition of an application can help in developing understanding in this regard. Cindy Krum defined mobile applications as “the multitude of small programs that can be installed after market on phones” (Tran et al., 2021). However, Chen et al. (2020) argued that mobile applications are not limited to the ones that can be installed after buying a phone. They stated that mobile applications are “software that are pre-installed on your mobile phone or are available to download from the internet” (Chen et al., 2020). They further stated that the concept of mobile applications is still novel around the world despite the fact that they have existed for several years in the form of utility tools and games in more complicated applications. Salimon et al.’s (2021) definition of mobile applications gives a deeper view and adds the value creation aspect; they stated that “Downloadable applications (apps) are defined as programs designed specifically to add functionality to mobile handsets and are able to interact directly with the technical features of the phone”.

On the other hand, the marketing definition of mobile applications has also been under radar in recent times. Bellman et al. (2011) is some of the pioneers who defined mobile applications from the perspective of marketing. Their definition of mobile applications stated that they are downloadable software to mobile devices, displaying a brand throughout the experience of using the application (Bellman et al., 2011; Croes and Bertels, 2021). In addition, Baykal (2020) stated that the function of mobile applications is to enable brands to connect with their current and prospective clients while assuring their convenience at all times.

Mobile applications by big corporations have become more common as compared to other mobile marketing tools. As the corporations have adopted apps for smartphones, the attention of all stakeholders has been diverted towards mobile app marketing to generate purchase intention and brand loyalty (Bellaaj, 2021). Branded apps help organizations engage by means of interactive advertisements as compared to launching traditional websites for the purpose of marketing (Bellman et al., 2011). To be specific, the presence of apps for smartphones allows businesses to advertise brands through different experiences and achieve the objectives of personal and mass marketing at the same time (Srivastava et al., 2021).

It is believed that a branded app for a smartphone enables consumers to access the business immediately, which also provides businesses with an opportunity to take advantage of the mobility offered. This highlights the difference in engagement experience of customers while using mobile apps or other internet tools (Cinar, 2020; Tran et al., 2021). As a result, one of the objectives of this research is to evaluate the impact of users' experiences of smartphone branded applications on their relationship with a brand and on their brand experiences as a whole.

Role of App Notifications in Informing and Attracting Consumers

It is important to define app notifications before considering their role and importance for brands and consumers. As per *Oxford Dictionary*, app notifications can be described as “a self-contained program or piece of software designed to fulfil a particular purpose”. Apps are available to customers for installation on devices such as tablets and smartphones (Olmstead and Atkinson, 2015). An app refers to software that leads to users being connected to the internet and acts as a portal. The use of apps and mobile marketing is on the rise because 68% of Americans own a smartphone today and have access to approximately 26 apps in a given month with total time spend equalling 37 hours. Further, the use of apps by smartphone users is continually increasing (Sarmah et al., 2020).

Cheng et al. (2021) reported that 89% of time spent on media by app users is on mobile apps and 11% is spent on mobile webs. It is argued that one of the key aspects that forces individuals to open mobile apps repeatedly is their notification system. App notifications are auditory and visual alerts that help users notice any development in relation to the application at hand, which can be a message or any other type of alert, which may be important for the user (Pielot et al., 2016; Karagkiozidou et al., 2019).

The core purpose of the development of options for notification within apps is to alert an individual immediately after something important has happened; the nature of the application or brand determines the type of notifications being sent to users.

App notifications can be classified into push and pull notifications. Push notifications are sent to the mobile devices of users and appear on the home screen/lock screen or in the boxes within the app; these notifications are not opted for by the user (Martin-Flatin, 1999). In other words, these notifications are used to send information to users by pushing it at a time that it is seen as desirable by the host/manager of the app. By contrast, pull notifications are received on users' request, for example, a request is filed by the user when searching for particular information using the app (Martin-Flatin, 1999).

The layout of new information can vary based on the nature of app. New content can be highlighted in novel ways. Only push notifications lead to pop-up messages and these are commonly used to send updates to users about brand activities and to engage them to generate higher brand value and purchase intention (Martin-Flatin, 1999). Customers find push notifications burdensome, especially when these do not offer something of value to the customers (Westermann et al., 2015). Computer-mediated features that are controlled by users are considered desirable by the users (Sundar et al., 2010).

It was found that applications that allow customers to customize push notifications are preferred. iOS and Android both allow users to manage push notifications; these services were launched in 2009 and 2010, respectively (Urban Airship, 2016). These systems allow customers using different operating systems on phones to customize the receipt of push notifications in particular. In addition, iOS also asks users whether to keep notifications on or off for a particular app after it is installed on a phone. At later stages, settings about push notifications can be changed from the settings of the respective app on iOS devices (see Figure 5).

A large black rectangular area covers the top two-thirds of the page, indicating redacted content. A white rectangular box with a red border is positioned at the bottom of this area, containing the following text:

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Sarin, P., Kar, A.K. and Ilavarasan, V.P. (2021), "Exploring engagement among mobile app developers - Insights from mining big data in user generated content", Journal of Advances in Management Research, Vol. 18 No. 4, pp. 585-608.

Figure 5: Notification customization features for iPhone

Source: Sarin et al. (2021)

As evident from the discussion, these options provide users with an option to control the way push notifications appear or sound if they are kept on or push notifications can be turned off as a whole. On the other hand, Android users are not provided with the option to turn off the notification at the time an app is installed. However, they can turn them off from the settings for the particular applications. Similar to iOS users, Android users can also customize the sound of and the way notifications appear on the screens of mobile phones (see Figure 6).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Sarin, P., Kar, A.K. and Ilavarasan, V.P. (2021), "Exploring engagement among mobile app developers - Insights from mining big data in user generated content", Journal of Advances in Management Research, Vol. 18 No. 4, pp. 585-608.

Figure 6: Notification customization features for Android

Source: Sarin et al. (2021)

The option to allow app users to customize notifications helps them gain some control over the app, which eventually improves users' perceptions of branded mobile applications.

Application of Holistic Brand Experience Theory

Earlier in this chapter, we used the theory on holistic brand experience by Schmitt (1999) to analyse each type of brand experience defined as “sensation, feelings, cognition, and behavioural responses evoked by brand-related stimuli that are all a part of a brand’s design, identity, packaging, communication, and environment” (Brakus et al., 2009, p. 52). Brand loyalty is defined as the willingness of customers to engage with and maintain relations with a brand (Aaker, 1996, p. 320). With the increase in popularity of different types of marketing, consumers today prefer to interact with brands virtually. This form of engagement differs notably from instore experiences as that was a direct selling experience. The academic interest in the recent times has expanded both online and offline (Fleming and Head, 2021).

This study focuses on holistic brand experience in relation to branded apps in particular. In addition, this study focuses on the moderating role of branded apps in the relationship between brand loyalty and experience using a particular application. Media involvement determines the importance of form of media, has been used in new media research (Collin-Lachaud and Diallo, 2021). This generates higher interest of consumers in messages being communicated by media

leading to higher media involvement. This motivated researchers to examine whether the use of mobile apps boosted the experience of customers dealing with Koran mobile companies. Despite an increasing interest in, and utilization of, branded applications, there is limited research work on branded applications, which highlights a potential research gap. Bellman et al. (2011) analysed the effectiveness of mobile applications in terms of their impact on purchase intention and brand attitude but left many gaps in the literature. Therefore, this study aims to identify the impact of branded apps on brand building through the use of empirical research data.

2.4.4 Understanding Branded Applications

Branded apps are considered attractive tools by businesses because they enable communication between the consumers and the business. Many big corporations and global brands, including Microsoft, Burger King, Pepsi and Unilever, have assured their presence on the internet through mobile applications (Jiang et al., 2021). The main reason for this is that the features of branded apps are notably different from those of traditional advertisements. Mobile marketing can be both pull based, and push based as discussed in an earlier section (it is based on the way notifications are sent to users). In the case of push notifications, the information to be received from apps can be controlled by users of iOS and Android phones (Bellman et al., 2011; Romaniuk and Sharp, 2018).

Mobile applications allow users to access the information they want regardless of when and wherever they need it, given that they have access to the internet at all times. This depicts the point of differentiation of apps from traditional methods of marketing; Turulja and Cinjarevic (2021) stated that branded apps are able to collect feedback from customers through real-time interactions with customers. Moreover, as branded applications use the latest technology it allows them to communicate more effectively with customers as compared to older communication methods. With the passage of time, smartphones are becoming more common around the world, which also allows marketers to focus on customer engagement using these apps as well (Tseng et al., 2021).

As discussed in the sub-section above, mobile applications have become a solid platform for interaction between consumers and brands. One of the best ways to create customer loyalty is to offer rewards using coupons. Reward systems form a strong way to manage the brand and generate customer loyalty (Kim et al., 2013). The retention of customers is one of the end goals

of modern-day organizations and one of the core steps to achieve it is to build brand loyalty by means of increased customer engagement. It is believed that the correct execution of a mobile app can help a business increase customer engagement to a significant extent. The impacts of mobile apps are not limited to the brand name and loyalty but can foster customer retention and returns for any given business (Miladian and Sarvestani, 2012; Lee, 2018).

Mobile apps, particularly unique and creative ones, can help brands connect with consumers in a highly competitive marketplace. The means of interaction between customers and brands have changed notably due to the presence of mobile applications. Mobile applications also allow businesses to generate true value for multiple stakeholders. To be successful in a competitive era, mobile apps need to cater to a particular need of customers. When an app is successfully integrated with business operations, its chances for success are generally high. However, an app must live up to consumer expectations; if the performance of an app is below expectations, the chances of its success are minimized (Lee, 2018).

Mobile marketing has risen to the top for businesses wanting to maintain a competitive edge and exploit new business opportunities (Gummesson, 2014; Kumar et al., 2018). Developing a mobile app is a highly optimal step for businesses, because it can help increase customer loyalty as compared to competitors using a website to achieve the same objective. Whenever consumers' app sessions are extended sessions, it leads to an opportunity for the business to improve customer relationships and brand value.

In the view of Cornfield (2021), the creation of applications that are customer-centric is important in order to achieve success for the business. The business model for mobile apps needs to be connected with the digital strategy at firm level with a primary focus on the needs, values and behaviour of customers. Mobile applications are generally unique, but they also share some characteristics, particularly those related to appeal, functionality and performance (see Figure 7); these characteristics need to be fulfilled by an application for it to be termed customer-centric (Cornfield, 2021).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at <https://hbr.org/2021/05/whats-your-customers-purpose>

Figure 7: Key elements of a successful mobile application

Source: Cornfield (2021)

Mobile apps help customers find out about the availability of products/services at a particular venue. Customers can create a wish list before visiting an app; they can skim through the inventory in an outlet's app (Candi et al., 2017). This also lets consumers know the quality of service offered by a particular business and can help a business interact with customers to ensure persistent learning and improvement.

Finding the best deal can take time when visiting a store or doing online research about a particular brand or product. A mobile app allows businesses to ensure that their loyal customers are up to date on events happening and allows them to take advantage of new offers and discounts from time to time (Homburg et al., 2015).

Mobile Apps and Customer Engagement

It is difficult to create customer engagement with customers who live far from a store. Kumar et al. (2017) and Ailawadi and Keller (2004) identified that as a result of online shopping the importance of the location of a store had diminished. However, at the same time, retailers do not find it easy to provide the same customer experience online as they do in an offline environment. They are faced with the unique situation where they might have eliminated store

location importance through an online presence but have reduced user satisfaction and sales because of reduced engagement. Retailer mobile apps may provide a way out of this by enhancing customer engagement and at the same time provide a solution to a firm's physical distance (Gill et al., 2017; Inman and Nikolova, 2017). The engagement experience of a customer even from far flung areas may be enhanced through a mobile app by allowing them to interact with the retailer and provide valuable input for search and purchase (Lemon and Verhoef, 2016). The mobile app may be interactive enabling the consumer to look at the product closely or even zoom in and out and have options of accessing further information and pictures. This may in turn build the retailer's rapport with the customer.

The mobile app may have a feature in which customers can view pictures of a new product, get information on it and have the option of purchasing it. Gray (2015) identified that some of the best retailer apps on customer smartphones are the ones where "alerts pushed at the perfect moment" are received. As businesses have now realized that more and more people are using mobile apps, they have made their own mobile applications to tap into the market. These allow businesses to provide better customer interaction and targeted marketing. If this strategy is implemented to the fullest, then it may result in profit for the organization (Soni et al., 2021; Kim and Baek, 2018).

A mobile app is a mine of information for a business; but this only happens when the mobile app is popular among consumers/users. To make an app popular, businesses might offer a loyalty programme or targeted discount offers that may attract customers to download the app and use it (Kritzinger and Pitzer, 2021). From the moment an app is downloaded by a customer, it is hard for the customer to forget about the brand as it is a permanent feature on the app gallery of their mobile.

Push notification is another way a retailer app can keep on reminding the customer about the app and the discounts and variety it has to offer. With advances in technology, companies with permanent addresses and physical locations can use geo-fencing and iBeacon technology to offer better customer experiences similar to instore experiences. If an app is well built and user friendly, it definitely gives an edge to businesses, even if they are small; businesses can increase their revenue by building a strong, vibrant and user-friendly app that allows user interaction (Lo Presti et al., 2021).

A pleasant user experience is vital; over time, apps have improved technologically and become strategic in nature. An app can provide and target particular aspects of customer experience from the point of pre-sale to the last point of post-sales experience. At the same time the customer is using the app and interacting with the brand. However, a bad online app experience will tarnish the image of the brand. The importance of apps as an important business channel is being established; at the same time, to drive better financial performance, businesses need an optimization strategy over every aspect and avenue of the customer experience (Morosan and DeFranco, 2016; Kim et al., 2017). Marketing personnel use apps as a perfect tool to target customers. But, in the future, apps will have a strategic role too. Businesses should be in a position to analyse apps' data and use it for research and their benefit. Businesses should monitor whether a high number of app downloads results in sales or registrations and analyse the brand image from the point of view of the consumer using the app. It is important for an organization to enhance an app's features and user interface and check that it performs as well on desktop platforms as on mobile sites.

Utilizing Mobile Apps to Create Loyalty and Engagement

Currently, the function of an app in the client's life cycle is uniformly divided among pre-purchase, transactional assistance and post-buy. These stages are utilized for the purpose of escalating faithfulness, enhancing communications and service, and progressive assistance in prime transactions (Elhamd et al., 2021). Some industries have a stronger influential grip on apps than other industries. For instance, apps are entirely regarding providing clients' alternative manner to handle accounts instead of facilitating Marketing with a platform to engross with recent clients in finance.

On the other hand, travel and gaming are energetically researching apps to obtain new clients, operate new business and enhance clients' experiences. However, firm feedback has been possessed by consumers with respect to apps and not progressively neglecting of a weak experience. Critically, in order to operate client engrossment businesses, look to utilize apps. Merely 16% of users will struggle with an app if it fails more than twice. In addition, users expect apps to be fast and, normally, to have a load time of two seconds. It is vividly suggested by the users to the mobile site for organizations to research the app for the purpose of enhancing engrossment and reinstate brand worth, weak functioning Apps or those with reliability problems will pose as an issue (Wang et al., 2016).

Many businesses are looking for worth in mobile and web apps with the purpose of motivating client engrossment because the business environment is highly competitive. The marketer is permitted by the apps in order to convey a firm mobile existence along with modified interfaces geared particularly to facilitate consumers with the great feasible experience (Mathis et al., 2016). Apps streamline clients' purchasing procedures, automate their various daily jobs and offer new opportunities for the purpose of operating engrossment in an effective manner. Currently, a great number of marketers are introducing consumer-facing apps in order to remain continually in contact with their consumers. Additionally, apps permit consumers to purchase from any place and at any time. The capability to transmit push and in-app notifications to consumers is one of the biggest benefits of apps (Kamboj et al., 2021). These notifications given to a restricted audience emphasize the consumer and convey great success proportion till the notifications contribute to pertinent and useful content. There probably would be more responses to marketing proposals and brand offerings at the time of requirement, when more audience concentrate on brand. However, for the purpose of notifying consumers, particularly younger demographics, of new products and proposals, push and in-app notifications do not prove to be useful (Stienmetz et al., 2013; Kim and Lee, 2018).

Marketers use these choices to make customized proposals to consumers. Suggestions can be customized on the basis of a new purchase or the consumer's location, which offers value to consumers and engages them in the app experience. Generally, mobile push notifications are considered scrap mail and may drive consumers to delete the app (Plotkina et al., 2021). However, push notifications are the best tool for tackling cart abandonment. Transmitting immediate push and in-app messaging when a consumer abandons a cart, tempting them with additional proposals, may prove to be influential in changing their decision and enhances the possibility of instant communication. It was demonstrated that in-app messaging has led to expansion of engrossment by 26%. In cases where in-app notifications are permitted, around 65% of consumers would come back to the app within the time period of a month (Rajaobelina et al., 2021).

For the purpose of enhancing client engrossment and overcoming the space that lies between a brand's online and physical existence, promotion of mobile-based faithfulness programmes is needed. Inducements and rewards can encourage clients to return to an app (Foroudi et al., 2018). Apps can make the management of faithfulness programmes easier and can convey the related rewards. Acquisition of reward points by consumers for each connection with a brand is regarded as the basic of any faithfulness programme. When consumers notice that their points

are increasing, then they visit the shop again. When these rewards are merged with gamification or points for any move completed with the help of an app, engrossment would certainly be enhanced (Pasca et al., 2021).

Starbucks is probably the most recognized brand, and it is skilled in providing huge rewards uniquely to app consumers. The “My Starbucks” rewards programme permits users to make use of the app for the purpose of making pre-orders, custom orders, receiving free-of-cost upgrades and particular discounts on the basis of their faithfulness footing. Permitting in-app payment speeds transactions and enhances usability (Wu et al., 2018).

2.5 Social Media Marketing Dynamics

2.5.1 Social Media Marketing and Online Brand Communities

The internet enables people to form groups regardless of geographic and time restrictions. As, Utilization exercises and e-commerce pose as foundations of these group integrations. Therefore, these internet tribes are of immense significance to marketing and business tacticians (Hu et al., 2019). Marketers who understand online communities can acquire advantage from observing variations in the methods individuals use to select a product or service and the manner in which they literally utilize them (Peng et al., 2014; Grashuis et al., 2021).

Brand community refers to “a professional, and non-geographically certain community and the basis of which are an organized set of social connections among devotees of a brand” (Gong, 2018). Members of the community are permitted to share information regarding their most-loved brands as well as assist other users. These communities contribute to the continuance of brands. Users take part in brand communities to make contact with other like-minded individuals who are interested in the brand (Hansen et al., 2018).

The encouragement of social media is not only regarding striking the first page of come upon or some other social information web page. For the purpose of setting up the firm's influence, status and item within spheres of possible consumers, guests and followers, it is a tactical and orderly procedure (Stelzner et al., 2015; Sharma et al., 2021).

Online brand communities enable members to communicate with each other. Such a facility directs consumers to recognize their importance while shopping from a particular online brand. The fundamental role of such communities is to sustain faithful customers, to engage impulsive

customers, to give customers positive insights into the brand and to spread information about the brand to customers; customers can benefit by participating in different social activities the brand offers to its community (Jibril et al., 2019). Brand communities have gained attention from social media; the curve of brand communities is upwards because of the increasing number of people on social media and their depending nature on the pattern of social media regarding purchasing from online brands (Islam et al., 2018; Khan, S. and Bhuiyan, 2021). Zhong et al. (2021) stated that social media is a power that has benefited online brands by sustaining their consumers and providing opportunities to engage with impulsive consumers.

Therefore, social media is a productive marketing tool for a brand's relationship with customers as it increases consumer engagement. In today's world, social media is used for many reasons, for example, a user might search for a fine restaurant; therefore, the owners of restaurants focus more on their social media to promote their restaurants as people in today's era rely on the reviews given by people on social media, such as Facebook (Chan and Guillet, 2011; Leung et al., 2017). Facebook is one of the most powerful social media tools with 2 billion monthly users active on it (Statista, 2017).

There are other social media platforms, such as Instagram and Twitter, but on Facebook there are easy ways to increase customer engagement. Facebook allows restaurants' marketing teams to create a page that contains all information related to the restaurant, such as food, ambience and timings (Liao et al., 2019; Martinek, 2021). Kaur et al. (2018) stated that people have an opportunity of rating and providing reviews on the restaurant, which gives the searcher for a fine restaurant more choices and options. On the one hand, Facebook can be beneficial for a restaurant's promotion, but on the other hand, if the reviews are not good, then it can also have a negative impact on consumer engagement (Wang and Kubockova, 2017); so, the marketing team of a restaurant should be very responsive on social media to eradicate the occurrence of problems, such as the negative feedback of consumers.

Zhong et al. (2021) reported the results of consumers' behaviour towards Facebook restaurant pages and their aim for bookings or reservations and WOM. According to Leung et al. (2017), there are four restaurants' Facebook messages that certify the productivity of social media marketing. The research conducted on effective social media marketing that provided with a little know how about the wanted results to the companies and the determinant of the results.

2.5.2 Facebook, Twitter and Instagram

In order to attract the maximum number of people, organizations nowadays try to find innovative ways to reach people through social media, as it is one of the good sources to advertise their product or service. In this regard social media platforms have gained a lot of importance and are increasing by more than 15% on a yearly basis (Marinucci, 2018). Social media is one of the most shared channels; it has enhanced audio and visual capabilities to communicate a product or service in a more attractive way, along with providing users with the opportunity to control what they want to see. Social media platforms have replaced many traditional marketing and advertising tools because they enable companies to attract and reach their target market in a better way (Li and Lo, 2015; Dessart, L. and Veloutsou, 2021).

A recent development in social media is Instagram Stories, which were introduced in August 2016 and are one of the most ground-breaking and significant features (Marmat, 2021). Instagram Stories can be shared on different platforms, such as Facebook and Snapchat, where users are allowed to share temporary content which includes photos, videos and also live transmissions. The time limit for such stories is 24 hours. At the user's end the other people are updated with shared stories that they can click open, and these stories are followed by other stories (Akrouf and Nagy, 2018). The user is in control, that is, they can go back and forth to new and old shared stories if they are interested in watching them. However, organizations are allowed to advertise their products and services in the same way as the stories created by users, but these are termed as "advertising" on the top left of the screen.

When an advertiser advertises content on a social media platform, the user can click the content in order to collect more information about the brand, which plays an important role in making purchasing decisions (Coelho et al., 2018). It was found that innovative features, such as Instagram Stories, might increase the success of campaigns run on social media platforms. However, the unique features of advertising on social media platforms will not be helpful if the advertisers fail to build content that attracts an audience (Belanche et al., 2017a; Tan et al., 2018). As stated by Pikas and Sorrentino (2014), in order to use social media platforms effectively and efficiently, organizations need to choose the most suitable platform. In addition, these platforms have an option of paid promotion and paid campaigns; so, in order to make a wise investment, marketing and advertising professionals need to learn the techniques.

Another element that is important in regard to running a campaign is to target the correct audience, such as region, gender, likes and dislikes, to meet the objective so that the chances of the campaign's success are high and the advertisements are placed on the right social media platform (Ahmad et al., 2019).

According to Braojos et al. (2019), studies have been conducted that showed that advertisements run on Facebook help to build and enhance brand equity and brand image. However, on the other hand, in the view of Chu and Seock (2020), this increases concerns of insensitivity. Additionally, according to Galati et al. (2017) and Barry et al. (2016), new platforms, such as Instagram and Snapchat, were found to be effective in terms of reaching a greater number of people and in building a good brand image for a longer time.

Moreover, in the view of Garrido-Moreno et al. (2018), previously conducted research has not focused on the unique feature of social media. Rather, as stated by Kim and Wang (2019), it only focuses on increasing the engagement of consumers on these platforms. Furthermore, research has not focused on measures to compare the effectiveness of advertising on different platforms (Voorveld et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2022). Hence, there is a need to examine the research gap, that is, to find out the effectiveness of advertising on different social media platforms. Therefore, this study is being conducted keeping the available opportunities in consideration regarding the management of campaigns related to online advertising; this research plays a part in understanding the effectiveness of advertising on social media platforms.

2.5.3 The Emergence of Social Media Influencers as a Marketing Tool

The new marketing technique that is being very much used by organizations these days is influencers. Influencer marketing is a type of marketing that uses a social media platform to endorse products and brands. In this technique, influencers, such as celebrities of cricket and movies, endorse a product by mentioning it in their videos and pictures. These influencers have a huge number of followers on their profiles (Chen, 2018). This marketing technique has become very effective because of the trust of the audience in the influencer; hence, influencers' recommended products are given importance by their viewers, and this helps a brand to increase the number of their consumers (Lim et al., 2017; Tseng and Wei, 2020).

According to Beard (2016), these days brands are unable to get maximum attention from the internet because almost all businesses have shifted to social media and are creating a lot of advertisements, which makes the audience very confused in regard to choosing a brand. Therefore, there is a need for organizations to opt for different and innovative digital marketing techniques and strategies to sell their products. Hence, this is one reason why influencer marketing is on the rise these days. Influencer marketing is becoming very popular among businesses and digital marketers, and organizations are ready to invest a handsome amount to run these campaigns because of its success rate (Leong et al., 2018; Drummond et al., 2020).

Influencer marketing is about developing collaboration with renowned influencers associated with a particular niche for brand promotion and improving sales prospects. Influencers are generally considered those who have numerous strong followers on different social media platforms (Pratt, 2018; Yousaf et al., 2021).

Furthermore, influencers are viewed as having expertise within their respective niches due to which their suggestions are considered valuable by the followers that they have. The difference between influencers and traditional celebrities is that influencers generally have a strong association with their fan communities. Through the use of social media, they are able to develop personal connections to gain the trust and the confidence of their followers. Identification and targeting of the right kind of audience is a key element of every marketing strategy (Soares et al., 2021). Nevertheless, it often turns out to be a hard job and it needs an in-depth understanding of potential customers. Marketing based on the use of influencers facilitates organizations in dealing with this challenge effectively as the influencers are already aware of the needs and the requirements of the targeted customers. The only thing that needs to be done is to identify the kind of influencer that can be linked with a particular niche, one whose public persona is aligned with the image of the brand (Silva et al., 2019).

Successful influencer marketing campaigns need effective planning and substantial understanding of the target audience along with understanding of the marketing objectives intended to be achieved. Engaging diverse customers efficiently is the major advantage of using social media influencers as they have the capability to influence the buying behaviour of consumers (Sundermann and Raabe, 2019). When content is shared by influencers on their profile on different social media handles, the audiences associated with them can be easily engaged with that particular content.

If they are pleased with the content, then they might tag their friends, which ultimately results in enhancing the reach of a particular marketing campaign (Appel et al., 2019). For the effective promotion of apps, organizations often make use of different endorsements from social media influencers who have the capability to influence their audience in terms of showing preference towards a particular product or service (Casalo et al., 2018). However, there is an argument that although social influencers have the potential to enhance the reach of a particular product by targeting extensive groups of customers, there is limited research that has studied the exact reason behind it (Choi et al., 2019; Gu et al., 2017). The element of trust is very important here and can have a significant impact on whether customers are influenced to purchase a product (Choi et al., 2019; Han et al., 2014). However, customers generally give significant value to the credibility of social media influencers, which is reflected in the posts that they make on daily basis (Audrezet et al., 2019).

Findings further demonstrate that customers genuinely consider social media influencers to be authentic endorsers and the ones who can communicate and interpret marketing messages (Freberg et al., 2011). In light of trust transfer theory, the trust of a customer within an established trusted entity, such as social media influencers, can transfer to a related entity as well, for example a product or service endorsed by an influencer. Consequently, trust transfer could be the mechanism related to the effectiveness of social media influencers in terms of increasing numbers of customers using apps.

Influencers of social media rely heavily on the trust of their followers which helps them to establish a loyal community of fans (Pick, 2021). Whenever influencers share their honest opinions about a particular product or service, it is perceived as a genuine story. Furthermore, it enhances the reputation of a brand along with establishing its credibility (Singh et al., 2020; Appel et al., 2019). Therefore, collaboration with influencers is very important for gaining the trust and the confidence of the targeted audience and gaining long-term benefits in terms of enhancing the customer base.

The trust of a person in a particular app can be established through two different aspects; one of these is the perceived utilitarian value of the app (Choi et al., 2019). If consumers feel confident about the value of a particular app, then they would be willing to display significant intentions towards adopting it. The second key aspect is concerns related to security (Gu et al., 2017; Han et al., 2014). Adopting an app is generally associated with a high level of risk. For instance, when users download any app, there is a possibility that their phone is exposed to a

virus. In addition, providers of apps also ask users to provide their private information. Users' estimation of whether the security measures of an app are credible plays a vital role in determining their trust towards that particular app (Choi et al., 2019; Yalew et al., 2017).

A survey conducted on Twitter (2016) highlighted that almost half of the respondents were involved in consulting social media influencers before doing shopping and almost 40% of them ordered products through the links that are attached to the posts of influencers. This is because consumers are constantly looking for authenticity within a brand before making a decision to purchase it and influencers can play a key role in developing it.

When the marketers of a brand facilitate influencers by providing product-related experience, such as product background, performance and information, then marketers are able to use these influencers for effective promotion of brands (Casaló et al., 2018; Gu et al., 2017). It is also crucial that customers have significant trust in the influencers, which can ultimately assist firms to gain the trust of their customers regarding their different products and services.

2.6 Marketing in SMEs

2.6.1 The Context of SMEs

The attention of researchers all across the world in recent times has converged on SMEs' success in the business market. For example, researchers are interested in evaluating the key aspects of SMEs that can differentiate them from other players in the market (Handriana, 2016). Some scholars tend to praise SMEs for the existence of a high level of proximity existing within their business operations allowing them to respond positively to dynamic market conditions as well as continuously change in response to customers' expectations or needs (Agarwal et al., 2019; Ahmad et al., 2018).

It is quite common that SMEs, like other businesses, need to make use of the marketing aspect to boost sales of their products and services. Marketing is one of the key business functions existing within an organization. Multiple definitions existing for marketing. For example, Widjojo et al. (2020) made use of the definition of marketing from the Chartered Institute of Marketing in the UK: Marketing is a type of management process to identify and meet the expectations of the customers positively. Carson et al. (2020) provided another definition of marketing stating that it is a type of organizational function carrying the potential to develop,

communicate and offer suitable value to customers for boosting their level of relationship with the organization and its relevant stakeholders.

The American Association of Marketing defined the marketing function as a business planning and execution process focused on the different aspects related to a product, including price, promotion, place and physical evidence, to ensure good alignment between customer expectations and organizational objectives (Handriana, 2016). One of the common aspects existing within all of these definitions is that the marketing function comprises different strategic, operational as well as tactical activities supporting the organization in achieving the desired amount of success. However, there is no clear definition available related to the performance activities of a marketing function in SMEs (Emerald Publishing Group, 2020). The reason is that the discussion related to SMEs has mostly focused on entrepreneurial behaviour. SME is a widely recognized concept in the contemporary world and there is a debate going on between different scholars related to the marketing aspect within business organizations.

Multiple SMEs globally use classical models of marketing to present their products or services to customers. However, most of the theories explaining this marketing behaviour of SMEs are quite descriptive or qualitative with limited empirical evidence (Handriana, 2016; Soderlund et al., 2021). It is necessary to mention the basic marketing principles that need to be accepted by all organizations regardless of their size and structure. All organizations, of a large, medium or small scale, need to implement the marketing function uniformly to achieve the targeted positive results. However, Ulas (2019) stated that most SMEs make use of the networking aspect between their employees and targeted customer base to boost their business sales. Ritz et al. (2019) agreed with the view of Ulas (2019); they stated that marketing within SMEs is carried out as a result of transactions conducted between different parties involved with the organization through their interactions and networking. In recent times, e-commerce and digital marketing have experienced exponential growth due to technological advancements (Hoque et al., 2017). Due to the same reason, the importance of WOM has increased massively among customers (Royo-Vela et al., 2021; Simonetti and Bigne, 2022). However, it is important to mention that the key application of these theories is mostly limited to the research or theoretical context, where limited evidence is available to support effective results delivery from the usage of the marketing function within SMEs.

2.6.2 Customer relationship management (CRM)

The concept of customer relationship management is referred as a business strategy which has a key focus on the customers and this CRM as a process integrates customer services, marketing and sales functions. The concept of CRM therefore is intended to add value for both customers and businesses (Gordon, 1988). A key focus of CRM is on collecting data through various mediums and then retain customers i.e., intelligently collect, manage and use data by using technological tools and developing exceptional customer experience and relationships (Anantharaman et al, 2022). Organizations can avail significant support by collecting data from different customer contact points and then developing marketing responses in line with the well managed data. For example, tailoring services, products and creating new ideas and ultimately gaining competitive advantage by delivering high customer service and value (Kumar and Misra, 2021). New technological solutions are being sought and delivered in today's digital age by increasing the variety, velocity and volume of data along with capacity of processing the large chunks of data such as, techniques of artificial intelligence (Brynjolfsson and McAfee, 2017). Higher customer loyalty is one of the prominent potential benefits that CRM provides when used as a system along with lower costs, improved efficiency, better customer service and improved marketing effectiveness (Cao and Tian, 2020; Migdadi, 2021). CRM initiatives often fail to meet expectations, despite of CRM technology's continued growth and development (Chen et al., 2020; CSO Insight, 2018).

Arsić et al. (2018) established the importance of reinforcing customer loyalty by analysing the expected benefits of using CRM, and by relying on the basic principle that in today's highly competitive market ecosystem, the ability to reduce the risk of losing the best customers is a key factor. This reflected that, a significant value is held by any tool focused on the loyalty of economically profitable customers, provided it is completely aligned with CRM strategy (Haislip and Richardson, 2017).

Since enhanced knowledge through CRM should increase the effectiveness and efficiency of marketing campaigns and actions, marketing is another area in which a highly beneficial impact is expected through the use of CRM (Guerola-Navarro et al., 2020). Better knowledge about customer needs is a key factor in the adaptation of marketing campaigns and in their segmentation and actions to these expectations (Li and Song, 2019).

Services is the third area in which a beneficial and direct impact due to the use of CRM is expected i.e., specifically in customer support and service. Excellent customer knowledge is facilitated by CRM for organizations, a deeper understanding of the needs of the consumer is achieved if it is used efficiently which then translates into better customer service and support and with it their satisfaction and loyalty; this goes back to the basic customer-centred strategy and marketing principle of customer loyalty (Kebede and Tegegne, 2018).

Relational marketing is the basis of modern marketing theories i.e., marketing efforts to strengthen and develop long-term relationships with customers. Moreover, these efforts are improved via commercial efforts that are channelled into the continuous improvement of customer service, which has a significant impact on customer satisfaction (Fidel et al., 2018).

A key CRM objective and part of its scope as a technical business management solution is that it is essential to put maximum focus and effort into the management of customer relationships, and especially into customer satisfaction. This particular process is also referred as the main way to survive and maximize financial health of organizations. This customer-centred marketing orientation is directly related to the expected benefits of the deployment and use of CRM in companies and is at the heart of relational marketing (Kumar and Misra, 2021). To track and analyse customer-related information, CRM has become the key software technology tool for organizations today, including the trust that their customer relationships can be greatly improved through technology management solutions (Libai et al., 2020).

The importance of customer relationships and customers' loyalty has been recognized by multiple organizations across the world in recent times. Gronroos (2017) argued that small business organizations had also diverted their attention towards the same area to gain a strong response from customers and remain competitive in the business market. Gummerus et al. (2017) argued that business organizations in the contemporary world must emphasize positively the interaction, relationship and information sharing with customers to develop a relationship of loyalty and trust with them. Many scholars also delivered the same recommendations to business organizations by informing them about the high costs of identifying and developing a new customer instead of retaining the current one. It is imperative to mention that customer acquisition is difficult; organizations have to carry out suitable advertisements, promotions, discounts and so on, which has an impact on their bottom-line profits.

Grönroos (2017) highlighted that the approach as well as the strategy adopted by business organizations within their relationship marketing strategy tends to carry high importance; otherwise, it might restrain the organizational capability to achieve the targeted objectives.

2.6.3 Viral Marketing

Hinz et al. (2011) defined viral marketing as customers being forced to share or pass a marketing message to other people, which creates an exponential increase in the viewership and exposure of the marketing message to the targeted audience. Miller and Lammas (2010) stated that the multiple potential benefits existing for a business organization with viral marketing include enhanced message delivery, improved credibility, faster diffusion, better targeting of customers and reduced cost of the marketing. Stonedahl et al. (2010) argued that viral marketing also supports the organization in reaching the maximum customer base in a limited time to boost business profits.

Viral marketing tends to gain maximum value from the networks and associations of customers through which they share the marketing message. Such marketing also supports the organization in keeping their customers engaged as well as active, which leads to campaign success (Hinz et al., 2011; Mason et al., 2020). It is necessary to mention that although viral marketing is important for business organizations, the organization must remain aware of the aspects motivating the customer to make that content viral.

Active and passive are the two key types of viral marketing. Passive viral marketing refers to the activity undertaken by a business organization for broadcasting the brand making use of some media without placing a positive focus on the content of the marketing (Stonedahl et al., 2010). Business organizations can gain benefits from viral marketing by adding a watermark logo within the viral content. Different pages operating on Facebook make use of the same strategy leading to a large viewership of the marketing content among the targeted customer base leading to improved business sales (Miller and Lammas, 2010).

However, the concept of active viral marketing is quite different from the passive one. In the case of active marketing, a business organization needs to remain completely managed as well as activities for responding to customer concerns and issues. For instance, if an organization organizes an event or content on a social media platform and encourage customers to share

event pictures with other people for a reward (Stonedahl et al., 2010), then the organization must ensure they respond to all the concerns and needs of the customers positively.

Viral marketing tends to come with a wide range of benefits for the business organization as compared to traditional media because of the cost (Choshaly and Mirabolghasemi, 2020). The reason is that the cost of performing viral marketing is quite low as compared to the cost for preparing and presenting advertisements on television or print media (Ho and Dempsey, 2010). The design of viral marketing is the key aspect differentiating it from all other types of marketing and it generates better business sales as well as profits. As per different studies, the main generation currently active on social media is the Millennial generation, which has a low level of trust in conventional marketing techniques. However, they are heavily influenced by influencer advertising in which the advertisements are specifically designed by the company for the customers (Joseph et al., 2021). The delivery of a message from their favourite celebrity tends to influence customers positively, which leads to improved business sales.

As much social media influence attempt for viral marketing; therefore, the type of marketing adopted by them to raise the desired profit for the organizations carry high importance within the context of the current study (Schulze et al., 2014). Stealth marketing is another key aspect available to business organizations for boosting awareness among customers and generating desired business sales or profits (Bresciani et al., 2021). Stealth marketing is a technique by which the business organization pays the influencer to promote their product; however, their advertisement or product is not revealed directly. This type of marketing tends to carry high potential as customers are heavily influenced because of the positive results delivery of the same product from their influencer (Camarero and San José, 2011). The marketing technique is quite unethical; however, its usage is quite high in the contemporary world. It is important to mention that this type of marketing is regarded as ethical in the USA; however, the EU has legislation that restricts this kind of marketing in the contemporary world (Palalic et al., 2021).

Viral marketing also has some weaknesses, like the control of the organization over the advertisement. For instance, if the organizational advertisement goes wrong for any reason, then there is limited opportunity for the organization to control and lemmatize its usage (Gupta and Saboo, 2021). This means that a mistake or error committed by an employee of the organization might have huge financial as well as reputational implications for the organization. Another key negativity linked with viral marketing for business organizations is that organizations have no control over the people who can view or access the organizational

content (Botha and Reyneke, 2013). This means that customers or individuals not targeted by the company might have access to the same content that went viral through the organizational marketing strategy.

2.6.4 Smartphones, SMEs and Security Challenges

The technology of mobile phones is changing rapidly. Mobile phones or smartphones are no longer only a means of connecting with other people, but also act as e-readers, gaming consoles and personal digital assistants. Information system security specialists have more expertise in the usage and operations of highly recognized Microsoft operating systems (Harris et al., 2012; Koch et al., 2020).

The growth of smartphones and tablets in the modern world has a wide range of security implications. One of the key reasons for this is that these appliances do not make use of the Windows operating system only. Instead, there are multiple operating systems being used in such devices, including Android OS, Google and Apple iOS, of which very few people are aware. This means that the software used by smartphones and tablets is quite different from the software used in typical computers (Baillette and Barlette, 2018). Moreover, it is imperative to mention that access to the software and applications within these devices is mainly provided by the operating system parent themselves. including Google or Apple. This means that the security concerns existing for such organizations are quite high in number relating to customer, business and employee information (Siddiqui et al., 2018). It also raises an issue related to the usage of the personal information of an individual as that information exists within the personal use of smartphones or tablets.

In the last decade, many business organizations have realized the importance of digitalization and the internet for boosting their business productivity; thus, they offered access to the internet and advanced mobile technology to their employees to complete their allocated tasks (Baillette and Barlette, 2018). This gave rise to the requirement of tech-savvy employees at the workplace who are capable of adapting to new technologies and completing organizational tasks efficiently. Organizational management in the contemporary world encourages their employees to make use of the latest technologies to complete their allocated tasks with minimum resources and in minimum time (Siddiqui et al., 2018). It delivers a benefit of efficiency to the organization; however, it tends to come at the cost of security concerns.

The rapid growth of tablets and smartphones in the market along with the exponential increase in their usage offers a key opportunity for business organizations to compete with each other. This means that SME employees can make use of these services to offer better productivity to their organization with maximum affordability as well gain a desired set of profits (Ahmad Tarmizi et al., 2019; Park et al., 2020). Wireless service providers are also exploiting this opportunity positively, especially for small business organizations, by offering them wireless technology that allows them to remain connected with each other and complete organizational tasks efficiently. However, similar to large organizations, SMEs also need to manage their business operations effectively to offer maximum value to the customer, including complete security to customers. It is quite clear from different instances that security breaches could cost an organization millions of dollars, resulting in lost trust and satisfaction from the customers' side (Siddiqui et al., 2018). SMEs have a limited customer base; therefore, SMEs must pay attention to making customers' data, like credit card numbers, phone numbers and identity card numbers, secure. Recent research showed an increased level of security threat in the contemporary world (Kurpjuhn, 2015). SMEs need to understand these risks to take suitable actions against them; otherwise, they will be unable to achieve the benefits offered by technology and it will lead them to unsatisfactory results.

Ulas (2019) stated that concerns related to security had also increased among the general public in recent times. This means that customers are now interested in knowing about the actions and strategies being used by organizations to protect their data against any kind of security breaches. If SMEs can provide a satisfactory response to customers' concerns in this area, then they are capable of developing a long-term relationship with them as well as generating desired positive results (He, 2013; Lepkowska-White et al., 2019). Otherwise, it will get complicated for them to compete strongly in the business market.

2.7 Dynamics and Typology of Restaurants in the UK

Cooper et al. (2017) carried out a study to evaluate the typology of restaurants, including mid-scale, business dining, multi-unit, quick service and moderate up-scale. Although most of these categories are non-existent in modern times, three main categories persist. Baiomy et al. (2014) provided a simpler classification for restaurant typology in this regard by defining the categories, including concept, market and menu. Nichele (2019) offered other typologies of

restaurants including QSR, casual dining and fine dining. Fine dining is a type of restaurant where the customers are offered a good selection of food items and high emphasis on service quality.

Canziani et al. (2016) stated that fine dining is one of the most formal types of dining; it is mostly used at formal events, like business events and marriage events, where a high level of sophistication, gastronomy, elegance and spectacular location is desired by the customers. Such restaurants tend to design their place based on the theme of the event or restaurant, like celebrity-owned or ethnic. Lane (2010) stated that the basic purpose of theme restaurants is to offer a unique and exceptional experience to customers to keep them satisfied and contented with the organization. It is possible to arrange such kinds of restaurants either in a formal or semi-formal manner based on the expectations as well as needs of the customers. An authentic cuisine feature is also ensured in these kinds of restaurants to ensure customers have a unique and positive experience. Celebrity-owned restaurants come with a combination of atmosphere, thrill and design to offer a unique and positive experience to customers (Griffiths, 2011; Grewal and Stephen, 2019). Different kinds of menu, as well as seating arrangements, are offered to customers to meet their expectations and gain positive reviews.

Ethnicity is a key feature for ethnic types of restaurants, like Chinese, Mexican, Italian and Spanish. Casual dining or mid-scale restaurants are quite popular all across the world with famous chains, including Frankie and Benny, and Hard Rock Café (Vít and Kopp, 2019). QSRs offer a limited menu option to customers; however, their pace supports them in boosting their business sales. This kind of restaurant targets customers who want fast service. It is important to mention that this classification of restaurants is not limited to the USA, it is equally applicable all across the world. For example, restaurants in the UK are divided into multiple formats, including ethnic, casual, quick service and pub restaurants. Elo (2016) stated that four key factors – price, location, ambience, service level and cuisine – play a key role in the classification of restaurants and their scope for delivering positive service to customers to keep them contented as well as satisfied.

2.7.1 Competitiveness, Demographics and Performance

The restaurant market has experienced suitable growth in recent times because of consumer trends as well as changing demographics. Due to the same reason, the level of competitiveness among restaurants has also increased, creating inflation and cost-related pressures (Iraldo et al., 2017). As the market is quite competitive, customers have a wide range of options. It had caused a functional shift within the consumers as well as demographics trend leading to a boost in transactional activity, especially in the last 10 years (Djeri et al., 2018). This means that the eating out landscape has changed positively in different ways in the last 10 years. Restaurant chains attempted to exploit this opportunity by offering suitable product choices, quality and low pricing to customers. Figure 8 presents a graph indicating the frequency of eating out in 1989 and in 2015 published by PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC), which is a credible international professional services firm.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in <https://www.pwc.co.uk/services/business-recovery/insights/restructuring-trends/restaurants-2017-food-for-thought.html>

Figure 8: Frequency of eating out

Source: PwC (2017)

The graph shows that the percentage of customers eating out once a month and once a week has increased significantly and the percentage of customers eating out less than once a month

has reduced. The graph shows that the trend and frequency of eating out have increased generally. In the light of this frequency trend, it can be noted that the restrictions caused by COVID-19 towards eating out posed significant challenges for small and medium-sized restaurants, which means marketing becomes even more important to survival and staying competitive.

The crossover between market segments also increased in this time. The food-to-go sector is available to customers day and night (Chen et al., 2011). At the same time, many new companies entered the market to connect small restaurants with customers, to the benefit of both, including Uber Eats and Deliveroo (Iraldo et al., 2017). For the same reason, the level of competition among restaurant chains has increased massively and they offer a wide range of options to customers. Sales were boosted, which enhanced market valuation (Djeri et al., 2018). However, the situation has also become challenging for restaurant organizations in terms of managing cost pressures.

The labour intensity required within the restaurant business is quite high; therefore, the workforce tends to play a key role in the success of a restaurant organization. In the UK, the National Living Wage boosted the pay structure of employees working in restaurants in 2016 by making an increment of 6% within their minimum wages (National Bureau of Economic Research, 2019). Compliance with legislative requirements created a challenge for restaurants to compete strongly in the market. The aggressive rollouts carried out by different brands in previous years had led to a shortage of chefs in the market (Chen et al., 2011). Moreover, the rate of unemployment in the UK reduced by 4.7% in 2017 affecting labour supply (Institute for Employment Research, 2020). Moreover, the labour shortage in the UK was also intensified by the BREXIT decision. All of these factors played a great role in increasing the wage cost of the employees working at restaurants.

There are multiple explanations for the dramatic shift in the casual dining industry and its growth. For example, BREXIT affected the economic condition leading to the low spending behaviour of customers (Deloitte, 2020). The increasing prices of food products as well as the dollar losing valuation in the UK market also contributed to the increase of food items as well as property pricing in the UK. At the same time, it became more challenging for large food organizations to keep their customers satisfied because customers looked for innovation and a positive response from brands (Perramon et al., 2014). All of these factors merged to divert the attention of consumers to small and medium-size brands to meeting their food needs.

2.7.2 Restaurant Image

The image of a restaurant tends to play a large role in business sales as it affects the consequent behaviour and subjective perception of customers. However, the conceptualization of a restaurant image is complex. Ryu et al. (2012) reported that customers take multiple tangible elements into consideration when evaluating a restaurant. Han and Hyun (2017) reported that the tangible elements include interior design and food pricing, whereas extrinsic elements include the level of service as well as the food quality offered by a restaurant to its customers. This means that there are multiple aspects involved within the restaurant that affect the image and customers' perceptions of the restaurant. Kim et al. (2019) and Dossena et al. (2021) agreed with these findings and stated that a customer develops a restaurant image based on symbolic attitude, ideas and emotional perceptions.

However, some authors believe that the quality of the food is the only key factor affecting the perception of the customer related to the restaurant. Customer loyalty is affected by the entire meal experience, which includes factors like hygiene, food quality, pricing and ambience. Jang et al. (2015) define in this regard involving both tangible and intangible elements offering suitable value to the brand in setting and sustaining its image in the market. For the same reason, this thesis distinguishes between intrinsic and extrinsic elements because they play different roles in setting the organizational image. Similarly, Jin et al. (2012) claimed that the corporate setting of a restaurant also tends to affect customers' perceptions of a restaurant. Jeong and Jang (2010) found that restaurant image is affected massively by customer satisfaction, customers' perceptions of value and customers' perceptions of trust in the organization. It could be a valuable consideration for restaurant organizations to sustain customers' trust to achieve targeted positive results.

Instead of focusing on the corporate sector, Erkmen and Hancer (2019) investigated brand image in the case of gastronomy restaurants. Celebrity chefs are not only responsible for characterizing the restaurant image, but they also transfer them into a brand of their own. It is possible to provide evidence for the same through the endorsements carried out by these chefs for food, drinks, utensils and so on. Kim et al. (2019) and Sabermajidi et al. (2020) stated that the total perceptual alignment comes with an inherent risk related to the charismatic founder-entrepreneur and brand, which have the potential to affect the brand image negatively.

Jeong and Jang (2010) clarified that some chefs become a global brand, making use of social media and ensuring their regular presence on television programmes. Erkmen and Hancer (2019) agree to the same informing that it tends to benefit the chefs in bringing information about their product quality to customers to boost business sales. Kim et al. (2019) made use of awards as a benchmark for excellence. However, Erkmen and Hancer (2019) criticized restaurant awards because of subjective experiences and objective intangible elements. However, Kim et al. (2019) stated that an award like a Michelin Star is still recognized as trustworthy in the eyes of customers. Overall, the brand image or reputation of a restaurant tends to play a large role in the value assessment of a restaurant and enables a restaurant to raise its prices above the average. Based on the literature review findings gathered, Figure 9 presents a thematic content representation of the chapter.

Figure 9: Literature review thematic findings

CRM, customer relationship management. Source: developed by the author

2.8 Thematic Evaluation of Literature

This literature review chapter has been conducted by focusing on examining themes within the chosen topic of social media marketing across SME restaurants. Identification, reporting and analysis of themes within the topic has been achieved in this chapter by reading, comprehending and utilizing the existing research papers. A theme is a repeating idea or narrative which is required to be developed in the specific context of research aim and objectives, and to achieve this a systematic process has been followed in this chapter. The table below is indicating the thematic content analysis and development of literature review chapter:

Figure 10: Thematic Content Analysis

Source: Developed by the author

2.9 Conceptual Framework

The purpose of the conceptual framework section is to discuss a number of variables that are part of the theoretical framework, which have been analysed through the literature review. The key aim pursued in this section is to develop understanding relating to the working relation that exists between different variables present in the study, while aligning the literature review findings with the research aims. The variables selected relate to the theoretical underpinnings of social impact theory along with the concept of traditional behaviour. A key highlight of the research is how social impact theory guides plays a role as an important tool in social media marketing. It will involve the use of assumptions of social impact theory to further guide the theoretical framework. The potential of mobile applications in a social media marketing strategy of a business will also be discussed. The framework is based on two broader and distinct variables, which are social mobile apps and social media marketing, while discussing its potential to have an impact on consumer behaviour. Both of these variables will be further divided into sub-variables that have emerged in line with the use and scope of both variables. These variables strongly reflect the key findings and the objectives being pursued.

2.9.1 Social Impact Theory and Social Media Marketing

Social Influence Theory can be deemed an appropriate approach to understanding the interaction of users on social media. Different measures are used by organizations to develop their presence on social media, such as sales and consumer engagement and awareness. Social psychology discusses the impact of a number of variables on interpersonal interactions, such as attitudes, behaviour and beliefs. According to Vega et al. (2019), there are different forms of immediacy, such as temporal, social and physical influences. One main feature of social media that distinguishes it from other formats is the personalized user-generated content. Dickey et al. (2018) claimed that users exercised greater control over the content. Consumers do not want to listen to business organizations but rather expect them to listen to consumers.

One of the major challenges faced by business organizations today is the shift that is taking place in the attitude and behaviour of consumers (Kietzman et al., 2011). It is necessary for organizations to understand the particular factors that can influence the behaviour of consumers on social media. This will enable organizations to develop more effective promotional

strategies for social media. It is stated in social impact theory that “When other people are the source of impact, and the individual is the target; impact should be a multiplicative function of the strength, immediacy, and number of other people”. From this, it can be said that increasing the number of people reached out to can help impact the attitude and behaviour of targeted individuals (Latane, 1981). Users are often seen using social media networking sites for sharing a variety of information, such as information relating to events, products and brands. The use of social impact theory is further justified for understanding the impact that social media has on influencing the attitude of consumers (Choi et al., 2019). Strong insight can be gained regarding the use of mobile applications by users can be better understood through social impact theory.

2.9.2 Social Media Apps and Consumer Behaviour

A unique feature of social media marketing which makes it particularly desirable is its two-way communication, which makes it an appropriate tool to support the marketing, promotional and advertising activities of a company. The adoption and usage level in social media is seen to be exceptionally high. A paradigm shift was seen in how people communicate, connect and express themselves with each other as well as with organizations, products and brands. It was also seen that social media became networks for fostering the knowledge of consumers (Roesler, 2016).

In order to effectively understand the relation between consumer behaviour and social media apps, it is important to understand the changing preferences and nature of consumers in the digital age. The process of connecting with others and sharing information has become particularly easy due to empowerment by technology. Carlston et al. (2018) stated that consumers expect businesses to meet all the needs of consumers instantly. This change was initially carried forward by laptops and home computers in the last 10 years, but now it is mainly led by smartphone technology as it offers greater power. According to Alnawas et al. (2016), smartphones will not be alone in leading such change in the future as other forces may also play a role.

Fang et al. (2017) carried out research recently to see how social media affects the behaviour of consumers. The focus of their study was to see the impact of social media while considering differences in age ranges and ethnicities. The main argument was that demographic variations

tend to significantly influence the social media use of users, such as the type of device used, and the information looked up. The use of social media is still relevant to all despite such variations. The research indicated that around 47% of Millennial's buying behaviour was influenced by social media, whereas the influence was 19% for all age groups. This reliable survey by Deloitte (2019) clearly showed how the use of social media influences the buying behaviour of customers. The study of Millennials is of particular interest in the current research as the number of working Millennials in the UK who visit restaurants on a daily or weekly basis is high.

The dominant role being played by social media shows that it is something that cannot be overlooked by businesses. As clearly pointed out in the report by Deloitte, consumers who use social media are expected to spend four times as much on purchases compared to those who do not (Nash, 2019). If business owners work to refine to their social media marketing strategy, then they will be able to boost their sales. Although new connective devices are gaining popularity, smartphones can still be labelled as the key technology that is being used today, since the penetration level in adults was around 85 to 90% in 2020 as indicated in a report by PwC (2016). This indicates that organizations operating in the UK will have to rely on digital and social media applications to influence the behaviour of customers. The discussion above indicates that the buying decision of customers is strongly influenced by digital platforms and social media applications. As technology develops further, becoming more efficient and affordable, it is expected that influence on everyday life of consumers would become more prominent becoming the preferred device for most customers.

Perkins (2014) has suggested bringing about consistency in colours used for advertising on social media as it would make the brand more recognizable. Having consistency in colours would particularly help to increase brand recognition given that the colours match brand visuals. The visual content may also help to boost the engagement of users on social media such as the use of videos and pictures. Well planned visual branding strategy is known to benefit companies significantly on social media.

Brand Image and Social Media

Brand meaning is seen to emerge from certain social constructs, such as brand and consumer perceptions that relate with both branding strategies and brand comparisons (Campelo et al., 2014). The social element of branding has particular importance relating with the role of

branding in shaping the focus of marketing. Branding is seen to be influenced by a number of factors, such as value placed by individuals, social pressures and social messages that others have placed on the brand ownership (Lim et al., 2021). The linkage present between value and branding is seen to be influenced by different components of the brand process, which include the brand message and brand knowledge.

Brand loyalty has been a common element in research exploring the use of social media by companies. Facebook currently has around 955 million users who log into their account at least once a month (Jacobson, 2020). Around half of the users log into their accounts on a daily basis through smartphones or other internet-based applications. The widespread use of such social media platforms has made them particularly attractive technology for promoting brand-related content as well as promoting brand association.

Although companies use social media to gain the attention of consumers as well as to spread brand awareness, it is not guaranteed that a positive response will always be achieved. Brand-related content is being introduced at an increasing rate and sometimes it is viewed as unwanted content by social media users. According to Laroche et al. (2013), consumers need to be aware of the impact that advertisements will have and response that could come to brand related content. A major element for market leaders like Facebook is to create an engaging environment by encouraging users to interact with each other (Broad, 2020). Individuals should be encouraged to take part in various activities that are being carried out on the social media platform.

According to Schivinski et al. (2016), effectively measuring consumer engagement in brand-related activities can help and be deemed as an important component of a social network marketing plan. The process of creating internet presence for a particular brand cannot be regarded as a static process anymore, through which brand depictions can be created without a feedback loop.

Graves (2016) pointed out that a large number of brands are leveraging social media for the purpose of attracting customers and gaining their attention. An important reason for including social media in a branding strategy is that it can provide access to a large customer base around the world which is continuously growing. This does not mean that one should only leverage digital channels, but rather one should use social media side-by-side with the traditional media strategy. Brand awareness is regarded among the greatest benefit that is achieved by brands when they engage with customers on social media.

Social Media Apps and Communication

Social media has largely altered the landscape of today's communication and has been viewed as a gamechanger. Social media can be regarded as a large umbrella under which several communication channels are present. According to Casalo et al. (2018), it has enabled people around the whole world to interact with each other and share information relating to products and brands. Communicating with the users is important to enhance brand awareness. Lots of information is present on branded apps relating to the products they promote. The latest trends have clearly pointed out that the use of a greater number of information formats carries greater benefit (Chritton, 2018). If a brand wishes to grow effectively then it should utilize a lot of information forms, such as pictures, video, audio and virtual reality. Promoting communication around the world is one method of achieving this feat. It can be seen that the world has become increasingly connected and online networks have evolved into digital communities (Mangold and Faulds, 2009). There are no boundaries for brands regarding the type of content that they can share. Users can wish for any type of information that they want, such as experiences, opinions or any additional information (Weinberg et al., 2012). The many-to-many communication channel provides access to a larger community base since it is not linked to the real-life social environment that we see today (Charlesworth, 2009).

Understanding social media platforms will become easier if they are divided into different points. There are number of categories under which social media platforms can be placed, such as social networks, social bookmarking, forums, visual sites, blogs, site-related portals and voting sites. Understanding these categories becomes significantly easier if they are clustered based on their individual functionalities. The first type of social media channels is known to promote communication between users, which include SNSs, bookmarking platforms and micro-blogs (Weinberg et al., 2012; Kreutzer, 2014). Social media sites, such as Facebook which is the largest social networking site and has around 2.13 billion users monthly, take up an important part of this category.

The Facebook network can be labelled a rich network that allows the sharing of a variety of content. such as videos, images, games and music. It fosters communication through the interaction of users and instant messaging tools like Facebook Messenger (Facebook, 2018). It has a particular focus on interpersonal contact, which can happen between individuals as well as groups of users. According to Van Dijck (2013), these platforms can also be divided based

on geographical, private or professional level. The latter category focuses on cooperation among users, where this cooperation can be seen varying in iterations, such as in general rating pages. The opinions of users on such sites can have a significant impact on the way users gather information and they influence attitudes towards certain issues. The last important category includes SM portals that are focused on the exchange of content, which is shown in a variety of forms, such as images, videos and audio sharing (Weinberg et al., 2012; Kreutzer, 2014). Popular channels that come under this category include sites such as Instagram and YouTube. This shows how certain sites are strongly focused on the sharing of information between users in rich forms, such as audio, video and statuses. Other networks are seen to play a role in the creation and the distribution of content that is created by users, which is generally labelled as user-generated content. User-generated content can be defined as content that is published in a public and accessible manner which is created by the user. According to Kaplan et al. (2010), such generated content also needs to have a certain level of creativity and should be outside the commercial context.

User Interface and Features of Social Media Apps

The role of application the life cycle of customers can be easily split between certain discrete phases, such as pre-purchase, post-purchase and supporting transaction. They are put to use to increase loyalty, improve service and enhance communication. It can be utilized to enhance loyalty through increased communication and service support along with core transactions (Law et al., 2014). Certain industries gain more help from applications as compared to other industries. One example is the financial industry, which has a number of applications that make it easier for users to track expenses. On the other hand, the travel industry and the gaming industry are constantly exploring applications through which they can gather a new customer base and drive new business through improving customer experience (McCosker, 2018). Customers are also becoming sensitive and would not forgive a bad experience with an application. With new businesses looking for the use of applications for driving customer experience, they seen to try at least two failing apps first of which customers are seen to be unforgiving. Exploiting applications is more beneficial for businesses as mobile applications as customers do not prefer to use the mobile site. Wang et al. (2016) pointed out that poor performing apps with usability issues can negatively impact brand value and brand engagement.

The features of a good user interface include the ability to effectively map out the intentions of the user and functions of the application. The user interface is an important part as it affects how the user is going to interact with the application. Usability is viewed as a by-product of a good user interface. Usability is viewed as an essential part of a design, especially when designing applications for websites where the interaction takes place between a large number of users and functions (Dion and Arnould, 2018).

User interface modelling is carried out after taking into account the particular wants and needs of the user in terms of social interaction. The actual model or design of the interface itself is viewed as a key component that needs to be worked on. Generally, there are three main problems that are faced by designers when creating a user interface: interaction mechanisms, utilizing screen space and the design to be used at large (Kanuri et al., 2018). Several techniques have also been shared through which one can make an effective user interface, such as making most of the space available through the use of groups, portrait, landscape, horizontal scrolling and lists that meet the needs of various dimensions. Jabeur (2013) is a computer science teacher at Laval University who claimed that it can be challenging to meet user expectations for performance on social media applications, if users do not receive the same level of experience as they had on their desktops.

Another challenge associated with the use of mobile phones is the limitations faced in bandwidth in the current cellular networks. The second problem area faced is interaction mechanisms where one needs to look at a number of problems that can come up followed by removal, such as resolving issues linked with order of entry or cursor control.

There are a number of prevailing trends related to interface design, with particular inclinations towards increasing complexity as a number of layers are being added through which user interaction can take place. Facebook has moved beyond messages and allowed the attaching of files which removed the need for mail. There are number of interesting methods through which interaction can take place between users in social media, as well as through mobile devices, along with unique services that include data sharing and location-based services (Jabeur, 2013). Location-based services allow the user to recommend a place or deal to a friend through communicating on a social network. Data sharing services are also seen to enhance engagement through becoming an integral part of users' experience by connecting them with their friends through a network. These trends clearly point out bringing all the needs of the user to a single space.

Application developers and designers work collectively to devise strategies through which they can add to the ease of the user and ensure that relevant content is available. Significant value is present in bringing together all these elements in one interface; to achieve this a number of application developers as well as designers are updating interfaces of social media sites, such as LinkedIn, Pinterest, Instagram and Google+ through which new customers can be retained and attracted (Khamis et al., 2019).

2.9.3 Mobile Apps and Consumer Behaviour

It is safe to say that mobile applications are highly relevant today and they are changing the way brands interact with customers. Research by Iowa State University indicated a direct relation between application engagement and purchase activity (Iowa State University, 2015). The use of an application is just one factor that can influence purchase intention; other factors include product reviews and social media posts. Mobile marketing has a large span ranging from first interaction to loyalty. Mobile marketing starts off by specifying a particular target to be reached out to, followed by designing content accordingly for communication. According to Yalew et al. (2019), the end goal is to acquire users who will not only drive engagement but become loyal advocates. A number of studies have been carried out to link the characteristics of consumers with application usage. Bohmer et al. (2011) studied a large database of 4100 users and found that previous app use was highly correlated with subsequent usage of mobile applications. Marketing research has only started to uncover the cross-channel impact, which is the impact of online as well as offline buying behaviour. Research by Xu et al. (2014) showed that introducing a mobile application increases the chances of traffic in the same application, but they failed to link it with actual sales rather than just views.

Digital and social media marketing can also make it effective to interact with a specific group of potential customers through social media influencers (Shakya and Christakis, 2017). They found that reaching a particular market is easier if social media influencers are included in the marketing mix. Ensuring that the content resonates with the audiences increases the likelihood that people will talk about the relevant network. Research suggests 94% of viewers will share material if it provides value or entertainment, while 78% will share to nourish relationships with their existing network (i-scoop, 2016). Digital marketing more generally provides opportunities to identify and engage with specific target markets which are then addressed by influencers, which raises the chances of achieving increased buying behaviour of consumers.

Marketers can also use analytics to more accurately identify their target audience for a product (Knoll and Mathews, 2018).

Another important perspective with regards to social media influencers is the encouragement of customers and linking their buying behaviour strongly with external factors. Focus on the ideation, creation, execution and monitoring of social experiences that engage audiences and strategically shape perceptions. These may be tied to external events, such as seasons and holidays, conference schedules or industry milestones (Deloitte, 2018). Or they may be linked to internal happenings, such as product launches, new content releases or media events. Content, promotions, games, mobile applications and micro-sites that embrace the power of social media to achieve business objectives are possible tools (Woolley and Risen, 2018).

2.9.4 Social Media Influencers

The decision making of users is seen to be dependent on information gathered through social media. The number of opinion leaders has grown significantly in recent years; they are influential members of online communities and are also a source of advice for others (Thakur et al., 2016; Casalo et al., 2009). Several brands leverage social media influencers to build a positive relationship with their customers. Irrespective of the fame of the influencer, they can utilize their social networks and blogs to reach out to the desired customers. Brands prefer to user influencers that seem to carry greater confidence. The confidence of an influencer is extended to the brand, which leaves a long-lasting effect on the consumers by encouraging them to become a regular customer (Glucksman, 2017).

The key platforms that are being used by influencers today include YouTube, Facebook and Instagram. Now, even marketers have become influencers by creating a specialized and trusted image among customers (Marcoux, 2019). According to Maheshwari of *The New York Times*, there are chances that we might also see the emergence of micro-influencers. According to Godwin (2018), micro-influencers are ordinary individuals who have a fan following of around 1000 individuals. These influencers are not being leveraged due to their fame but rather the potential outreach they have is utilized. The endorsement of a brand by an influencer is bound to be noted by the influencer's followers. Recommendations from an authentic influencer are highly valued. An example is the success of Daniel Wellington, who can help reach out to a large number of followers without paying massive sums to celebrities as had been done in the past. Brands can now easily cut through hassles and quickly reach the desired target market

through these influencers. Zhao et al. (2018) stated that this not only gives increased visibility to the brand but also helps to establish meaningful conversation about the brand.

The fame associated with influencers has mainly been gained through them posting on social media about their passion, which allowed them to gather immense popularity. They become opinion leaders that influence other people through videos, tweets, pictures, blog spots and so on. Having a large following at their disposal means that they can easily propagate messages and encourage people to follow certain purchasing behaviour. The influencers also benefit from this activity as they can either be given a direct monetary reward or will be given free products as a form of compensation (Kristin, 2016). The benefits of social media influencers as marketing channels are presented in Figure 10.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Kristin F. (2016) "Examining the Beauty Industry's Use of Social Influencers." *Elon Communications Journal* 7

Figure 10: Social media influencers as marketing channels

Source: Kristin (2016)

Digital and social media are seen as richer marketing channels as they do not involve one-way communication as was seen in traditional media but allow two-way dialogue between a brand and its customers (Lisa, 2016). Social media influencers have capitalized on this feature to become a strong force in today's marketing environment. Every two in five marketing managers have recognized the role of social media in helping promote their brand. Similar results have been achieved around the globe; for example, Chahal (2016) reported that half of the marketers interviewed indicated that influencers play an important role in helping achieve

the desired target market and building brand engagement. However, other marketing channels still have relevance as one-quarter of the participants in Chahal’s (2016) survey mentioned that the television market was the best channel for building customer engagement. A survey carried out by Tubular Insights (2017) indicated that around 64% of individuals make a purchase after watching a branded social video. Video format has become particularly common as not only do consumers like viewing the content but also engage, such as through the comment section. Social media influencers are particularly dependent on the video format as it helps drive consumer buying behaviour. Social media has also found use in industries that are less engaging, such as finance.

Based on the literature findings and discussion presented in this section, the theoretical framework for this study has been prepared as presented in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Conceptual framework

CRM, customer relationship management. Source: extracted from Dossena et al. (2020); Han and Chen (2021); Hwang et al. (2021)

2.10 Chapter Summary

This chapter has comprehensively presented different aspects attached to the research problem and topic. Definitions of branded apps, social media and consumer behaviour have been presented separately. It has been identified in this chapter that social media marketing is frequently used by companies around the globe and by SMEs because it embeds significant potential because of its reasonable cost or investment. The trend of using mobile phones, social media and the internet is consistently increasing in the UK for shopping purposes, which gives a signal to small and medium-sized restaurants to adopt it. Consumer buying behaviour has been understood as a complex process which requires SMEs to stay in touch with their customers to address their needs and wants. Facebook, Twitter and Instagram are some popular social media platforms which are used by customers in the UK. SET and social identity theory have been identified as relevant theories in this study. A social exchange includes all unknown obligations that one marketer has towards the consumers. An example of such a relationship is that a marketer can be motivated to provide high-quality products. Social identity theory proposes that when an individual is a target, where other people act as a source of impact, then it tends to create multiplicative functions based on the number, strength and immediacy of the people. It has been mentioned in this chapter that relationship marketing and viral marketing are not only suitable for small businesses; however, in reality, small businesses are increasingly shifting their focus to relationship marketing.

A key concluding point of this chapter is that due to the advent of social media marketing, consumer buying behaviour has now become the recipient of influence from a variety of variables and factors that can be industry specific. However, the emergence of these factors has also provided firms with more options to undertake their marketing strategies and activities. A positive impact is expected on consumer behaviour in the restaurant industry in the UK when social media marketing and mobile apps-related variables function in the desired direction. This chapter also reflected on the features and attributes of mobile apps that have a major role to play in creating an impact on consumer behaviour.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the methodology that is followed in the current study and the design which led to the findings. It is presented that methodology is the procedure that facilitates the researcher to focus on their findings. It denotes the overall approach taken for data collection and analysis. This chapter presents the strategy used for the current research and provides the theoretical basis and the rationale for using a qualitative methodology. As the aim of the researcher was to ensure that the findings were reliable, and no gaps are experienced.

3.2 Ontology and Epistemology

Ontology and epistemology are two popularly used research philosophies in the literature. Ontology is a philosophy that is concerned with the nature and identification of different things by taking a general view. This philosophy intends to address two central questions: what the nature of existence is and what is existence itself. When individuals ask detailed and in-depth questions about different aspects and things, then it means they are pursuing ontological questions (O'Boyle and McDonough, 2014).

Researchers must answer the questions (in the ontological assumptions) regarding the nature of reality (Creswell, 1994). The ideas about the existence of and relationship between society, people and the world in general” is the definition of ontology given in the literature by Eriksson and Kovalainen (2008). This means and assumes that whether the reality is subjective or objective. In cases of objective reality, human beings are considered a product of the external reality; in cases of constructionist reality or subjective reality, they can shape the world within their own unique experiences (Morgan and Smircich, 1980).

The objective view considers that social reality does not depend on social actors and tends to depend on accurate measurements and observations only, whereas the subjective view considers that social reality exists in the form of the imagination of human beings and prior to a full understanding of the structure of meaning it expresses, that human processes tend to mask the reality which interpret and judge the phenomenon in consciousness. Due to this reason, human beings are considered capable of shaping the world as per their past experiences, perceptions and culture. Subjectivism causes the approach of phenomenological epistemology,

and objectivism causes the epistemological approach of positivism. However, between the extreme of subjectivism and the extreme of objectivism, there are several ontological positions on the continuum (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). The researcher's position in this research study is closer to subjectivism but lies somewhere near the middle of the continuum by accepting human beings as social actors.

The researcher in this study is of the view that human beings are capable of modifying and interpreting the surroundings to enact the reality (Morgan and Smircich, 1980). An understanding of research paradigms and philosophies is important while pursuing in-depth research activities. The incoherent taxonomy of research philosophies, and debates on the dichotomy of qualitative and quantitative research in the literature have created much complexity in pursuing in-depth research activities over the years (Saunders et al., 2009). Therefore, an adequate understanding of these concepts has become even more important for researchers. Moreover, by gaining understanding the researcher can behave innovatively in either the adaptation or selection of research methods which would not otherwise be possible.

3.3 Research Philosophy

As stated by Creswell (2015, p. 16), “we all bring a worldview (or paradigm) to our research, whether we make it explicit or not”. Creswell (2015) also argued that the set of beliefs or values that constitute how we undertake a study “may relate to what type of evidence we use to make claims (epistemology) or whether we feel that reality is multiple or singular (ontology)”. Before answering the research question, the researcher had, therefore, to define the relevant research philosophy (epistemology). Research philosophies may be divided into three types:

- Positivism, which emphasizes the importance of the research aim. It allows the researcher to separate themselves from that objective (scientific method) (Mangan et al., 2004). In positivism, the general view is that there is knowledge other than the understanding of the researcher. This means that in positivism, the researcher will never mix up the realities in their work and will keep the work objective, so that the truth outside does not have an impact on their work. This ensures consistent work in the groups and subjects.
- Realism mainly focuses on the idea that social sciences and nature might be explored using a similar approach to data collection (Ntseane, 2012).

- Interpretivism is mostly focused on developing knowledge of the world, on the basis of objectives developed for the research. This can be done by improving the knowledge of the individual by forming rational and predictable ideologies (Blaxill, 2008). This mainly focuses on the social and cultural factors of studies and provides the viewpoints towards the subjective reality.

Considering the presented definitions and the purpose of the study, interpretivism is considered the most suitable method to study consumer behaviour and the use of social media marketing strategies in the restaurant sector of the UK. As the researcher aims to focus on the subjective realities of restaurant owners, this methodology is the most suitable for the current study. This method will help the researcher to gain knowledge of the use of digital and social media marketing from the perspective of the restaurant industry and help the researcher to make recommendations to improve practices.

Furthermore, the researcher has a background of business management and has practical understanding of how risk management works; it is presented that an interpretivist research approach would be the most suitable because risk is also measured on the basis of interpretations. As the philosophical approach has been presented for the current study, the next step to be taken is understanding deductive, inductive and abductive reasoning, and why the researcher selected it.

3.4 Deductive, Inductive and Abductive Approaches

In this section, the researcher discusses two main methods of logical reasoning, deemed as the most appropriate basis for this research. Creswell (2007) stressed the importance of illustrating the research approach as an effective strategy to increase the validity of social science research. Therefore, this section describes the deductive and inductive approaches, and the benefits of combining them.

3.4.1 The Deductive Approach

In this form of approach, the researcher is expected to have a general view of the world, which they will use to test the data with implications. They present some steps similar to inductive reasoning, but the sequence will be altered. This approach uses a general to specific approach for a study. In such instances, the researcher can work on existing theories and develop findings from the work of others (Zikmund et al., 2010). The researcher might select a theory to work on. A researcher using a deductive approach creates a hypothesis based on the findings of other studies. A pictorial depiction is presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12: The deductive research process

Source: Creswell (2003)

3.4.2 The Inductive Approach

An inductive approach requires the researcher to incorporate more and more data that is related to the research topic. Once enough data is gathered, the researcher might aim to have a bird's eye view over their data. The researcher might aim to observe patterns at this stage and create a theory to explain the data. This could lead the researcher to get certain sequences from the data (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Hence, the moment this research will be used, the researcher will present the propositions for the experiences. Figure 13 presents an outline of the inductive research approach.

Figure 13: The inductive research process

Source: Creswell (2003)

3.4.3 The Abductive Approach

Unlike a deductive approach, an abductive approach, does not involve the pre-selection of a theory to be verified through the testing and formulation of hypotheses (Haig, 2005). The abductive approach moreover is not concerned with justifying and developing theory from evaluating empirical data such as, with the help of “secure observations” of singular events, which is the case when it comes to inductive approach (Haig, 2005, p. 372). However, hypotheses are developed from examining facts in an abductive approach and this infer: (i) that an existing theory may be further developed or (ii) that a new theory can be accepted and may have validity if no other explanation has greater validity (Haig, 2005; Kapitan, 1992). The abductive approach can be proceeded with or without an initial theoretical frame.

Abduction is not necessarily an alternative to induction and deduction, rather, each one may lend itself to different research objectives. Abduction, as an approach to research, provides a way of inferring new theory or the development of existing theory, and positioning against different theories such that data can contribute to and develop further the chosen research questions” (Ahrens and Chapman, 2006, p. 820). Abduction has the potential to meet the challenge of recognizing the researcher’s experience as a methodological approach, in a manner that would not undermine but rather enhance the research (Thomas, 2010).

The deductive, inductive and abductive approaches can complement each other. In a few instances, researchers incorporate different approaches, such as deductive and inductive methods; they may start their research with one method, but later realize that this method is not suitable for them, so they start using another method.

Therefore, the inductive approach is deemed most appropriate for this research, because it will benefit from the researcher’s experience as a management professional. An inductive approach will lead to the formulation of various theoretical assumptions underlying contemporary marketing trends.

One main difference that can be stated between the deductive approach and the inductive approach is that the deductive approach aims to test a theory and confirm its accuracy, whereas the inductive approach aims to build new theories from current theory (Saunders et al., 2012). This is precisely what the research objectives outlined earlier require to be addressed effectively (i.e., the accuracy of digital marketing). This study’s aims and objectives do not

revolve around testing any existing theory or concept, instead they are about producing a new theory/mechanism, which indicates that the inductive approach is feasible.

It is presented that inductive reasoning is linked with qualitative research design and deductive is linked with quantitative research design. This is based on general ideology, as it supports the evidence based on numbers and collected in the study. This kind of study offers more flexibility and can be fruitful to address the objectives of the study. Such an approach stresses that studies can be carried out with the help of existing evidence, but the reliance of the study will not be on those facts. Each study in this kind of approach is different as it helps in finding new elements. Considering this fact, this kind of methodology will be feasible for the current research, as it will help in finding new facts about the use of social media in the case of the restaurant industry.

3.5 Research Design

Research design can be defined as a systematic procedure that defines how different tasks are to be carried out in a research study (Creswell, 2012). One key benefit of research design is that it provides a clear path to be followed by researchers and guides them in the right direction without distractions. It provides the strategy to be followed in detail. The research starts off by framing the problem statement of the research work. Next, the sampling approach has to be determined which involves calculating sample size and location. Different operating variables of the study are identified along with a mechanism for measuring these variables. The last part relates to the collection, interpretation and dissemination of results. A good research design will allow different components of the research to connect with each other in a sound manner (Kumar, 2014). In the same manner, the data gathered needs to link with the research purpose, theoretical and conceptual framework, and method of data analysis. The theoretical and conceptual framework should also be in line with the research purpose and goals being pursued.

Saunders et al. (2009) stated that an effective research design is the overall scheme of any particular study for answering the research questions. The researcher needs to be aware of the various methods available for qualitative research in order to ensure the applicability of the method. Some factors that the researcher can consider here are qualitative versus quantitative as presented in Figure 14.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Kumar, R., (2014) *Research Methodology: A Step-by-Step Guide for Beginners* (Google eBook) 4th Ed., London: SAGE

Figure 14: Comparison between qualitative and quantitative methods

Source: Kumar (2014)

3.5.1 Adopting the Qualitative approach

A qualitative approach was critical for this research, as it helps in finding data in the form of words and narratives. As the researcher aimed to collect data in the form of interviews, the qualitative research method was the most suitable. This method helped the researcher to find the ideologies of the participants, which are rooted in their subconscious, towards the use of social media and the interviews also helped the researcher to work with the participants in their natural setting. Participants chose the time and place of the interviews, which made it feasible for them to provide true responses, and give their true feelings, to the questions. As per Cohen and Crabtree (2006), the qualitative method helps in the collection of data in natural settings. This fact was verified by Blaxter et al. (2006). Interviews allow the interviewer to probe the participants by asking open-ended questions to get as much information as possible (Dörnyei, 2007). Considering this fact, the interviewer was able to eliminate any challenges and misunderstandings in the collection of the data, providing more accuracy to the results (Alshenqeeti, 2014). In addition to the advantages and benefits presented earlier, the interviewer as well as the interviewee benefit from this method due to its flexibility and the presentation of particular points that cannot be applied using a quantitative method. Due to this, the interview method enables understanding of the answers to certain questions and seek information (Mack et al., 2005).

This research will focus on several organizations in a specific sector (restaurants) and on a specific geographic region, given the dearth of such research, as indicated earlier. Hence, considering the qualitative approach, the collection of data can be done by focusing on various restaurants; the researcher is capable to understand, investigate and analyse the data on the basis of the natural environment of the interviewees.

3.6 Sampling Approach

The sample for this research was identified by deploying the non-probability sampling technique, specifically, “purposive sampling”. This kind of method is used when the sole aim is to gather data on the basis of achieving the study’s objectives. Given the occurrence of the notable contextual factor of COVID-19, the process of reaching a suitable sample size was difficult and complex.

Accordingly, the researcher chose the participants from the restaurant industry by focusing on London, which is a hub of international tourists and businesses. In this research, the respondents were selected from the managerial and supervisory staff of restaurants, who form an integral part of the social and digital media marketing in restaurant organizations. Using non-probability sampling, the research collected data from restaurant managers preferably and shift managers/supervisors.

3.7 Using Thematic Method of Data Analysis

In order to carry out analysis of the interviews, thematic analysis was the most suitable approach. This approach was suitable because it works well with the objectives and aim of the study (Ryan and Bernard, 2000). Some authors promote the fact that thematic analysis is beneficial to forming a reliable analysis, whereas others do not believe in the effectiveness of the method (Nowell et al., 2017). This method helps in the generation of themes that help in capturing the studied phenomenon (Ryan and Bernard, 2000). It is a method used to identify, analyse and report themes within data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Thematic analysis was applied in the current study, as the study aims to get common elements from the responses given by the participants. Braun and Clarke (2006) argued that thematic analysis should be considered a method in its own right and highlighted a number of points that should be considered when using this method. For example, they suggested that when beginning thematic analysis, it is important to consider the ontological and epistemological framework being followed, whether coding shall be semantic or latent and whether it shall be used inductively or deductively (Clarke and Braun, 2016).

A key reason why NVIVO tool has not been used in this study is the problems faced during data collection process due to COVID-19 i.e., collection of data had to be stopped multiple times and these unintended breaks in data collection made it difficult to use NVIVO tool because the researcher had only basic level of understanding about using this tool. The development of themes and sub-themes is also achieved in two and three different phases which made manual method feasible as compared to NVIVO which had certain risks involved if used in phases. The process of learning advanced features of NVIVO is time consuming and difficult (Zamawe, 2015) which was a mental barrier for the researcher in the midst of pressure and stress posed by already challenging COVID-19 factor and data collection process.

In the current study the researcher obtained a number of themes from the responses given by the interviewees. Some themes were identified as common themes presented by the participants, whereas some were unique and provided different insights and perspectives about the use of social media marketing in the restaurant sector. Patton (1990) suggested that the analysis begins with semantic description before progressing to interpretation, which attempts to explain the patterns and their wider meanings and implications. As a result, thematic analysis can be used to summarize and interpret the data.

Braun and Clarke (2006) identified a six-step approach to doing thematic analysis. They noted that the steps do not need to be approached in a linear fashion as the researcher may need to move back and forth between the stages. Braun and Clarke's (2006) steps for thematic analysis are as follows:

The researcher familiarized themselves with the information collected, so that they could make notes with more accuracy. After notes, coding was done to grasp the analytics ideas from the responses. These were developed on the basis of available concepts frequent in the data. The themes were presented in the form of codes. The themes were allocated names on the basis of the information they held. The analysis was written up within a report.

3.8 Reliability and Validity

In order to conduct credible research. Reliability plays a critical role in terms of the authenticity of a study (Thomas, 2003). Reliability refers to the accuracy and precision of the results attained by a researcher by choosing the most suitable and unbiased method of study. The reliability of the study is calculated on the basis that the aims and objectives of the study are truly addressed in the study. Validity refers to the authenticity of the research and is measured when the researcher aims to focus on the extent to which the results can be generalized. Hence, in such a study, the use of scholarly resources, journal articles and high-impact factors studies are incorporated and reviewed to gather literature and defend the results. When information is collected through authentic sources and reviewed properly, this assures and increases a study's reliability. Careful consideration was given to the selection of reliable journals and articles, and primary data, by considering reliability and validity factors.

Information was collected through adequately designed interview questions with customers who buy using online platforms (i.e., digital and mobile applications). The procedures and processes employed for the collection of data were reviewed in order to ensure their consistency (Somekh and Lewin, 2006). In the collection of data, it is important to ensure that the information collected is unbiased; therefore, the researcher consciously tried to not exhibit any kind of personal bias while developing the interview questions and while interpreting the gathered results. For this purpose, the researcher took the critique of their supervisor seriously and made sure that questions were an adequate reflection of the literature review, conceptual framework and research objectives. Using a consistency tool is crucial in ensuring the relevancy and occurrence of unrepeated data. Moreover, validity can be ensured by the creation of metric reliability. However, it is not necessary that a reliable assessment is always valid as well.

Reliability and validity are crucial aspects in improving the validity of research. Respondent validation was used by the researcher in this study to manage the reliability and validity (i.e., the respondents of interviews were asked to comment on the transcripts that were prepared). Respondents were asked to comment whether the concepts and themes created sufficiently reflected the research topic under investigation and their perceptions.

Validity is regarded as the extent to which the data interpretations are accurate and the way in which these are suitably used (Boddy, 2016). When the research results are good enough to be believed and truthful, it ensures that the study has validity. In this research, the research's validity was ensured by giving attention to these details. In order to ensure and determine validity, a series of questions were posed, and the research aimed at answering those questions. The study is relevant in the light of research studies conducted by others. Reliability has also been defined as the consistency of results under repetition of experiment with similar methodologies. In this case, the research instrument utilized is aligned with the nature and direction of research objectives.

Different types of procedures for validity can be used in the measuring of a specific construct (Mahmood, 2017). In this research study, special concern was shown towards the validity of the research by considering, understanding and adhering to these mentioned factors. It is important to be aware of the procedure of measurement to have a construct with strong validity

and this increases with time. It is not correct to make a statement that a procedure has an established validity construct, or it is permanent.

Overall, a researcher should be aware that even if a measurement procedure is shown to have strong construct validity, this is something that develops gradually over time. Surface validity or face validity is also known as appearance validity for any research study; it is the evaluation of the validity of the measurement processes or procedures employed in the research study (Colepicolo, 2015). Several factors are considered important in this regard, including balance in the research, racial prejudice, speed, anxiety and emotions. The research must reflect the measure it is going to or has measured, which makes face validity important for researchers.

3.8.1 Content Validity

Content validity is related with the adequacy of the instrument in covering the entire content in relation to its variables. Content validity refers to the evaluation of whether an instrument covers the entire content regarding the variables and the construct, which was developed for measurement (Walter, 2006). The validity of the content ensures that the measurement tool and assessment of different aspects of construction under study has been done accurately. This research study ensured the validity of the content as the questions of the study strictly assessed the construct under study (i.e., within the specific scope of digital/social media marketing and mobile applications). The responses to the interview questions were in line with the research objectives (i.e., all the responses fell under the scope of the research objectives). Content validity can be threatened by several factors influencing the responses of respondents. In this research study, detailed content was sourced and incorporated using previous studies for and against the set research topic. Most of the time, content validity is measured by dependence on the information of people related to the construct under measurement. Experts on the subject are given access to the tool of measurement and feedback is received about the measurement of the construct under question. The effectiveness of every set question is decided after an analysis of feedback. In this study, interview questions were used for data collection and this tool embedded the potential of addressing research problems that are wide in scope, giving good adherence to content validity.

3.8.2 Face Validity

The representation of a research project is evaluated through face validity. This determines how a project looks at face value. In short, it is about the good or bad appearance of a project. Face validity is done through reading plans and evaluating the research validity. It is also known as representation validity. Face validity should not be neglected because of its weak measurement of validity (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Therefore, in this research study, special attention was given to face validity by keeping and maintaining an alignment across all the research sections and chapters.

Moreover, the literature review section strictly addressed and covered the research objectives despite its comprehensive nature (i.e., case examples, theoretical perspectives, conceptual framework and arguments of other scholars/researchers strictly remained within the scope of the research objectives and problem statement). The interview questions, as a data collection tool, also revolved directly or indirectly around the key focus, conceptual framework, literature findings and objectives of this study. Therefore, a considerable effort was made to ensure the presence of face validity in terms of the research direction, route, nature and scope.

In addition, a reflective journal was maintained by the researcher covering the decisions taken by the researcher in a documented form. The process of debriefing was made comprehensive to assist the researcher in uncovering biases that were taken for granted. For example, the general and background questions were not focused on the topic itself, however the later questions gradually became highly focused, and a holistic approach was adopted. Reflexivity was also used in questioning the researcher's own judgments, decisions and practices that could have affected the research process. Lastly, other recent doctoral theses were reviewed to identify how their interview questions were designed and how their process of analysis was conducted so that this research process could be conducted by learning from others as well.

3.9 Ethical Considerations

It is necessary to protect participants through the application of appropriate ethical principles. Such principles are seen to be more relevant in the case of qualitative research as it involves a study that is in-depth in nature, such as the use of semi structured interviews. The particular situation of face-to-face interview could make participants vulnerable. Participants may feel uncomfortable during the interview process; therefore, care should be taken to make them feel

safe. The privacy and anonymity of participants have to be ensured as each participant has the right to them. Care should be taken to not collect information relating to the identity of the individual in any form. This right of anonymity also extends to the group or organization that is taking part in the research. The current research showed due regard towards the privacy and anonymity of the individual as no personal information was collected in any part of the research process. Every individual taking part in the research was presumed to have the right of having their identity protected. A research participant also has the right to understand the purpose for which the research is being carried out and they will not be forced to take part in the research. The research ethics mentioned may seem easy to follow on paper but applying them can be challenging as groups may feel that they cannot refuse when asked to participate in research. This pressure can come from different sources, such as from peers or superiors. All participants were expected to show their consent to participating in the research in written form. The participants were personally approached in order to explain to them the purpose of the research along with gaining their consent. Adequate time was also allotted to them for understanding the research purpose and asking any questions that potentially came up. It was clearly mentioned that participation was voluntary and withdrawing from the study would not have any impact on their job.

4. Results

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the results that were gathered with the application of the semi-structured interview technique of data collection. These results will be presented in table format and textual paragraph format to aid understanding. The interpretation of the results is intended to be made easy due to which the proper and formal presentation of the gathered results will be conducted in this chapter. Interview questions used in the data collection process were aligned with the research aim and objectives, due to which the sequence of results for each question will be presented so that the logical flow of the results can be maintained and understood. This will help in carrying out the discussion on the results in the next chapter. Twenty restaurants based in London were targeted for data collection; therefore, the results consist of responses given by 20 respondents. One respondent from each restaurant was included in the data collection process. Respondents were cooperative and they showed interest in answering the questions due to which meaningful results were gathered. Transcripts of three restaurants as respondents are provided in Appendix A. Before presenting the results and conducting the discussion it is important to showcase the details of restaurants from where the qualitative data has been collected with the help of semi-structured interviews.

Restaurant Sr No	Restaurant Allocated Code	Interviewee Position
1	A	Manager
2	B	Manager
3	C	Owner/CEO
4	D	Owner/CEO
5	E	Floor Manager
6	F	Owner/CEO
7	G	Manager

8	H	Manager
9	I	Manager
10	J	Owner/CEO
11	K	Owner/CEO
12	L	Manager
13	M	Manager
14	N	Manager
15	O	Owner/CEO
16	P	Owner/CEO
17	Q	Owner/CEO
18	R	Owner/CEO
19	S	Manager
20	T	Manager

4.2 Interpretation and Presentation of Results

Q.1 Why is the use of social media and mobile apps for marketing purposes in restaurant industry important?

All respondents gave an answer to this question. The number of respondents giving similar answers are categorized for clarity (i.e., brackets will indicate the chosen answer). All respondents (20/20) said Yes social media marketing is Very important (no shop no Uber Eats only working from social media) +1(because everyone has smartphone and use social media) +1(increase audience) +1(personal connection with customer)+1+1(brand name awareness)+1(everyone on social media)+1+1(targeted marketing in north London)+1(important for small business)+1(more audience and customers).

Respondents from the targeted restaurants gave answers to this question which mostly differed from one another in terms of the reasons stated and only a few respondents gave similar answers; however, the overall embedded theme exhibited by the answers was positive. For example, respondent of restaurants **A/D/E/K/L/M** answered that social media and mobile apps are important for marketing purposes because they allow businesses to keep in touch with their customers and develop a personal connection, which helps in retaining the customers. Some respondents, including restaurants **B/C/J/N/O/Q**, answered that the prevalence of social media and smartphones is increasing visibly across the country, which makes the use of these platforms important for marketing purposes. Restaurant **P** answered that social media is an affordable and efficient way to reach out to customers, especially when a business is new in the market, which makes it important for the brands. Some respondents, including restaurants **A/B/F/O/Q**, answered that brand awareness is a key benefit that businesses can achieve by using social media and mobile apps for marketing their products, which ultimately makes it important for businesses. The answers gathered to this question reflect the significance of the first major theme ‘use of social media platforms and its sub-theme ‘positive aspects’. This first question fits well in the scope of the first major theme. To sum up the results of this question, it can be said that all the restaurants knew their survival and progression today depended significantly on their social media presence. Quotations from two respondents is presented below which are reflecting the interpretation and direction of the result trend against this question:

Respondent1: “Because you can reach a bigger audience that you typical wouldn’t using traditional marketing”.

Respondent2: “To increase recognition of restaurant and establish a name for ourselves”.

Q.2 What kind of social media and mobile apps do you use for marketing purposes?

All respondents answered this question. The respondents chose or named more than one social media app due to which the frequency of this selection will be reflected here clearly. The most used apps were Instagram=**20/20**, Facebook=**14/20**, Twitter=**2/20**, snapchat=**1**, TikTok=**4/20**, WhatsApp=**4/20**, email=**1**, Google=**2/20**, own app=**1/20**.

The answers to this question showed a primarily one-sided trend with some answers indicating a slightly different trend. For example, a majority of the restaurants answered that Instagram

was their preferred method of marketing, which means that Instagram as a premier social media app possesses significant importance for restaurants across London. Facebook was the second most popular social media platform being used for marketing purposes by the restaurants that were targeted for data collection. TikTok and WhatsApp were chosen by some restaurants; very few of them used Twitter, Snapchat, or their own restaurant apps to market their products. There could be several technical, social, and technological reasons for preferring Instagram and Facebook as marketing platforms; however, this study is focused primarily on the impact of social media apps on restaurants. The answers to this question are related to and point towards another major theme ‘Friends and family influence’ and its sub-theme ‘Facebook and Instagram posts’ making it clear that the development of themes is strictly in line with the direction of the results. The result of this question certainly indicates a trend that will need attention during the development of recommendations for restaurants. Quotations from two respondents is presented below which are reflecting the interpretation and direction of the result trend against this question:

Respondent1: “Instagram and Facebook”.

Respondent2: “I use WhatsApp, Instagram, Snapchat and just started using TikTok”.

Q.3 Are you using paid advertisements on social media apps for your restaurant and does this increase your customers? Why?

All respondents answered this question. The number of respondents giving similar answers were categorized for clarity (i.e., along with some quotes from the respondents). All respondents (20/20) said they used paid advertisements, and they increased audience. Restaurant **C** said, “received free advertisements voucher from Instagram”, **D** “of course”, restaurant **E** said, “not sure if paid advertisements have helped or not, I also linked Instagram to Uber Eats” and **N** said, “paid advertisements increased monthly sales by 30%”.

The answers to this question were varied and it was clear that restaurants operate with different mindsets and approaches, which are similar only to a small extent. For restaurant **A** “It doesn’t always get extra customers. But helps awareness to a larger audience”; that is, paid advertisements help increase their online followers and brand awareness, but they cannot be sure if their customer numbers increased solely because of paid advertisements. However, a majority of restaurants, including **A/B/F/I/J/M/N/O/R/T**, answered those paid advertisements

certainly improved visibility and the presence of their brand across customer base on social media. Some restaurants mentioned that their per day visits on social media pages was increased as a result of paid advertisements; however, only restaurant N answered that their sales and number of customers increased as a result of paid advertisements on social media. A majority of restaurants however experienced and believed that only non-financial benefits can be availed with the help of social media paid advertisements. Overall, the results of this question contribute towards the development of a major theme ‘Paid and unpaid use of social media’ and validate this theme as well.

Quotations from three respondents is presented below which are reflecting the interpretation and direction of the result trend against this question:

Respondent1: “yes, paid ads on Instagram”.

Respondent2: “yes. We were gifted some sponsored adds from Instagram, but we have not pursued them ourselves. not sure yet if this increases our customers”.

Respondent3: “I’ve used paid ads once, and that’s because Instagram gave me a £20 voucher”.

Q.4 Do you use social media apps to give new offers, promotions and discounts and what response do you get?

All respondents answered this question. The number of respondents giving similar answers are categorized for clarity (i.e., brackets will indicate the chosen answer). Yes, we give offers and discounts on social media apps by restaurants=**14/20**, offers and discount on restaurant website=**1/20**, offer and discount by Uber Eats=**1/20**, no offers=**4/20**.

The answers to this question were mostly one-sided and indicated a specific trend (i.e., social media apps are beneficial when it comes to using them for offering discounts and new promotional offers). Only restaurant A answered that they have not used social media apps so far for promoting new offers and for giving discounts to customers, instead they use their website to offer discounts or offers. Restaurant B said, “discounts and offers are offered by Uber Eats”. Restaurants E/G/L/M/N/T found it useful to give promotional offers via social media apps because it allowed them to receive feedback from customers, which was valuable for them. The answers to this question relating to the sub-themes ‘Brand visibility for home-based brands’ and ‘Impact on brand awareness and visibility’ developed against the major

theme 'Paid and unpaid use of social media'. Moreover, it can be noted that a logical flow has been maintained between data collection phase and literature review findings as a result of which the identification of themes and the development of sub-themes is making sense and gives an opportunity to address the research objectives and aim.

Quotations from two respondents is presented below which are reflecting the interpretation and direction of the result trend against this question:

Respondent1: "We show specials we have on offer but not discounts and good response to these".

Respondent2: "I use social media to give promos, I do everything on social media there is no shopfront so I get all my customer through social media, also I'm only a few weeks in so I can't really say if the promos/discount brings in more business".

Q.5 How do you compare the effectiveness of marketing for your business before and after social media apps adoption? Why do you say that?

All respondents gave an answer to this question. The number of respondents giving similar answers are categorized for clarity (i.e., brackets will indicate the chosen answer). No comparison because social media is first marketing platform, **18/20** said that social media marketing is the first marketing they have ever done. "Can't evaluate because new start-up" "very good target marketing for Asian Desi community" **1/20** restaurant said, "business increased after using social media as compared to traditional marketing tools." **1/20** said "not sure if it helps".

The answers to this question were not one-sided as varied responses were received from targeted restaurants. This variation in the answers indicated that there are other noticeable factors that play a key role and can certainly implicate on the usefulness of social media apps as a marketing tool for restaurants. For example, restaurants **M/N/P/Q/A** are not sure yet about the effectiveness of social media apps for marketing purposes because their businesses are relatively new, and they are not in a comfortable position to give their verdict in this regard. However, restaurants **B/C/F/H/R** answered that their sales certainly go up when they use social media apps for marketing, which was not the case with traditional marketing methods. For most of the restaurants, improved visibility and access to a large number of customers was the

unique advantage that social media apps provide to restaurants, and this makes the post-social media adoption time period more productive and fruitful.

The answers to this question are related to and validate the development of sub-themes ‘Attracting customers’, ‘Promotions and discounts’ and ‘Impact on brand awareness and visibility’ presented in the thematic table in the next chapter. The answers to this question have given validity to the identified sub-themes which will assist in drawing conclusions and developing recommendations.

Quotations from three respondents is presented below which are reflecting the interpretation and direction of the result trend against this question:

Respondent1: “Well, my company is new, and we have only used social media marketing. We started our business 1 month ago”.

Respondent2: “We are quite new so I wouldn’t be able to comment on this yet”.

Respondent3: “I’ve only ever used social media there is no before social media for me”.

Q.6 Do you think social media posts about food or restaurants by friends and family members impact customer buying behaviour?

All respondents gave an answer to this question. The number of respondents giving similar answers are categorized. All of the respondents said that social media posts by friends and family always help. For example, here are three quotes from restaurants: Restaurant C “good advertisement by friends”, restaurant F “dramatic increase in sales when someone posts about our restaurant” and restaurant I “customers bring people from their circle”.

The answer to this question embeds diverse avenues as all the restaurants answered this question with more interest. Since all restaurants agreed that social media posts about food/restaurant produced a positive impact on buying behaviour of customers, it gives a clear picture about the importance of friends and family when using social media marketing for restaurants. However, the reasons and methods based on which restaurants gave this positive one-sided response differed. For example, restaurants A/B/D/G/H/I/K/M/O and others mentioned that all social media apps are helpful in this regard, as many of their customers have referred them to their friends and family. This resulted in increasing their sales and customer base. This finding holds value and is in line with the academic literature because different

scholars have mentioned the effectiveness of this marketing method, which is called WOM. Whether it is friends and family referrals or verbal recommendations, or it is the use of social media influencers who in a way also use their own experiences in the form of WOM to motivate their followers towards the respective brand.

As stated by Barker et al. (2016), the best marketing with social networks leads from the customers and not the businesses themselves. Arnd was one of the pioneers who defined WOM in 1967 as a person-to-person verbal communication. WOM includes a speaker and a listener discussing some products or services without commercial purpose. With the increase in the acceptability of the internet, WOM has changed to electronic WOM. Electronic WOM is defined as communication directed to customers of a particular brand by usage of social media or internet in general for the purposes of promotion (Litvin et al., 2008, pp. 147-169). It is further clarified that Facebook is the most dominant internet tool for small entrepreneurs as it can be used to put influence of particular brands and services through electronic WOM and relevant communication practices. The major factors that have contributed positively to the success of electronic WOM include participation rate, innovation, participation and experiences over time.

WOM has been acknowledged by a majority of the restaurants as an effective method of getting new customers. The level of conviction exhibited by the restaurants while giving this answer reflected that friends and family are a critical success factor of their social media marketing. Taking pictures of the food and then tagging friends and family on Instagram and Facebook is a popular method of marketing for a majority of the restaurants. Trust is another key factor identified from the answers given by a majority of restaurants (i.e., friends and family possess a good level of trust which gives them confidence of visiting the restaurant and giving online orders from the respective restaurant. Some restaurants observed improvement in their brand presence as a result of friends and family tagging and referrals. The answers to this question validated the development of the major theme 'Paid and unpaid use of social media' and three sub-themes 'Food vlogs', 'Sharing pictures' and 'Social media influencers'.

The consistent relevance and embedded nature of the themes and sub-themes with the answers to interview questions reaffirms the interconnectedness of the research objectives, literature review findings and research methodology adopted. Moreover, this interconnectedness is also helpful in improving the reliability of the discussion and conclusion to be presented next in this

thesis. Quotations from three respondents is presented below which are reflecting the interpretation and direction of the result trend against this question:

Respondent1: “yes”.

Respondet2: “yes”.

Respondent3: “yes”.

Q.7 Do you think social media influencers and food vloggers can help in attracting new customers?

All respondents gave an answer to this question. The number of respondents giving similar answers are categorized for clarity. The results showed that **10/20** responders said social media influencers can help in attracting customers. Restaurant **A** said “yes, it can help but I never used”, restaurant **C** said, “yes, it helps but for short time” and restaurant **G** said, “yes, depends on the followers of influencers”. However, **7/20** restaurants responded that they did not believe influencers can help in attracting new customers. Restaurant **I** said, “increase followers but no sales”, restaurant **K** said, “they are only after money and can promote anyone who offer them money” “used them but not benefit”. Also, **3/20** responded they were not sure.

Different opinions emerged from the answers to this question, which is a positive sign from the discussion point of view. The answers to this question were longer than the others and indicated some important aspects for the purpose of conducting a discussion and then devising recommendations in this study. Restaurant **B** replied that they have used food vloggers and influencers because a vast majority of customers do listen to and follow social media influencers. Restaurant **B** is of the view that if a social media influencer or food vlogger recommends something, then their community will probably build its opinion on what the influencer or food vlogger said. Most of the time, it increases sales, then increases followers. First, people will try the food recommended by the influencers and once they have tried it, they will commit to the brand by following it on social media. Therefore, this process becomes important for restaurants from a marketing perspective. Restaurant **I** stated that they do not believe in the effectiveness of social media influencers and food vloggers because followers will increase, but they are not the people who buy products.

Social media influencers and food vloggers can attract people, but they are not effective for sales, although they help increase brand awareness and presence. However, most of the respondents have not used any social media influencer themselves which means that their answer is based on their personal judgement and subjective knowledge. A few other restaurants stated their opinion that social media influencers are not useful when it comes to increasing customer base and sales. For example, restaurant **K** mentioned that social media influencers and food vloggers are only after fame or financial gain.

Anyone that sponsors the influencers would be advertised. Rather than propagating quality, health or taste-driven food, they will post nearly anything which minimizes their positive impact on the followers. Some restaurants pointed out that social media influencers and food vloggers post with such frequency that their reviews or recommendations become meaningless. For example, restaurant **L** stated that they have used social media influencers in the past and have not had a lot of success in attracting new customers.

Most of the food bloggers have a lot of similar food pictures on their page and it is very likely for your brand to disappear in their feed. Although food bloggers are great for some free food photography (in return for some food) they have not worked so well for restaurants to get more customers. The answers to this question have validated the development and use of the major theme 'Paid and unpaid use of social media' and three sub-themes 'Food vlogs', 'Sharing pictures' and 'Social media influencers'. The answers to this question have provided a clear perspective that the desired benefits of using social media influencers and food vloggers were not achieved by the restaurants, apart from in a few cases where it worked in the desired way. This provides scope for developing appropriate recommendations which can address this issue faced by restaurants when using social media influencers for marketing purposes.

Quotations from two respondents is presented below which are reflecting the interpretation and direction of the result trend against this question:

Respondent1: "yes".

Respondent2: "yes definitely, whenever a blogger reviews my food i see activity on my page go up".

Q.8 In what ways do you think the current use of social media and mobile apps can be improved for making them more effective in influencing consumer buying behaviour?

All respondents gave an answer to this question. The number of respondents giving similar answers are categorized. The results showed that **7/20** respondents said they were not sure about how to improve social media apps for restaurant business, whereas **13/20** respondents gave their recommendations on how to improve apps. Most of the recommendations were about more features and tools for apps. Restaurant **B** said, “algorithms on Instagram should be changed”, restaurant **J** said more “live videos options and details needed” and restaurant **G** said, “apps should add features to show customer reviews”.

The answers to this question showed diverse opinions and indicated the variety that exists in the perception and understanding of the restaurants about improving the use of social media apps to influence the buying behaviour of consumers. Restaurant **K** stated that social media platforms are not specifically designed for the food industry and an improvement should be to add food-focused features. However, a majority of restaurants, including **A/F/I/M/N/R/T**, stated that more features are required to make social media and mobile apps more feasible to make them more effective.

Restaurant **C** stated that integrating a purchase system in the apps could be useful; however, they were not able to give a precise explanation of what they were saying. Restaurant **D** gave a unique answer: if everyone does what they do best, they will be successful no matter what, this is the case in social media or in normal life. This answer is driven by ambitions and emotions with a less pragmatic aspect.

Quotations from two respondents is presented below which are reflecting the interpretation and direction of the result trend against this question:

Respondent1: “Algorithms on Instagram should be changed”.

Respondent2: “I’m not sure, haven’t really thought about it sorry”.

Q.9 How has the COVID-19 crisis impacted your sales and marketing?

The answers to this question were majorly one-sided, apart from few restaurants who answered it differently (i.e., for some restaurants COVID-19 posed challenges and for some it gave opportunities). Restaurant **A** said, “just started before pandemic. But all festivals etc. got

cancelled due to pandemic”. On the whole, a majority of restaurants stated that COVID-19 crisis had affected the sales of restaurants and they had to shift their focus to online selling and ultimately devising online marketing strategies. A few of the restaurants, including **B/H/J/Q**, were started during the lockdown period, because it gave them the opportunity to cater to the needs of the customers by providing home delivery services. Restaurant **E** said, “I’m the owner, I started around a few weeks ago, I’ve seen a few start-ups from home, having a lot of free time during lockdown has given me an opportunity to start up my own business”. Restaurant **P** said its online business just started a month ago, “And yeah, I thought as people can’t eat out, I’d provide delivery of premium burgers”. Restaurant **H** said “started in October 2020. Had to change to takeout and change menu ideas and prices”. Existing restaurants have opted towards marketing on social media apps and have adequately managed the challenges posed by COVID-19.

The answers to this question highlighted the importance of a key factor in the context of this study: COVID-19 and lockdown as drivers of change. Interestingly, the answers to this question assisted in the development of a major theme ‘Impact of pandemic/COVID-19’ and a sub-theme ‘New opportunities. This also indicates the alignment and relevance of the themes and sub-themes with the scope and objectives of this study.

Quotations from two respondents is presented below which are reflecting the interpretation and direction of the result trend against this question:

Respondent1: “started in october2020. Had to change to takeout and change menu ideas and prices”.

Respondent2: “drop in sales”

Q.10 What recommendations would you make to restaurant business owners on the use of social media and apps, and do you recommend using social media for marketing?

All respondents gave an answer to this question. All the respondents recommended small and medium-sized restaurants use social media marketing.

The answers to this question were quite one-sided in a positive way as all the restaurants recommended the use of social media for marketing purposes. The reasons and arguments given were somewhat different; however, a clear trend was extracted of using social media for marketing. Restaurant **J** stated that it would definitively recommend food business owners to

use social media as restaurants need to know their targets to be able to use the good ones and to be able to use them right. Some restaurants, including **A/B/E/F/L** stated that they would suggest restaurant businesses to use social media marketing because it can reach people and increase the popularity of the brand. Restaurant **S** stated that developing a social media presence before starting business operations is important to give a boost to the business when it actually starts. Restaurant **D** stated that if done right, social media marketing is a great tool for any restaurant to attract new customers. During lockdown and COVID-19 crisis, people spent a lot more time on their phones and social media; therefore, social media presence and marketing can make a big difference. Financial and non-financial benefits were cited as reasons why the restaurants recommended the use of social media for marketing purposes.

Overall, the results indicated that Instagram and Facebook are the two most frequently used social media platforms. Twitter and WhatsApp are used relatively less for marketing purposes. Paid advertisements were mostly used to create brand awareness across a large audience and for more exposure or visibility across the consumer market. Social media advertisements were used to maintain brand image, whereas websites were being used to offer discounts to customers. Some restaurants used third-party marketing, for example, Uber Eats does promotions on behalf of an actual restaurant because they have extensive reach to customers.

Importantly, restaurants exhibited that this using social media has proven to be useful in attracting customers. It has been noted that social media platforms are very helpful for attracting teenagers and the younger generation. No mechanism is being developed and used by restaurants to measure the effectiveness of social media platforms in terms of their impact on sales and revenues. This has indicated a need for developing a comparative analysis tool for restaurants, which they can use to determine the performance of their social media platforms and traditional marketing methods. Some restaurants used the statistics recorded by Instagram, which helped them conduct a comparison of performance. Some restaurants had recently started their business, due to which they have neither conducted, nor are they able to conduct, a comparison. The dynamics for the food and restaurant industry are unique and it was indicated by some restaurant owners that there is a need to develop a specific and relevant tool for making comparisons for this industry. Restaurant owners noted that when they do promotions and marketing on social media platforms, especially Instagram, then their brand awareness increases, and it helps to attract and retain customers.

A significant impact of WOM was noticed by the restaurants when their customers referred them to their family and friends. However, they also noticed that it depended on the opinion of the customers, if a customer is convincing enough then they can positively influence their friends and family. This indicates the usefulness of posts on restaurants created by customers as this builds the trust for a potential customer, which then results in an increase of sales and consequently an increase in social media followers.

Social media influencers were perceived as effective at promoting the business of the restaurants from where data has been collected. Some restaurants noticed that when social media influencers' post or share food vlogs about their food, then the activity on their social media pages increases; however, not all restaurants experienced an increase in sales as a result of social media influencers' posts. All restaurants agreed that brand awareness and presence increase across social media when they are supported by social media influencers.

In terms of improving social media and mobile apps to drive consumer buying behaviour, most of the restaurants were not sure how to do it. However, a few restaurant owners stated that Instagram should initiate the same rating system which Google uses instead of relying on "likes" of the pages.

Most restaurants indicated that originality has value in the eye of customers; therefore, it is important for restaurants to maintain their originality and capitalize on it in a positive way. To present the results from the responses given by the respondents, the researcher conducted a thematic analysis by obtaining common themes from the answers of individuals. The table of significant themes, sub-themes and common themes can be seen in the next chapter; it will be discussed further in line with this chapter.

Quotations from two respondents is presented below which are reflecting the interpretation and direction of the result trend against this question:

Respondents1: Utilize it to the best. We launched our whole business via social media, and it has been good Now it's a matter of retaining the customers.

Respondent2: Definitely should use, I only get business through social media at the moment, and it is doing well, I'm still pretty small and not enough people know about me. I've seen other burger pages advertise and do their market properly and the hype

around their burger's food has been through the roof. If social media is used properly, you can and will do well.

4.3 Chapter Summary

This chapter presented the results gathered with the help of a qualitative research methodology from the 20 targeted restaurants as sample respondents. Codes were allocated to the 20 restaurants for the purpose of presenting the results coherently and in a logical flow. This chapter briefly presented the answers given to each interview question. It was found that respondents representing the restaurants shared some common and some different views about the importance of social media as a marketing tool. The role of friends and family were cited as important in making the use of social media marketing effective for restaurants. The trust factor among customers was cited as critical: if a restaurant has been referred or suggested by friends and family, then potential customers can become existing customers. COVID-19 and restrictions related to this crisis shifted the attention of customers and restaurants towards the use of social media, which meant that social media apps and platforms were a significant avenue for customers and restaurants alike. This chapter has made it evident that not all restaurants are confident about the benefits of social media for restaurants and there is room for improvements to social media that could enhance the usability of social media marketing and influence the buying behaviour of customers.

5. Discussion

5.1 Introduction

This chapter is a continuation of the previous chapter which presented the results of the interviews. In this chapter, a complete thematic table will be presented which will contain the explicit quotes of the respondents who were part of the data collection process from the 20 restaurants. The thematic table will also include the themes and sub-themes identified from the interview results of the 20 respondents (i.e., these themes will represent the most important factors/variables of the study). Each major theme will then be discussed in this chapter in the light of literature review findings for the purpose of addressing the earlier established research objectives and questions. A comparative evaluation will then lead towards concrete understanding of the research study, ultimately providing an opportunity to conclude the study appropriately and meaningfully. A critical perspective will be adopted in this chapter while presenting the discussion of the results.

5.2 Thematic Table with Experts' Quotes

Experts' Quotes	Sub-themes	Major themes
<p>The owner of restaurant F said, "it is an important marketing tool to reach large audience".</p> <p>The owner of restaurant D said, "social media is an important source of advertising because it has increased our presence across customers".</p> <p>The manager of restaurant A said, "social media marketing has provided us with increased brand awareness and sales".</p>	<p>Positive aspects,</p> <p>Impact on consumer buying behaviour,</p> <p>Preferred apps,</p> <p>Use of partner/third-party applications,</p> <p>Friends and family influence,</p>	<p>The use of social media platforms</p>

<p>The manager of restaurant B said, “The only benefit we have achieved from social media marketing is to reach more people”.</p> <p>The owner of restaurant J said, “social media does drive a lot of business depending on people's opinions because if you are good then you will get good reviews and more customers”.</p> <p>Floor manager of restaurant E said, “social media has allowed us to keep in touch and build a personal connection with our customers and reach new customers”.</p> <p>Manager of restaurant M said, “social media marketing helps reach a wider target audience especially the teenagers and younger generation”.</p> <p>Manager of restaurant N said, “we only get business through social media at the moment, and it is doing well for us”.</p> <p>Manager of restaurant L said, “social media is an affordable, simple and effective way to market your brand/product”.</p> <p>Owner of restaurant O said, “if social media is used properly, you can and will do well”.</p> <p>Manager of restaurant B said, “we are delivery only business and it has increased our profile engagement”.</p> <p>Manager of restaurant A said, “it's very important to be visible to potential</p>	<p>Attracting teenagers, Promotions and discounts.</p>	
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<p>customers and social media is giving us that opportunity”.</p> <p>Manager of restaurant Q said, “we have noticed an increase in sales monthly and new customers are always ordering from us having seen our ad on Instagram/Facebook”.</p> <p>Managers of restaurant A and I said, “discounts and promotions, they are mainly offered by Uber Eats, and it is working well”.</p>		
<p>Owner/CEO of restaurant F said, “I have used paid ads once, which helped brand visibility and more customers visited our social media pages”.</p> <p>Owner/CEO of restaurant C said, “social media is used mostly for brand awareness and to promote the business and we have seen good results from unpaid marketing because we wanted to reach more people”.</p> <p>Manager of restaurant N said, “On Facebook ads, we can set specific goals such as 'get more engagement, likes, messages by paying less money' and I have done this for getting more likes”.</p> <p>Manager of restaurant M said, “I have chosen local targeted marketing by paying to Instagram and Facebook, and I saw increased brand awareness and sales as well”.</p>	<p>Brand visibility for home-based brands,</p> <p>Paid views,</p> <p>Food vlogs,</p> <p>Sharing pictures,</p> <p>Impact on brand awareness and visibility,</p> <p>Social media influencers.</p>	<p>Paid and unpaid use of social media</p>

<p>Manager of restaurant G said, “Using paid ads or influencers is like 50/50 effective and now I do not trust paid ads really”.</p> <p>Owner of restaurant O said, “We can reach so many people whilst keeping our costs low and I have been successful in increasing brand awareness by giving discounts as well”.</p> <p>Owners/Managers of restaurants B/G/J/K/M/Q/N/O/R said, “People will try the food recommended by the influencers and they will commit to the brand, and it has been experienced that influencers do help drive online business”.</p> <p>Owners/Managers of restaurants A/B/C/F/I/L/M said, “Paid ads are used to get more exposure and they do not necessarily give extra customers, but brand awareness definitely increases”.</p> <p>Owners/Managers of restaurants B/D/F/G/I/O/R/S/T said, “people trust those influencers which they follow, and it increases sales before even increasing followers”.</p>		
<p>Owners/Managers of restaurants B/G/J/K/M/N/O/P/Q said, “when friends and family members post food vlogs and share pictures of the food, then people in</p>	<p>Picture sharing, Referrals, Word of mouth,</p>	<p>Friends and family influence</p>

<p>their social circle specifically ask for that food and they do try our restaurant food”.</p> <p>Managers of restaurants A/B/G/H/L/M/N said, “referrals of friends and family are the most effective because of the trust level that they share with each other, and it improves our sales”.</p>	<p>Facebook and Instagram posts</p>	
<p>Owners of restaurants D/K/Q said, “Due to pandemic, the business is impacted negatively because of lockdown, schools closed, and events cancelled, but with help of social media apps we managed to work online and mostly did food delivery”.</p> <p>Owner of restaurant C said, “we were thinking about opening food business for a long time, this pandemic gave us a lot of free time and we could focus to start our food business online from home. And social media marketing helped us with this”.</p> <p>Owner/managers of D/E/I also said that they had free time because of the pandemic, so they had just recently started their food business during the pandemic.</p>	<p>Challenges, New opportunities, New food delivery restaurant because of pandemic.</p>	<p>Impact of pandemic/COVID-19</p>
<p>Managers of restaurants H/I/A/B/Q/T said, “Do not post fake things about your brand because when customers find out they give negative comments and feedback”.</p> <p>Manager of restaurant B said, “If Instagram can add that rating system on their app, then</p>	<p>Originality, Rating system of Google, New features</p>	<p>Suggestions for improvements</p>

<p>it will be helpful for me to do the comparisons”.</p> <p>Manager of restaurant A said, “More live videos options and more details can be added on Instagram”.</p>		
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From the table presenting the themes, it can be seen that social media marketing plays a critical role in the growth of SMEs, which can be divided into three categories: restaurants operating online, restaurants opened during COVID-19 pandemic and restaurants that were operating before COVID-19. There are four major themes: the use of social media, ROI, challenges related to pandemic and recommendations. The themes are analysed as per below.

5.3 The Use of Social Media Platforms and Consumers

The first central theme discussed is social media. The sub-themes are positive aspects of social media: consumers’ buying behaviour, preferred apps for advertisements and partner apps. After observing the responses given by the participants, it can be seen that social media was used extensively by restaurants operating online, restaurants opened during COVID-19 and by restaurants that were operating before COVID-19. The sub-themes for this section are slightly different for all three categories yet explain how social media is being used in these SMEs. First, the themes will be discussed in the context of the restaurants operating online. The sub-themes in this section are positive aspects, impact on consumer buying behaviour, preferred apps and partner apps. The responses of the restaurant owners indicate that they have used social media marketing once or twice, but they are not frequent users. However, it can still be shown that social media can help businesses to increase their growth rate.

Engaging customers has been identified as a key challenge for SMEs in the literature and social media marketing is seen as an effective communication tool because it improves the engagement level of customers with the respective SME brand (Felix et al., 2017; Leek et al.,

2016). This aspect has been observed in the results of this study as restaurants experienced improved customer engagement in response to their social media marketing strategies and activities. This also shows that restaurants can make use of this engagement level to provide better customer service and achieve lead generation. Digitalization has increased the importance of online forms of marketing, including social media marketing, and this is especially significant for entrepreneurial firms because it gives them a fair chance of initiating and progressing in the market (Drummond et al., 2020).

Digital engagement strategies and tactics are of direct practical benefit as found in this study; they have given a lifeline to new businesses in the restaurant sector to make their place in the market. Restaurant **K** stated that social media marketing has some positive aspects, such as it is an "Important marketing tool to reach a large audience". Another participant mentioned that "Social media as an important source of advertising". The restaurant **E**, another online restaurant, noted that it helps in "Increased brand awareness and sales". From these responses, it can be seen that social media marketing plays a critical role in business growth.

On the other hand, a few participants, including restaurants **A/B/D/E/H/L/M/P**, also mentioned some positive effects of social media on consumer buying behaviour and improved reach. People during early 2010 decade **spent** relatively more time using social media than on traditional media channels such as television for their entertainment. More than 50% of the global population spends some time on Facebook as compared to 39% watching television on a regular basis (Cooper, 2018). Moreover, 40% of the internet users today have stated that their favourite brand has presence on social media channels (Global Index, 2018). However, the privacy concerns of users for social media restrict its use to a notable extent (Jung, 2017). Another key challenge is that people have concerns about their social media profiles being used for commercial purposes (Allcott and Gentzkow, 2017). These challenges highlight the areas that a new business or marketer must consider. The online restaurants **C/F/Q** noted that in addition to social media, they work with partner apps, mostly Uber Eats and Deliveroo. One of the participants said they use "Discounts and promotions, Uber Eats mainly offer them". This finding addresses a research objective by indicating that social media is a useful marketing tool that small and medium-sized restaurants can use, and, in fact, they can extend their reach to customers with the help of social media marketing.

This finding reflects that social media marketing is helpful, but the restaurant owners also use other methods to reach consumers. However, social media marketing positively impacts consumer engagement and buying behaviour for online businesses. One important aspect that is identified in this significant theme is the buying behaviour of individuals. From the themes, it can be seen that social media has a slight impact on followers' and customers' buying behaviour. Social media can impact buying behaviour because the participants have mentioned that "It's critical to be visible to potential customers". Another participant, restaurant **M**, stated that "I have seen many new customers buying once family and friends have helped to put out the word".

This finding addresses a research objective by showing that the multidimensional nature of social media is a key feature that connects friends and family and ultimately benefits restaurants in terms of increased customers and brand visibility. This finding also addresses another objective by clearly indicating that a key benefit attached to social media marketing is the friends and family factor, which improves brand awareness and the customer base.

This means that social media can help in improving the buying behaviour of individuals. However, online restaurant owners believe it is more due to WOM. On the other hand, the owners who started to operate restaurants during COVID-19 are also available on the tables. The themes for the restaurants that began to operate during the COVID-19 pandemic are positive aspects, consumer buying behaviour, preferred apps and partner apps. Participants viewed social media as an "Important marketing tool", which helps "Reach audience and customers". A participant stated that "Social media builds a connection with your customers". As per this statement, it can be presented that the outcomes for social media marketing are similar to some extent (i.e., benefits in the generation of revenue and build a broad population). Moreover, owners who started to operate restaurants during COVID-19 also stated that social media marketing increases the chances that a customer will buy the product when they see it, for example, "It helps to engage with the public and customers". Therefore, it can be extracted from this finding that customer engagement is a significant benefit that small and medium-sized restaurants can obtain by using social media platforms for marketing purposes. In addition, the capability of social media apps to connect restaurants with their customers in an interactive manner has been found helpful to influence customers' buying behaviour. This connecting nature addresses a research objective to identify features that can influence the buying behaviour of customers.

Furthermore, the owners who started to operate restaurants during the COVID-19 pandemic also stated that they used partner apps along with social media apps, such as Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp, and TikTok to reach a wide range of the population. However, social media is the second favourite method for restaurant owners, and they consider WOM to be a helpful method. For instance, one restaurant owner mentioned that "WOM is still one of the best marketing strategies".

According to the study conducted by Belanche et al. (2019), Instagram Stories not only enhance consumers' attitude towards advertisements but also increase perceived intrusiveness compared to Facebook Wall. Millennials are more disturbed by Facebook Wall advertisements than non-Millennial users. This literature finding has been validated and confirmed from the results gathered in this study; hence, it addresses a research objective by highlighting that social media apps benefit restaurants by attracting Millennial customers, which is a unique advantage.

A triple interaction effect reveals that non-Millennial men are more loyal towards Facebook Wall advertisements, whereas Millennials of both genders and non-Millennial women are more loyal to advertisements on Instagram Stories. This fact has been reflected in the results of this study because Instagram was found to be the most popular, primarily because the managers and owners of the targeted small and medium-sized restaurants are Millennial generation men.

This means that they still rely on how the people present their restaurant to others. This is a unique finding for this theme from the online restaurant owners. The restaurant owners who operated during the COVID-19 pandemic, such as restaurants **B/D/E/F/Q/R/S** also stated that social media impacted consumers' buying behaviour. A participant stated that "If social media is used properly, you can and will do well". This means that social media will help to improve the buying behaviour that will support the business. Another participant stated that "It helps to engage with the public and customers". This also indicated that social media marketing could impact buying behaviour by engaging the customer.

The third and last form of a restaurant owner is those who initiated their business before COVID-19. The themes were the same as those for the owners who started their business during the COVID-19 pandemic (i.e., positive aspects, negative aspects, consumer buying behaviour, preferred apps and partner apps). The sub-themes for the group are the same as the sub-themes for the group earlier, which indicates that social media is used by established restaurants as well. One of the respondents, restaurant **J**, mentioned that "Important marketing tool to reach a large audience" for the positive aspects of social media. This means that the

restaurant owners are mindful of how they can reach a large audience. Another respondent mentioned that it increased "brand awareness" and "sales", which means that they have been using it effectively. One noticeable comment given by restaurant **F** is that "Social media does drive a lot of business depending on people's opinions", which indicates that there is potential in using social media for the growth of the business. This finding addresses the research objective by showing that business growth can be a key benefit facilitated by social media marketing for small and medium-sized restaurants.

This aspect of people's opinions has been covered extensively within the paradigms of social media influencers and friends and family referrals. In the view of Arnold (2018), Millennials are generally more influenced by influencer advertising as compared to advertisements placed by businesses independently. This is due to two reasons: people's appetite to be influenced by internet-based personalities that they like and a higher inclination to watch advertisements, which are supported to internet content creators (Arnold, 2018).

Trust in the opinion of social media influencers or friends and family was a prominent factor for the small and medium-sized restaurants operating in London when attracting and influencing the buying behaviour of customers. Stealth marketing refers to a type of internet marketing in which an influencer promotes a product without letting viewers know that it is a marketing strategy. This is perceived to be more effective in general because people assume that the influencer is promoting a product because of a natural response to the product rather than it being a paid promotion.

Some participants focused on personal connections. One participant stated that "Social media helps keep in touch and build a personal connection with your customers and reach new customers". All these themes suggest that social media marketing is a beneficial tool for businesses, allowing them to generate revenue, whether high or low. Considering all these elements in the first theme, it can be said that the themes obtained by the three kinds of restaurant owners, it can be mentioned that social media is proved to be beneficial for all types of restaurants. However, the restaurants operating online have been the least affected by the use of social media because the owners have used social media marketing once or twice only. They are not sure if they get customers from social media marketing or from WOM.

The results indicated that almost all the restaurants are interested in utilizing the influencer marketing method; however, it is also evident from the results that not every restaurant is happy with the outcome of using influencer marketing. Influencer marketing has been increasing

significantly over the years as companies believe that there is 11 times more of a ROI with influencer marketing than with traditional forms of marketing (Han and Chen, 2021). It has been stated by Kusumasondjaja and Tjiptono (2019) that if influencer marketing is done in the right direction, it can be a huge success. The tool was used by the fashion house Gucci in a bid to support its new product line (i.e., Gucci Bloom – the fragrance line). The company used 23 artists, who were famous on Instagram, to create content highlighting the importance of the fragrance line to their target customers. The campaign was a huge success in terms of response rate and increase in number of followers (Dost et al., 2019). This is a classic case in the use of social media apps and features, and it can be taken as a lesson by small and medium-sized restaurants of London.

The increasing global popularity and prevalence of influencer marketing across brands validates that its practice can be useful for restaurants in London; however, at the same time, it has been observed that its use needs to be strategic and well directed. As mentioned in these examples, the use of influencer marketing can go wrong if due attention and strategic consideration are not given. A similar kind of message was also communicated by a few respondents from restaurants during the qualitative interviews, including restaurants **G/Q/T**. Therefore, it can be stated that there is a certain level of risk attached to the adoption and execution of influencer marketing. This aspect also indicates a gap that needs to be filled in the recommendations section.

A recent study by Belanche et al. (2020) found that influencer marketing is an effective marketing method. The findings of the research highlighted that the influencer must have a profile on Instagram that aligns with the nature of the product or service. The customer response rate and reactions are based on the influencer's type of following and whether they like the product alongside the influencer.

The viral marketing concept presented in the literature review section refers to the act of propagating marketing messages through the help of, and with cooperation from, individual consumers. It is believed to offer many benefits, including better targeting, faster diffusion, enhanced message credibility and lower cost (Voorveld et al., 2018). The essence of this concept can be seen as integrated in the marketing through social media apps and influencers. There are essentially two different types of viral marketing presented in the literature: passive and active. It can be observed that both these types of viral marketing are implemented by restaurants using social media apps and platforms to some extent. For example, passive viral

marketing is, in its essence, broadcasting your brand through some type of media without it being the focus of the content. This can be equated to something like adding a watermark to a viral video. This method can be applied to the Facebook pages of restaurants; it can also be used as a recommendation in this study because various other brands across the UK and other countries are using this method already.

On the other hand, the working nature of active viral marketing is different. It is important to call to action and participation the target customers before a campaign can be termed as active. A good example is social media contests, which are run by brands very frequently these days. These contests boost comments and shares of a particular social media post and eventually lead to a better spread and response rate of the marketing movement. The provision of references to family and friends as part of these contests is also categorized as viral marketing.

Therefore, it can be determined here that social media influencers and brands should be able to carefully and proactively manage actions undertaken as part of influencer marketing. Influencers' audiences and their involvement should be controlled by the brands with featured products so that they are seen to promote them in a natural way. On the other hand, it is equally important that social media influencers should endorse products/services that fit their own style and resonate with their lifestyle and personality as this will increase the interaction on their accounts.

This aspect of using social media influencers to attain more brand visibility and attract customers addresses a few research objectives and questions. For example, two key research questions were "What kind of benefits do consumers look to draw from social media apps?" and "What benefits and uses can social media marketing offer to small and medium-sized restaurants in London?". It can be stated that consumers look for recommendations about quality food from their favourite and trusted people, which includes social media influencers and friends and family. This can be referred to as an extended benefit on which consumers draw, and it ultimately helps restaurants to influence the buying behaviour of customers.

Two research objectives established earlier were: "To evaluate the effectiveness and benefits of social media apps as a marketing tool" and "To analyse and discuss the features of social media apps that affect consumer buying behaviour". Both these research objectives have been addressed under this influencer marketing factor (i.e., it is clearly observed that using social

media influencers to share the food products of a restaurant influences consumer buying behaviour and this feature is a prevailing significant benefit of social media platforms).

5.4 Brand Visibility and Awareness

The factor of brand visibility was cited extensively during the qualitative data collection process as almost all the respondents were aware of this concept and had experienced change in their restaurants' brand visibility while doing social media marketing. One aspect that was distinctly understood was that not all social media platforms have gained an equal level of attention and preference from the restaurants for marketing purposes.

Previous literature focusing on Facebook has led to the finding that advertisements on this platform lead to a notable improvement in brand image and equity (Dehghani and Tumer, 2015). However, it raised some critical concerns at the same time (Lin and Kim, 2016).

In turn, recent research shows that newer social media platforms, such as Snapchat or Instagram, are powerful tools for increasing brand reputation and for reaching younger audiences (Sashittal et al., 2016; Barry et al., 2016). However, the scant research comparing advertising across social media platforms does not consider the distinctive features of the newer social media formats (Pikas and Sorrentino, 2014), it focuses exclusively on enhancing consumer engagement on social media (Ashley and Tuten, 2015) and does not compare specific measures of advertising effectiveness across platforms.

Therefore, the finding of this study about the preference being given to certain social media platforms/apps not only addresses the research gap about which contemporary social media app is more extensively used by restaurants for marketing purposes, but it also addresses two research objectives: "To evaluate the effectiveness and benefits of social media apps as a marketing tool" and "To devise a set of recommendations to improve the adoption and implementation of social media apps in small and medium-sized restaurants in London". Instagram was found to be most frequently used app. Therefore, improved brand visibility is a benefit of using social media apps and for the purpose of recommendations, it can be stated that restaurants should focus on using Instagram more strategically as this app is the most prevalent used app among customers.

The next major theme that has been identified from the responses given by participants is the impact of social media marketing on brands. The sub-themes that have been identified from this major theme are 'brand visibility for home-based brands', 'brand image', 'paid views' and 'influencer's role'.

Considering the restaurants that operate online, the participants mentioned that brand visibility is increased due to social media promotions and marketing. They were able to improve how their customers perceived the brand. One participant mentioned, "I've used paid advertisements once, which helped brand visibility". This means that online businesses benefit if they use social media. Another participant stated that "Social media is used mostly for brand awareness and promote the business"; this also showed that potential consumers get more familiar with the brand if the restaurant uses social media marketing. On the other hand, some participants stated that "On Facebook advertisements you can set specific goals such as 'get more engagement, likes, messages etc.'". The participant explained that social media marketing is a beneficial tool, which allows the brand to engage potential customers. This reflected that social media marketing could prove to be a critical tool for online businesses, as they are not visible to people otherwise.

This aspect also addressed the research objectives and questions as it is evident that customer engagement is a prominent benefit that restaurants can achieve by using social media apps and it also reflects why social media apps are important for small and medium-sized restaurants. Brand visibility, customer engagement and brand awareness are some identified benefits which make it important for restaurants to use social media apps as marketing tools.

Another critical element that needs to be discussed in this section is the role of influencers in the brand's growth. As it also links with paid views, the role of influencers can be critical to reaching a broad population over social media. In this regard, the responses given by the online business owners were mixed. Restaurants **G/L/P** stated that influencers were effective, but others disagreed. For instance, one of the participants mentioned that "Using paid advertisements or influencers is like 50/50 effective". This indicates that they did not get many benefits from social media use and influencers. One of the participants suggested that "People will try the food recommended by the influencers, and they will commit to the brand", which means a campaign might have been beneficial for them to grow the business.

On the other hand, restaurants **B/H** stated that "The influencers are only after fame or financial gain". This shows that the use of influencers is not beneficial. Considering these findings, it

can be said that influencers did not prove to be helpful for brands. In a few cases, the experience was better. However, in general, the use of influencers is expensive, and social media marketing can help in a better way. This aspect addresses the last research objective by giving a valuable suggestion about being careful when using expensive social media influencers as SMEs usually have limited resources and funds to spend on their marketing function.

Considering the same main theme for the restaurants operating during COVID-19, the sub-themes are 'brand visibility for home-based brands', 'brand image', 'organic views for the restaurant owner', 'paid views' and 'influencer's role'. The participants stated that they use "paid to add for once or twice", which means that the effectiveness cannot be judged based on such promotions. On the other hand, another person stated that it has helped them "To increase restaurant recognition and establish a name for ourselves". This means that they can be famous with the help of promotions. Furthermore, a participant stated that "advertisements reach so many new customers and we can expand our market and brand awareness". This means that they could get various customers with the help of social media marketing, and they may use it in the future. Considering the organic views, a participant mentioned that "Come back to « social proof » people trust influencers they follow.". This means if they switch to having influencers, they can generate organic views.

Reaching out to an increasing number of potential customers and expanding the market in terms of geographical reach has been made possible by using paid advertisements and influencer marketing, as indicated by the restaurants during qualitative data collection. For new starters, the use of paid social media advertisements and influencer marketing has been helpful in terms of establishing a brand name in the market. Therefore, this adds to the set of benefits that social media apps offer to small and medium-sized restaurants when used for marketing purposes. This not only addresses the research objectives, but also confirms the arguments made in the wider academic literature regarding the effectiveness of different social media apps as marketing tools.

However, some participants stated that "Using paid advertisements or influencers is partially effective". By this, they meant that influencers could not help their brand greatly; instead, it has a partial impact. Another participant, in this regard, stated that "People will try the food recommended by the influencers and they will commit to the brand". This showed the method to be effective. By this, the participants inferred that influencers may bring more business to SMEs. However, one of the participants mentioned, "Anyone that sponsors them would be

advertised", which means even if the influencers are helpful, they will help competitors if they ask for help. Considering all these factors, it can be seen that getting help from an influencer cannot help the companies to a great extent, as the method is not perceived to be very helpful by the business owners.

This aspect of the discussion addresses the research objective regarding developing recommendations, as the use of social media influencers is not a simple and random process, it demands integration of a certain level of consideration of suitability and a strategic mindset. Therefore, every restaurant will have to review and analyse their internal and external factors while using social media influencers for marketing purposes.

For businesses operating before COVID-19, the sub-themes for this major theme are the same, (i.e., 'brand visibility', 'brand image', 'organic views for the restaurant owner', 'paid views' and 'influencer's role'). It can be seen from the participants' responses that their views of the terms in the sub-themes 'brand visibility', 'brand image' and 'organic views for the restaurant owner' are interlinked. One of the participants stated that "brand visibility is increased by paid ads", which means they have been using paid advertisements to increase their visibility. Another participant stated that "social media is used mostly for brand awareness" and "to increase restaurant recognition and establish a name for ourselves".

This indicates that social media marketing helps improve brand image, visibility and reputation. Therefore, this aspect of the discussion addresses a research objective by conveying that improved brand image and visibility are benefits that social media marketing can facilitate for small and medium-sized restaurants. This is a new finding that can help improve the body of research. Another participant stated that "Social media are one of the most effective ways to raise brand awareness" and "Facebook ads, you can get more engagement, likes, messages etc". This means that paid advertisements have helped the brand to grow and increased brand awareness.

Moreover, considering the sub-themes 'organic views' and 'influencer's role', it can be stated that restaurant owners presented various elements that indicated the efficacy of influencers. One of the participants stated that "If we were to do paid promotions on a larger scale and offer discounts, I do believe that our customers would increase". This statement states that restaurant owners can benefit from discounts and may generate organic click for their social media. Another participant stated that "Influencers do help drive business", which indicates that working with influencers can help a brand to grow faster. However, another participant

mentioned that "The influencers are only after fame or financial gain", which means that influencers are not considerate towards business and the business may lose its position if the influencers behave the same way. Considering all these themes, it can be stated that those businesses may improve their brand image and awareness with the help of social media. Social media can also help them in generating organic views and in getting more people involved in the brand.

However, the role of influencers can be seen as changing. Some participants believed that influencers could help them, whereas others mentioned that they might not prove to be helpful for their brand as influencers are not loyal to their brand. Considering all these facts, it can be stated that using social media marketing is in general beneficial for brand awareness and growth.

5.5 Pandemic Crisis and Challenges for Restaurants

It is stated that the pandemic brought various challenges for restaurants that operate online. The sub-themes that are derived from these restaurants are mainly a lack of financial loss caused by COVID-19.

Restaurant owners stated that "Due to pandemic, the business is impacted negatively". Another participant stated that "COVID-19 helped us give it the time it needed by giving us a break from work". This means that businesses were negatively impacted by COVID-19, as they were experiencing a break from work and a lack of orders. However, they were able to improve the business drastically, as presented by a participant that "Having a lot of free time during lockdown have impacted business negatively".

Restaurants face stiff competition irrespective of the market in which they operate, and the UK restaurant market is known for its high competition level because of its diversity and tourism attraction. Digital and social media marketing is a powerful tool for these restaurants to gain a competitive advantage, which has been proven as a useful tool in a time of crisis as well (Emerald Publishing Group, 2021).

For businesses started during the COVID-19 pandemic, the situation is different, as they stated that they experienced benefits along with loss during the pandemic. Restaurant **G** stated that "Festivals etc. got cancelled due to pandemic", which was a source of financial loss for them as consumers order more food during festivals. Another mentioned that they "Had to change

to takeout and change menu ideas and prices”, which means they decreased their prices as consumers were not coming to eat more frequently. One of the restaurant owners mentioned that “The return on investment was not given in pandemic”, which means they could not get benefit from social media marketing. Some counted on the benefits, such as the pandemic “decreased the cost of hiring”, which might have helped them in managing their balance sheet and financial flow in that difficult time.

These responses can be seen as valid in the light of literature findings and facts stated by credible sources. For example, the recent health crisis caused by COVID-19 quickly turned into a financial downturn due to the restrictions imposed by the UK to control the expansion of this pandemic (IMF, 2020). This unexpected crisis affected the tourism industry in particular, and, as a result, the restaurant industry was one of the most affected industries (Muller, 2020). Restaurants were forced to either close or operate with many limitations; in the UK, only takeaway and delivery services were allowed. According to Kim et al. (2020), by understanding the characteristics of this pandemic, the financial impacts on the restaurant business can be minimized if counterstrategies are applied.

In this regard it can be observed that the shift to social media apps was a ray of hope for restaurants because it kept them in contact with their customers and gave them a chance to carry out their sales in line with the changes to consumer behaviour.

Another reason why marketing and the survival of small and medium-sized restaurants is important is their pivotal role in the overall economic development of the UK, which is due to the industry’s strong integration and links with the tourism industry. Restaurants can play a fundamental role as a distinctive element in the competitiveness of destinations because they link food to tourism. In this way, gastronomy can be used as a tourist orientation factor, and restaurants are valuable cultural elements sharing this role with other segments of the cultural industry (Meneguel et al., 2019). London, as a top tourist attraction for a global audience, experiences a consistent inflow of people from all around the globe, which means that a large number of customers can be engaged on a consistent basis using social media marketing, and restaurants are a tourism-associated industry (Chu et al., 2020). These aspects make it clear why it is important for small and medium-sized restaurants to employ sound marketing strategies as well as why restaurants’ use of social media apps as a marketing tool has become inevitable (i.e., customer base can be increased significantly).

Some people started their food business because of the pandemic; for example, they said that “COVID-19 helped us give it the time it needed”, which means they were able to benefit from COVID-19. One business owner mentioned that “Having a lot of free time during lockdown has allowed me to start up my own business”. Some restaurants opened because of the pandemic; some people with free time because of lockdown started their food delivery business from home. The owner of restaurant **C** said, “we were thinking about opening food business for long time, this pandemic gave us a lot of free time and we could focus to start our food business online from home”.

Social media marketing helped small and medium-sized restaurants cope with the COVID-19 situation. Owner/managers of **D/E/I** said that they had free time because of the pandemic so they started their food business during the pandemic. They were able to re-establish their business and gain momentum to work on their business. On the other hand, some business owners were not able to reach many followers due to COVID-19 as customer engagement was low. They stated that “reaching 20,000 you get about 5-10 followers”. This means that COVID-19 can be seen as a negative force for most of the businesses, as they were unable to gain a return on their investment.

The challenges posed by COVID-19 for restaurants have been realistic and the facts gathered about this aspect reaffirms this finding exhibited by the respondents of restaurants. For example, the economic downturn resulting from coronavirus restrictions was concentrated among certain types of business. Overall, the UK economy, measured by gross domestic product (GDP), shrank by a record 19.8% in the second quarter (April to June) of 2020, following the start of the first lockdown on 23 March 2020. By September 2020, GDP was still down 8.2% compared with February (ONS, 2020). Services such as hospitality, including pubs, restaurants recorded almost no output in April 2020 and May 2020, but industries such as information and communication, where staff could largely work from home, saw little change compared with February.

At the same time, this challenge played a role in the prevalence and increased adoption of social media apps and platforms for marketing purposes by the restaurants because these apps enabled restaurants to reach out and engage with customers. The enforced closure of shops selling non-essential items during the first wave of the pandemic led to a boost for online retailers. This also allowed customers to develop a habit of exploring restaurant options online with the help

of different social media apps, which ultimately helped small and medium-sized restaurants to survive the COVID-19 challenge.

Social media has changed the landscape of communication and this one factor of unique way of “communication” has made the use of social media apps and platforms effective when used for marketing. Social media marketing has enabled people all over the world to interact and share product-related information and brand-related information with each other (Casalo et al., 2018). In a way, this new way of communication has given more opportunities to small and medium-sized restaurants to attract customers, which were not available before. This aspect also addresses the third research objective established earlier in this study (i.e., interactive way of communication is a key feature of social media apps which helps small and medium-sized restaurants to influence the buying behaviour of customers). Since Instagram has been found to be the most frequently used and most effective social media app for influencing consumer behaviour, it means that the communication factor and method of Instagram is more effective as compared to other social media apps.

5.6 Suggestions for Improvements

The last major theme is the suggestions for improvements given by the restaurant owners. The restaurants operating online presented with two sub-themes, which were to have food-oriented marketing apps and target audience more effectively. They also stated that the use of data analytics can be helpful. For instance, one of the owners stated, “Do not post fake things about your brand” and another mentioned that “We can encourage more sales if we apply a discount”. This means that fake news should not be posted about the business, and promotions can prove to be helpful. Restaurant **D** suggested that “Algorithms on Instagram should be changed”. This proves that restaurant owners can make the use of analytics on social media and get the maximum potential from using it. Considering these results, the study suggests that most restaurant managers need to measure their social media strategy to ensure that it is well executed and designed. This finding addresses the last research objective by reflecting that to effectively use social media apps, small and medium-sized restaurants need to devise formal strategies and measure the performance of their social media marketing because every restaurant operates with unique dynamics.

It is difficult to predict how the world will be once the pandemic is over. The pandemic has affected different countries in various parts of the world quite differently. As a result, the measures proposed by countries are also notably different from each other. In most parts of Europe and other areas around the world, catering spaces and restaurants have started opening again with restrictions on capacity and the establishment of certain rules, including hygiene measures (Aristovnik et al., 2020). Results of past research studies have depicted that restaurants are involved in pursuing passive strategies to cater to different types of crises that can come their way, including those posed by regulatory agencies (Miao et al., 2018).

For the restaurants that started during the COVID-19 pandemic, the suggestions given by the owners is that restaurants need to incorporate more data analytics and target an audience in their marketing strategy. One of the owners stated that “100% food oriented » social medias maybe with relevant statistics”, which can be accurate in this case, because it will allow them to make use of data analytics more successfully. Another owner stated that “More live videos and more details to be added to it”. This will allow restaurants to get in touch with the targeted audience, and customers will like their content or desire to buy something. This finding addresses the last research objective, which is about recommending appropriate steps or strategies for small and medium-sized restaurants for adequate use of social media apps for marketing, especially given the context of the COVID-19 crisis (i.e., live videos are identified as a suggested step that restaurants can use).

Moreover, the restaurant owners who were operating restaurants before COVID-19 presented findings similar to the other two forms of restaurants; they mentioned that a separate app is required to understand trends in the restaurant sector. Also, one manager said, “social media apps should introduce new feature of customer feedback and reviews like Google reviews so it’s easier for customers to choose their restaurant on social media apps”. To conclude, it is stated that restaurant owners are mindful about how they can improve their social media marketing and its impact on the industry and how they can make a difference by improving the ROI and bring in more customers.

Good management in the restaurant business is based not only on long-researched operational ratios but also on market and competition analysis techniques, such as benchmarking (Parsa et al., 2019; Camillo et al., 2018). Therefore, in the light of this aspect, a key argument that emerges here is that small and medium-sized restaurants should consider benchmarking

practice when it comes to using social media apps and platforms for marketing purposes. The kinds of suggestions made by the restaurant respondents for improving the use of social media apps indicates that they must develop a benchmark to cover all these areas or look for benchmark practices that lead the industry by successfully integrating the suggested factors. Although there have been other global crises, such as the severe acute respiratory syndrome health crisis in 2003 and the subprime economy in 2008, which had major impacts on the restaurant industry, the present crisis has different outlines, as there was a mandatory lockdown which had never happened before (Muller, 2020). Therefore, the complexities and uncertainties attached to COVID-19 have made small and medium-sized restaurants realize the importance of executing social media marketing and improving the features of social media apps. In times of crisis or post-crisis, competitiveness among market players increases as demand decreases (Jung and Jang, 2019). This factor is visible in the answers of the restaurant respondents, as only some restaurants experienced success or considerable survival during the COVID-19 period because demand decreased; now, more restaurants are turning towards social media marketing.

5.7 Discussion on Themes and Sub-themes

The use of social media marketing by restaurant owners has been highlighted in the study; also, the study found interest in using social media marketing among those who have not started using social media marketing. A major reason behind the decisions of restaurants to start engaging in social media marketing is the occurrence of COVID-19 crisis and the related restrictions imposed by the government from time to time.

Three sub-themes ('impact on consumer buying behaviour', 'preferred apps' and 'attracting teenagers') were identified in this study as part of the major theme 'use of social media apps/platforms'. In relation to this, an overwhelming majority of restaurants' respondents indicated that Instagram was their preferred app for marketing purposes. This shows that the most prevalent app used by small and medium-sized restaurants to attract teenagers and to influence consumer buying behaviour is Instagram. Contemporary literature validates the research findings; there are some significant reasons behind this prevailing preference and the extensive use of Instagram for marketing purposes. For example, Instagram has recently experienced extraordinary growth, both in terms of its popularity as a social network and as a marketing channel where companies spread their commercial messages (Kim et al., 2017;

Serra-Cantalops et al., 2018; Rietveld et al., 2020). In this sense, brands use Instagram not only as a direct channel or advertising medium (Belanche et al., 2019), but also as a platform to better reach their target audiences through Instagram influencers. Consequently, Instagram has become the preferred social network channel for brands to run influencer-based marketing campaigns (Relatabe, 2019; Sanz-Blas et al., 2019).

The findings of this study support the evidence that the importance of social media marketing increases with time. However, the restaurants' managers and owners are still not sure regarding the use of influencers to improve customer engagement. This study suggests that social media measurement and the goals of restaurant owners are uncertain as the restaurateurs do not know whether the likes for their restaurants increased because of WOM or due to social media marketing. The findings of this study put the usefulness of social media marketing as a strategic tool for marketing under question. The major findings of the study highlight that most restaurant managers have not considered a well-defined social media marketing strategy.

Agius conducted a study in 2018 to evaluate the importance of social media marketing and found interesting results. Agius (2018) found that four out of five marketing goals that were possible with social media were selected by six out of the 20 respondents of the study. When asked about their target audience for social media marketing, 10 out of the 20 respondents chose existing customers and 10 respondents selected new customers. The findings presented by Agius (2018) have been validated by the findings of this study, which means that social media is a useful marketing tool for influencing the buying behaviour of consumers, which includes existing and new customers (some restaurant managers/owners mentioned that they have been successfully attracting new customers via marketing on social media platforms and apps).

A key finding of this study that is aligned with literature review findings is the benefit of being resourceful that SMEs can extract by engaging in social media marketing (i.e., it widens the pool of resources in a cost-effective manner and extends their reliance on their initial local network) (Iankova et al., 2018; Salo, 2017). Restaurants have practically experienced this benefit during the COVID-19 crisis as exhibited in the results, which means that social media marketing is a valuable resource for SMEs in the midst of intense competition and challenges posed by the business environment.

The sample taken in this study was small and selected through the convenience sampling technique, due to which the results cannot be generalized to a large extent and the validation will be restricted to a small extent only. It can be seen that most restaurant managers using social media marketing have not defined their strategies well and one-half of them have only benefitted by reassessing their target market and refining their social media goals. It was highlighted by the respondents that the restaurants were not harmed by the use of social media. This study suggests that an undefined social media strategy would not be beneficial, and the ROI cannot be measured accurately. The point to be understood here is that mere use of social media for marketing is not enough (i.e., restaurants have to come up with the right strategy and execution plan by considering external environmental factors especially). For example, restaurant managers and owners need to understand that they can utilize the presence and experience of their existing customers to attract new customers.

As mentioned in the literature, well-defined social media marketing with prioritized, achievable and workable goals and aims can have a positive influence on business operations. Social media managers cannot make logical decisions in the absence of a clear goal or strategy; to achieve this, there has to be awareness and understanding at the top level of the restaurant as an organization. Therefore, a specific goal and target audience for social media strategy must be set by the social media managers (Jauhari, 2017), which can be owners themselves in the case of this study. The online research and activities must be aligned with the goals of the restaurant's social media marketing and their desired intended outcomes.

For example, the goal can be to take maximum benefit from friends and family referrals while using Instagram and other social media apps. Despite the importance of influencer marketing on Instagram, studies in this research area are scarce (Casaló et al., 2018). Previous studies have focused on the metrics used to measure the impact of influencers' actions (Arora et al., 2019), the different uses made of the tools provided by the social networks (Erz et al., 2018), brand–influencer relationships in influencer marketing campaigns (Boerman, 2020; Jiménez-Castillo and Sánchez-Fernández, 2019) and the type of content uploaded by influencers (Casaló et al., 2018). However, giving the importance of this phenomenon, more research is needed to understand the efficacy of influencer marketing campaigns in terms of their impact on customers' online behaviours.

The managers and owners need to align their social media marketing activities with their strategic objectives. For example, a well-defined social media strategy for increasing the consumer's bond with the brand and focused on the target audience of loyal consumers would differ from one targeted to manage potential complaints and from one targeted at attracting new consumers (Kourdi, 2018).

A different approach is required by social media marketing as compared to traditional marketing as a direct connection with consumers is developed through social media. For example, a key finding that can be drawn from this study's results is that engaging customers in different activities can help the restaurants improve their brand visibility and attract new customers. So, listening to consumers is important along with posting and responding. Most restaurants utilize social media for different reasons. For example, food trucks need social media to share their menu and location. The low cost of social media marketing meets the restaurant industry's demands (Kourdi, 2018; some restaurants in this study mentioned that affordability is the fundamental reason they opted for social media as a marketing tool. Managers can get a lot of information through the internet that can help them learn about people's perceptions regarding their restaurant and they can use these opinions to improve their restaurant's performance and to manage complaints.

A virtual relationship with current consumers or with newcomers can be developed with a well-designed social media site. Moreover, a restaurant can manage its social media site to improve its online reputation. Social media has the capability to impact all levels of Lavidge and Steiner's traditional hierarchy of effects model, such as from awareness until purchase stage (Ting et al., 2018).

The ROI of social media still faces some questions despite that most of the social media users, holders, and stakeholders are supported by unreliable evidence. However, when the confirmation of return has some issues, the presentation of the social media case has also faced some difficulties. The dealers have to look for some well-grounded means to guard the activity of social networking, but they are difficult to find and made. Therefore, instead of calculating the ROI in social media, the investment in social media marketing can be thought of as providing a vital instrument, the importance and use of which is continually growing; however, there is scant academic research on this topic. ROI calculation has also included the calculation of earnings, which is the result of the activities of social media (Kourdi, 2018).

Usually, a social media account is free, therefore the measurement of costs is quite easy. However, labour is the major cost that contributes to the purchase of social media software by a firm. Although, the most challenging interest for measurement is the potential revenue. To increase revenues, a firm should take an individual for a sale, by pleasing an online potential customer.

The measurement of this can be possible, however, a customer who shares his/her review on their experience of the restaurant, is really tough to be measured and calculated. A feature like that made a major challenge in defining the return of measurement correctly. Some arguments explain that the strength of a network is the business's return, and this is due to time. Because time has been invested in a process of networking it is the most demanding investment that the companies want to have and make strong connections (Jauhari, 2017). According to the review of the literature, the measurement of social media is a hard and challenging job. According to an author, there are many non-physical advantages of social media marketing, for example building relationships and branding. Therefore, a company should have set the aims and goals before, for the Plans of the success of the social media marketing, entirely not for the features of the sales for a particular campaign of social media.

Most of the traditional ways of tracking the success of marketing campaigns may not be as accurate as ROI. Because of this, the physical and non-physical advantages cannot be analysed side by side. Gunelius (2018) gives a way of measuring the return on objectives due to the above certainties: it is done when the efforts of social media marketing are analysed comprehensively. Previous research has reported that it is not practically possible to quantify social media conversation's ROI. However, this does not mean that these conversations are useless in terms of the process of brand building (Gunelius, 2018, p. 220). The research suggested that setting some clear goals and aims for the analyses of social media performance are a crucial element in its measurement before stepping into social media's topography (Minazii, 2018).

Changing in thoughts about the most accurate social media assessment due to the grounds which are experiencing the development. For example, the grounds for foundations permit business to correlate and disagreement on distinct podiums. These grounds will help to grow the efficacy of certain actions that take place in the market depend on the crucial podiums' measurement (Minazii, 2018). Impact, advocacy, influence, engagement and interactions are the five main foundations of social media. The number of clicks, comments, shares and views

can be used to measure interaction. While on the other side of the picture, engagements included the measurement of the discussion or comments that people do in their online conversation. It is not measuring only that replies which are present for some specific reason (Lovett, 2018).

It is also come to know that all above points are same and confused by the businesses. Influence includes the ability of a person to practice decision-making potential over the actions of other individuals. Minazii interprets this point in many manners, but it is based on an institute a kind of social media. Highly engaged people promote brands, and some companies are brand advocates.

An increase in the number of advocates is linked with their capability to take part in some significant discussions with clients. The performance of a company either good or bad, regarding have their aims and objectives in business is included in impact and explained by Minazii. However, in some cases such as the Instagram advertising campaign, connected to some certain actions can be able to measure single activities only and is unable to give ROI to marketers (Minazii, 2018). Big restaurants still manage to measure the marketing performance to have a few valuable instruments for analysis. However, it is still a challenge to find an accurate instrument for marketing performance analysis. Therefore, restaurants can measure whether they have achieved their goals according to the strategies and plans they have. Companies can have better measurements by having many different approaches to tracking social media together (Gunelius, 2018). Side by side, to make better decisions, performance monitoring, making strategies, separating the information of followers, and to head their profile, many tools are present for companies to do these (Minazii, 2018).

For example, there is an instrument through which information is passed to companies about the actions of blogs, sites and websites called Google Analytics. Almost every social media channel, such as Facebook, YouTube and Instagram, have their means to measure the performance of campaigns. Companies should keep in their thoughts that these mechanisms are not perfect for quantification, but they can be helpful in different ways. Social media marketing is a never-ending learning method, and this is because of changes in the landscape of social media. Due to this, it is vital for restaurants to actively take part in different activities, listening and making social media plans.

Gunelius mentioned that both indirect and direct marketing strategies are included in a successful social media plan. Any kind of marketing that is not aimed at the direct purchase of a product or service is indirect marketing. Gunelius identified four key ways to participate in social media in her books: content sharing, community building, content development and connection building. She named them the "4Cs" and mentioned that all of these can be used for indirect marketing. The focus of indirect marketing is brand building and long-term opportunities, whereas direct marketing is focused on motivating consumers to immediately make a purchase decision. As compared to traditional media, social media provides real-time communication that helps a business to get immediate responses. Sales can be effectively increased with the use of direct promotion or marketing, but their impact is short-term. Therefore, the focus of the restaurant business must be on indirect long-term marketing and not on a short-term sales boost (Gunelius, 2018).

Partnering with social media influencers is the latest trend in the restaurant industry. Evidence highlights that around 90% of marketers find it effective to use influencer marketing (Patel, 2017). An influencer is someone who can influence or change someone's purchasing behaviour (Del Rowe, 2018). Steve Cox (2017) mentioned that travel influencers are experts who move around the globe and show their experiences and adventures to others using videos and images. Generally, people follow those whom they are inspired by and trust. For this reason, some marketing experts use influencers as WOM marketing. People define themselves by the influencers they follow as they think they have perceptions similar to these influencers. The ability to motivate or inspire people is different in every influencer.

Consumers are more interested in the perspectives of third parties rather than the perspective produced by companies. Marketers can gain this outside perspective through influencers (Del Rowe, 2018). Hence, businesses can have great marketing benefits due to this relationship between influencers and their followers. According to LaHayne, brands can reach their target market by collaborating with influencers (Del Rowe, 2018, p. 29).

The size of their network is the classification criteria for influencers, such as a few thousand to millions of followers. Micro-influencers are those who have a small network, whereas mega-influencers have millions of followers. Restaurant marketers can use various approaches to identify the ideal influencer for promotion. They need to identify an influencer whose characteristics best match their brand. On the other hand, a different view is shared by Nicholson; according to Nicholson, restaurants need to first understand who inspires their

followers. After considering the preferences of consumers, marketers can hire influencers that inspire their target market. The key aspect is the extent of the influencer's networks, but engagement with the influencers' posts is another point to consider. This means that having a large following will not ensure the best results, thus influencers with few followers but more engagement can be the suitable ones (Del Rowe, 2018).

Paid and unpaid collaboration are two types of relationships between influencers and businesses. In paid partnerships, influencers receive money along with the company's products or services for creating content. Nicholson suggested that, in contrast, in unpaid partnerships early access to services, products or experiences is offered to the influencer so that they would be encouraged to include product companies in the content they create (Del Rowe, 2018, p. 30). While considering influencer marketing, companies need to have a transparent partnership with the influencers. This highlights that an influencer must reveal their partnership with the product brand in their content. Moreover, companies should allow influencers to present the brand's products in their own way so that followers can be naturally inspired by the influencers. In other cases, the audience will feel like they are watching television advertisements and will reject the strategy.

According to Fiorella and Brown (2013), dyadic relationships positively influence the purchase intention of consumers. A dyad is the smallest kind of social group that involves only two individuals. In such cases, a friend, workmate or a relative who has an interest similar to the consumer, influences the consumer's purchase intention. Ideas and behaviours can also influence purchase intention.

Hence, consumers may buy certain products because of a recommendation by a friend. Such personal communication influences purchase intention a lot, as the relationship between the two people is strong. The social media trends among various other trends that were used in the company were highlighted by the respondents as Snapchat, Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram. According to Gade (2019), consumers' purchase intentions are influenced by personality, such that most of the mentioned trends include a consumer's profile that highlights their personality, which also influences the purchase intentions of other consumers. The customer-centric model is another framework that can be applied to analyse this observation.

5.8 Chapter Summary

This chapter has presented a detailed and critical account of the results gathered as a result of the data collection process. Key themes and sub-themes have been identified in this chapter, which summed up the significant and noteworthy dimensions of the research findings. The use of social media platforms was one major theme under which four sub-themes were identified (i.e., 'paid and unpaid use of social media', 'friends and family influence', 'impact of pandemic/COVID-19' and 'suggestions for improvements'). The scope and direction of themes and sub-themes identified has been specific and in line with the research context established by the research aim and objectives. Mostly, the findings and critical evaluation conducted have indicated that literature review outcomes and assertions are valid. This chapter has highlighted that restaurant across London extract benefits from the use of social media marketing in the form of financial and non-financial gains. It has been mentioned in this chapter that brand visibility and awareness are the most frequently gained benefits from the use of social media apps and platforms for marketing purposes. COVID-19 has been found to be a key factor that has pushed restaurants to embrace social media marketing to attract and retain customers. Instagram and Facebook have been cited as the most significant social media apps and platforms which restaurants use to gain marketing benefits and to influence consumers' buying behaviour. Restaurants across London are realizing the importance of social media marketing and they are anticipating new developments and features in terms of mobile apps and social media platforms that they can utilize to communicate with their customers and to promote their businesses.

Considering these results, the study has suggested that most restaurant managers/owners need to measure the results of their social media strategy to ensure that it is well executed and designed. It was identified that not all the small and medium-sized restaurants are ready for adopting and integrating social media in their marketing strategies and activities, which strengthens the theoretical viewpoint that managers and owners of small and medium-sized restaurants need to develop themselves and their restaurants to embrace social media marketing. In this way, the readiness of restaurants can enable them to cope with a crisis situation in a better way. This chapter also indicated and concluded that social media marketing has benefits to offer that have not been explored or experienced yet, because the integration of social media platforms across the marketing function of SMEs has not been significant. The role of social media influencers is a prime example of this aspect, as not all restaurants are convinced about the effectiveness of using them.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Conclusion

It can be concluded that the research objectives established for this study have been addressed after completing the research process. It has been concluded that social media apps and platforms are a premier marketing tool and source for influencing consumer buying behaviour; this is because in today's digital age a significant number of customers have started using social media apps for shopping and spending money on their different needs or requirements. It has been concluded after evaluating the theoretical concepts of social media marketing that the application and adoption of social media apps has become imperative for the marketing of restaurant businesses because it engages and influences customers with the particular business. Customers can be positively influenced through the use of several social media marketing strategies, such as discount offers, paid advertisements, videos and promotional activities, which can reach out to large numbers of customers via social media apps. The business aspect of small and medium-sized restaurants can be served well by using social media apps as a marketing tool because it not only generates brand awareness but also increases sales of the business. Brand image and visibility are the most frequently cited benefits of social media marketing which validates the literature review findings.

A key objective of this study was the evaluation of benefits embedded and offered by social media apps which can help small and medium-sized restaurants influence consumer buying behaviour. The findings of this study while addressing this particular research objective indicated that social media apps offer a variety of benefits and are effective as a marketing tool. Product or service usage tips, service experiences, product reviews and suggestions about product quality from customers are some examples of such benefits that help small and medium-sized restaurants market their products effectively. Another important concluding remark of this study is that the occurrence of the COVID-19 crisis raised the importance of social media apps for marketing purposes. This aspect adds to and addresses the research objective by showing that social media apps are useful and effective even during a time of crisis, which is a valuable addition to the reliability of social media apps as marketing tools. Another key benefit of social media apps cited in the findings is that when used from a marketing perspective, these apps can influence the buying behaviour of customers.

Friends and family referrals along with endorsements or reviews from social media influencers were found to be key factors that help influence consumer buying behaviour towards small and medium-sized restaurants.

This study also concluded that managers and owners of small and medium-sized restaurants will have to improve their understanding of social media apps to be able to execute effective marketing strategies. The findings of this study showed that social media apps provide freedom to customers when it comes to expressing their views about the product or service they use, which small and medium-sized restaurants can use in their favour. This feature of social media apps which engages customers with a restaurant's offerings can be used by the restaurants to improve their food quality and services as per the demands of the customers. Therefore, social media apps can be used as a key strategic resource to not only attract but also retain customers. Another key benefit of social media apps observed in the study's findings is that it is cost effective and puts less financial pressure on the restaurant, which in itself is a point of advocacy for embracing social media apps for marketing purposes.

The behaviour of customers is influenced if their family/friends or celebrities share their posts about the food they are having, this finding confirmed the proposition of social impact theory which mentions the influence of WOM. In the light of this conclusion, it can be stated that social media apps are the digital version of WOM and are an effective marketing tool when used positively and strategically. A potential recommendation in line with the study findings can be the strategic adoption of social media apps for marketing purposes, because not all of the respondents of the restaurants were inclined towards using it extensively and they perceived limited benefits of doing so.

6.2 Recommendations

By considering the direction exhibited by the research findings and by considering the findings presented in the literature review, a set of recommendations has been developed which will be presented in this section:

1. It is strongly suggested to adopt and regularly use social media apps for marketing purposes because the COVID-19 pandemic has blindsided many businesses and with very good reason. Amidst the chaos and uncertainty, only the nimble and flexible have the greatest hope for survival. There are three approaches that could help businesses

respond or pivot in the current COVID-19 climate and social media marketing plays a key role in the successful implementation of all three (Palgrave McMillan, 2021).

2. Launching a new service to respond to the changing environment (e.g., online buying/ordering, online delivery and using a strategic mindset to engage customers on online platforms) is also suggested for backing up the regular use of social media apps. This recommendation is meaningful because with most of the population staying at home during the COVID-19 crisis it is important, wherever possible, for businesses to adjust their offerings to help their customers engage with their brand and products from home. This means making purchasing online or over the phone a simple and convenient process and home delivery not only readily available and affordable but contact-free.
3. It has been noted during data analysis that some restaurants faced relatively more challenges and they reduced their business activities as a result. Therefore, it is recommended to embrace social media marketing and integrate it even though business activities are not functioning in a normal routine. This means initiating presence on social media apps and using social media to increase engagement and build a strong online brand community while the business is in hibernation. Now is the time to increase social media activities to help and entertain customers while they are stuck at home. Creating helpful content to show customers how they can get by at home until they can use your products again is one of the best ways to strengthen customer relations.
4. It is also suggested to make use of paid and original social media advertisements. Using paid and organic social media posts can be extremely effective in promoting these new offerings to current and prospective customers. Creating a paid advertising campaign on social media platforms, such as Facebook and Instagram, can be highly targeted to reach people within a specific geographical area, from specific age groups and with interests relating directly to your brand. Also, it is suggested to have the Facebook pixel installed in restaurant's website so that advertisements can be retargeted to people who have visited your website. This is the most cost-effective way to advertise on Facebook and Instagram. Paid ads on social media apps will promote the restaurant's page and, according to some managers in interviews, paid advertisements are helpful to increase reach and they help restaurants get new followers, which in turn gets new customers.

5. Given the implications of the COVID-19 crisis on the mindset of the customers and owners of restaurants, it is suggested to pay attention towards crafting adverts that create ease for the customers, because people are already facing unique challenges in their daily routine life. A good way to implement this recommendation is the formulation and communication of a new business vision (i.e., focusing more on how the services and products can assist customers instead of focusing on mere selling only). This will probably generate a positive response from new and existing customers. Depending on the business context, location and theme, small and medium-sized restaurants can generate helpful content, which could be the recipes from a specific café or restaurant presenting their specialization.
6. Other forms of engaging content could be competitions where customers have to share a video of themselves performing a particular task (e.g., the results of a recipe). Customers will be grateful that you provided a fun and useful experience for them while they have been stuck at home. Therefore, making the effort to ramp up social media efforts can result in strengthening existing customer relationships and forging new ones. It has been noted in the research findings that initiating online presence has helped small and medium-sized restaurants to survive and sustain their business; therefore, it is recommended to revamp the brand image of the restaurant with a relaunch plan for when the current COVID-19 restrictions end.
7. It is challenging to know what is around the corner. However, it is recommended to create a relaunch strategy ready for when the restrictions are finished completely. The COVID-19 pandemic has demonstrated that change can occur quickly. Restrictions may end as quickly as they were imposed, once we are safely on the other side. Create a marketing communication strategy with a strong focus on social media and have it ready to go as soon as the UK government gives the green light.
8. It has been observed from the research findings of this study and from a review of the wider academic literature that social media influencers are a new reality of the marketing world and they do influence customers in their own respective ways. Therefore, it is suggested to make use of social media influencers for marketing purposes, but this should be carefully and strategically driven. Some guidelines for

executing this recommendation are presented in the Figure below (Figure 15), which outlines the key points that need to be ensured while using social media influencers.

Figure 15: Key points for using social media influencers

Source: Koay et al. (2021)

Faced with the need to invest limited budgets in social media platforms in the absence of a clear criterion, restaurant owners and managers need guidance to make their investment choices. As an additional element to be considered, each advert itself or the marketing campaign is suggested to have concrete objectives. The advert or the marketing campaign should reach a specific target audience, which can be in terms of gender or age. This will be best achieved by placing the advertisements on the appropriate social media apps, which this research found to be Instagram. Extensive use of Instagram will be cost effective as well. Some recommendations have been formulated by specifically considering the role that marketing managers or managers responsible for marketing activities across small and medium-sized restaurants play, because they are the ones who are, and need to be, the users of social media apps.

9. Skill development in the functioning of social media apps and using them in an advanced manner is recommended because it has been observed in the research findings that not all the respondents are expert in using social media apps. It is suggested to view

social media marketing as an important tool of marketing and then try to provide improved marketing services to achieve the business objectives; in the UK, the most effective marketing tool for SMEs is social media marketing. For this purpose, relevant training and upgrading of expertise is recommended for managers or owners of the small and medium-sized restaurants or whoever is responsible for marketing activities.

10. It is suggested to figure out the most popular social media apps as a key marketing objective of the restaurant because doing so will give the restaurant an advantage of reaching out to the most relevant target market and with maximum reach. With this knowledge, a restaurant can then incur resources and strategies in that particular app with a focused approach. For example, it has been identified in the data analysis that Instagram and Facebook are the two most popular social media apps among restaurant industry customers. Focusing on specific social media apps will save time, cost and energy as well for the restaurant which is imperative given the limited availability of financial and non-financial resources.
11. Small and medium-sized restaurants are thought to be more adaptable and proactive in responding to changes in the business environment (i.e., change your social media strategy according to the situation, like a global pandemic; for example, managers changed their menu and their prices because of the pandemic). Some restaurant owners said that they started their food business because they had free time during the pandemic, so they found enough time to start a food delivery business.
12. It is suggested to keep offering discounts and promo codes to customers on social media platforms to keep them engaged so that the chance of their return remains high. It is also important to keep learning from customer reviews and fix issues or complaints, because many customers describe good or bad experiences in their reviews on public platforms, like social media apps, which can hurt the business. A key recommendation for small and medium-sized restaurants is to improve their social media marketing content and pages and then link them to their website's contact information. These tactics will improve the efficiency of marketing practices and will attract more traffic as well. Starting new and distinct campaigns is also recommended to increase business credibility and to increase the restaurant's awareness regarding products and services

and knowledge about consumers; this will, in turn, enhance customer engagement and increase sales.

13. The integration of delivery apps like Uber Eats, Deliveroo and Just Eat in restaurants' social media pages is especially recommended; data analysis showed that only a few restaurants are doing this. This can be done by sharing the restaurant's delivery app links with restaurant's social media pages. According to some interviewed managers, there are many discounts and promotions offered by delivery apps, such as Uber Eats; so, if customers can directly order on Uber Eats from your social media pages that could be extremely helpful in increasing the sales of the restaurant.

6.3 Contribution to Knowledge

Towards Literature

This study makes some contributions to the literature and body of knowledge. For example, a key contribution to theory is the validation of social impact theory in today's digitally driven market with customers who are digital users.

Theory and empirical evidence discussed in the literature made it clear that social media marketing and the use of social media apps are of critical importance to the sustainability and success of restaurants. In the extant marketing literature, the concepts of brand image and brand loyalty are seen as key elements of social media marketing; this also emerged in this study's data analysis. A key contribution of this study to the body of knowledge is its coherence with, and its validation of, the importance of social media marketing for small and medium-sized restaurants as business entities, as expressed in the literature.

A key contribution of this study is the context of the COVID-19 crisis, which posed serious challenges to businesses around the world; uncertainty was one key challenge in this regard. The use of social media marketing allowed small and medium-sized restaurants to understand changes in consumer behaviour due to the ongoing COVID-19 crisis and this enabled restaurants to survive (Dabas et al., 2021). Therefore, social media marketing can be seen as a crisis management tool, which is a new avenue in the business environment. At the same time, a sub-contribution within this main contribution of shaping the value of social media marketing

is the finding that restaurant managers and owners are keen to adopt social media apps as marketing tools.

This study contributes by highlighting two new factors to be added to the overall marketing framework, where key elements are considered to be brand image, customer engagement, brand visibility and other such factors; the new factors are brand survival and sustainability. From an entrepreneurial perspective, this study contributes a unique point: social media marketing can, and is, drive entrepreneurial thinking and behaviour because it successfully enabled small and medium-sized restaurants to initiate their operations during the COVID-19 crisis, which is a valuable characteristic.

Considering the significance of social media use for marketing and the effectiveness of such tools, it is stated that the need for investigating research gaps is critical. Hence, there is a need to understand the available opportunities in the field of marketing that would improve formats of social media marketing. Certainly, the research facilitates in providing the answers to queries for the improved effectiveness in advertisement and related campaign for marketing.

This study has also contributed towards building consensus that the concept of viral marketing is still applicable in the digital age and the essence of viral marketing can be integrated with social media apps for marketing purposes to improve results, for example, the creativity and relevance of a marketing campaign or advert can be enhanced.

Instagram is not only one of the fastest-growing social media platforms, but it is also a social virtual space where individuals like to spend time (Sheldon and Bryant, 2016); visitors stay 45% longer on Instagram than on Facebook and 40% longer on Instagram than on Twitter (Alter, 2018). The incredible growth of Instagram, and particularly the recent launching of Instagram Stories, demands that researchers analyse its differential features and compare its value for advertisers with that of well-established social media formats, such as Facebook Wall.

By considering these trends and other similar recent trends cited in the wider academic literature, this research study contributes towards developing clarity and consensus that Instagram is the most effective and popular social media platform for marketing purposes.

Towards Conceptual Model

The data analysis of this study has briefly improved the already established conceptual model. Social media apps and social media marketing were two main components of the framework,

and these still hold as valid in line with the study findings. However, this study contributes to the model through the addition of another factor: strategic adoption/use of social media apps. This study's findings revealed that without a strategic direction the use of social media marketing can be less beneficial; therefore, the consideration of multiple factors has become imperative when aiming to influence the buying behaviour of relevant consumers.

Readiness of restaurant owners and managers is a prerequisite identified in this regard, because the adoption and implementation of social media apps and marketing platforms will rely heavily on the readiness of small and medium-sized restaurants. The skill development of restaurant managers is embedded within this readiness to aid understanding of the dynamics of social media and for its optimal use. This will also assist in the selection of the most effective social media app, being original and organic, and in making sure that social media marketing activities are cost-effective. Resources and capabilities will be required for continued and improved use of social media marketing, which means that small and medium-sized restaurants will have to pay attention towards developing their resources and capabilities, which includes infrastructure facilities and skill development. Monitoring and evaluation of the desired outcomes and results are of equal importance because without knowing and understanding the effectiveness of different marketing activities, restaurants cannot improve and adjust in line with market trends.

Figure 16: Conceptual framework modified by the author

F&F, friends and family

In the light of the research findings, the conceptual framework has been modified and major implications can be observed on the social media marketing component and its variables (see Figure 16). The addition of some variables is a key change to this conceptual model. The variables added to the social media marketing component are “customer engagement”, “originality” and “friends and family”. This reflects that customer engagement is a pivotal objective that needs to be achieved by restaurants when using social media marketing, because customer engagement then leads to buying behaviour and this can give a precise strategic direction going forward for restaurants. Moreover, using original content and exploiting the potential of friends’ and family’s social network are two vital variables that should be targeted to influence consumer buying behaviour. This modified conceptual model is more precise and pragmatic; it can be used by small and medium-sized restaurants to attract customers and drive sales, especially in the midst of a COVID-19 crisis and in a post-COVID-19 scenario.

Along with the addition of a new component in the conceptual model, changes have occurred in the existing components “social media apps” and “social media marketing”. A small-scale change can be noticed in the social media apps component and its variables, with the addition of “popularity among customers” and ‘Instagram” as variables. The conceptual model has been changed significantly in line with contextual factors, which also increases its generalizability for the UK market.

6.4 Research Limitations

This research study has some research limitations. The continuity of the data collection process was halted a few times because of the lockdown restrictions imposed by the UK government, and face-to-face interaction with the potential respondents of small and medium-sized restaurants was not possible. The number of respondents included in the data collection process is a key limitation that this study faced because of the COVID-19 crisis and its implications. Reaching out to the respondents online was a difficult and time-consuming task because of a lack of response from the individuals. Incorporating the COVID-19 aspect in the research

process was also difficult and within this a limitation that factors might have been missed during the data collection and analysis process. Little or no prior experience of conducting thematic analysis and especially the development of coding and use of direct quotes was another limitation that was faced during the completion of this study.

The implications of COVID-19 are diverse and unique, especially in the context of the restaurant industry and consumers' responses in this market. More specifically, some respondents reflected on their social media experience and behaviours prior to the occurrence of the pandemic and some respondents who initiated social media marketing during the pandemic reflected on their experience and behaviours accordingly. The data of this study was gathered soon after the COVID-19 pandemic was declared. Therefore, the chances are high that consideration of some important factors might have been missed, which the researcher was unaware of. Similarly, a considerable number of the responses given by respondents were made against the backdrop of COVID-19, which means that respondents might have answered with a certain degree of personal bias towards the current situation. Therefore, a potential limitation could be the fact that respondents were not able to provide a clear and comprehensive picture in their responses because of the situation they were in at that time.

Another potential limitation of this study is the geographical coverage of the small and medium-sized restaurants across London; that is, only a specific area of London was covered as part of data collection process due to challenges of resources and COVID-19 implications. A more diverse area could have been covered for data collection, which could have improved the validity and generalizability of the results presented in this study.

Moreover, a potential limitation could be the process for formulating questions for the semi-structured interviews (i.e., certain significant factors might have been missed while formulating questions which could potentially affect the reliability of the data findings). For example, an attempt was made to formulate questions in line with the literature review findings and research objectives; however, due to subjective preferences and understanding, the researcher might not have considered some significant theoretical perspectives. A conscious effort was made to maintain the alignment of the research objectives and literature review with the interview questions; however, this limitation still needs to be acknowledged. For example, it was important to consider the empirical evidence presented, and assumptions derived from SET and social impact theory, to shape the interview questions. Any kind of unawareness and

unintentional neglect of assertions and propositions embedded in these theories could restrict the relevance and quality of the interview questions.

6.5 Future Research Directions

Future research should consider examining in-depth comparisons of various consumer segments (e.g., demographics, lifestyles, benefits sought, etc.) to get an understanding of how various consumer market segments may be changing because of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. The research limitations of this study have also opened the door to the initiation of future research directions. For example, no celebrity or social media influencer was included in the data collection process for this study, which could have added a unique perspective to the research findings and improved the validity of the findings. Therefore, including London-based influencers in a research process can be seen as a future research direction to improve the generalizability of the results. Research across other industries to enrich the evaluation of the impact of congruity on marketing activities in which influencers are involved would be of value.

Another suggestion is the use of a sample population that has gender-based balance or age-based balance because these factors can play a moderating role in the context of this research topic. Another future research direction could be on the effectiveness of Instagram as a lead social media app for marketing purposes (i.e., future research studies can compare the usefulness of different formats and features of Instagram when it is used to promote products and services) in the context of fitting in an influencer's campaign.

This study adopted behavioural intentions that are prominently used as antecedents of actual behaviours in the absence of actual behaviours, such as conversion rates on sales. Therefore, a potentially important area for future research includes behavioural metrics to gain a complete and clearer view of how an influencer–product fit affects the responses of users to marketing campaigns that are based on an influencer.

The results obtained through the study were derived from reported attitudes regarding social media. More authentic results could be obtained by carrying out studies on real social media behaviours. For instance, studies could be carried out about the use of certain social media platforms and the time duration that customers or users devote to them. The possibility of a

positive or negative impact of the social media platform on the user also exists; therefore, the research question could also include the positive or negative influence of the said social media platform on the user (e.g., Dhir et al., 2016). These impacts could include an increase in shopping searches, online shopping and customers' reviews after online purchases. Furthermore, investigations are required to explore businesses' policies on brand image, equity and customer satisfaction. Also, longitudinal studies could assist in determining the long-run impact of the changes observed in the behaviour of users during the pandemic. It is important to study the impact of social media marketing on different segments.

6.6 Research and Managerial Implications

The managerial conclusions suggest that restaurants need to take great care while promoting their goods and services through influencers. They must carry out market research before the marketing process and partner with the most authentic influencers (i.e., the influencers whose content and profiles focus on products that the business wants to promote) (Casaló et al., 2018). It would be ideal if brands worked in cooperation with influencers and created stories and content that relate to the products of the businesses and what the influencers share with their audience. Such efforts would create an increased perception of fit between the influencer and the products and would generate positive attitudes towards the marketing strategy used.

Brands also need to determine the users' product involvement level for effective collaboration with influencers. The involvement of users with the products the business is interested in promoting is of significant importance and it could affect revenue generation for the brand. User engagement is increased by the interaction of influencers through their accounts or profiles (Hughes et al., 2019). It is therefore important that influencers have appropriate knowledge of the goods a brand offers before collaborating with them. Relatedness between these goods and the content that they publish on their profiles on a daily basis is important for increased user interaction. In simple words, it can be said that promoting goods that match the content of the influencer serves as a basic marketing tactic to attract users to both the influencer and the brand.

Due to the pandemic, the online shopping trend has increased to a great extent and customers' willingness to shop in physical stores has declined. The pandemic has, ultimately, increased the use of social media for purchasing purposes. The literature reveals that consumers get impacted by external entities. This idea is explored in stimulus-organism-response theory and

the consumer decision-making model. Also, it is important to note that the purchasing decisions of a person get impacted after getting recommendations from an influencer. Furthermore, the positive reviews of other buyers also impact customers' decision making.

The results of studies reveal that customers use social media for shopping and other purposes and the trend in the use of social media has increased after the pandemic. Social media has become a major platform to compare products, look for alternatives and purchase products. It could therefore be used to create brand value and improve consumers' perceptions of a brand and its goods (Dhir et al., 2016). Users decide about buying or not buying a product through reviews and experiences shared by buyers on social media. Therefore, brands should use social media platforms that promote active engagement and portray the product in the right way. Social media platforms that are disliked by customers should not be used by brands for social media marketing (Kaur et al., 2018). According to the findings of Kaur et al. (2018), users' interest in a social media platform defines their interest in continuing their usage of that platform and interacting with brands through it.

Businesses could use the approach of collecting and sharing feedback from satisfied customers to promote their products on social media. Sharing reviews of buyers, tweets, likes and highlighting satisfied customers' feedback on the product could build the trust of customers and positively impact their attitudes. For instance, a brand could share positive reviews on its website so that interested people could know more about the product and buy it. Also, the brand could collaborate with an influencer to promote its product. The influencer could recommend the product and share their experience about it. Furthermore, social media could be utilized to create focus group interviews and develop connections between a brand and its customers. This could assist the brand in knowing about the issues faced by people and could assist them in resolving them.

Focus groups could also be used by brands to create success stories and customers' satisfaction posts that could be shared on different platforms. It is observed that businesses are motivated to engage with customers, but it is important to note that they shouldn't appreciate customers' attitudes creating social media fatigue. For instance, a business could appreciate consumers engaging with it by participating in brand-related activities and then sharing them online. The business could encourage customers by introducing a photography contest and announcing a giveaway for the winner. Such activities could create a positive relationship between customers and the brand. Dhir et al. (2017) reported that photo-sharing is a gesture of affection; Eftekhari

et al. (2014) identified in their study that relationships could be improved by photo tagging. It is important to note that increased social media interaction could negatively impact the performance of a business.

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8. Appendices A

8.1 Smash Burgers & Co (Owner as Respondent)

1. Why the use of social media and mobile apps for marketing purposes in restaurant industry is important?

Ans: Because you can reach a bigger audience that you typical wouldn't using traditional marketing.

2. What kind of social media and mobile apps you are using for marketing purposes?

Ans: Instagram and TikTok.

3. Are you using paid ads on social media apps for your restaurant and does that increase your customers? Why?

Ans: yes, paid ads on Instagram.

4. Are you using social media apps for giving new offers promotions and discounts and what the response you get?

Ans: Yes. And I get good response.

5. How do you compare the effectiveness of marketing for your business before and after social media apps adoption? Why do you say that?

Ans: Well my company is new, and we have only used social media marketing. We started our business 1 month ago.

6. Do you think social media posts about food or restaurants by friends and family members impact of customer buying behaviour?

Ans: yes.

7. Do you think social media influencers and food vloggers can help in attracting new customer?

Ans: yes, I have used few influencers and yes, they help get new customers.

8. Any link between pandemic and you opening this business?

Ans: its online business just started a month ago. And Yeah, I thought as people can't eat out, I'd provide delivery of premium burgers.

9. In what ways you think current use of social media and mobile apps can be improved for making it more effective in influencing consumer buying behaviour?

Ans: I don't know.

10. What recommendations would you make to restaurant business owners on the use of social media and apps and do you recommend using social media for marketing?

Ans: Utilize it to the best. We launched our whole business via social media, and it has been good Now it's a matter of retaining the customers.

8.2 Kofi & Co (Owner as Respondent)

1. Why the use of social media and mobile apps for marketing purposes in restaurant industry is important?

Ans: To increase recognition of restaurant and establish a name for ourselves.

2. What kind of social media and mobile apps you are using for marketing purposes?

Ans: Instagram and Facebook.

3. Are you using paid ads on social media apps for your restaurant and does that increase your customers? Why?

Ans: yes. We were gifted some sponsored adds from Instagram, but we have not pursued them ourselves. not sure yet if this increases our customers.

4. Are you using social media apps for giving new offers promotions and discounts and what the response you get?

Ans: We show specials we have on offer but not discounts and good response to these.

5. How do you compare the effectiveness of marketing for your business before and after social media apps adoption? Why do you say that?

Ans: We are quite new so I wouldn't be able to comment on this yet.

6. Do you think social media posts about food or restaurants by friends and family members impact of customer buying behaviour?

Ans: yes.

7. Do you think social media influencers and food vloggers can help in attracting new customer?

Ans: yes.

8. Impact of pandemic on your business?

Ans: started in october2020. Had to change to takeout and change menu ideas and prices.

9. In what ways you think current use of social media and mobile apps can be improved for making it more effective in influencing consumer buying behaviour?

Ans: Algorithms on Instagram should be changed.

10. What recommendations would you make to restaurant business owners on the use of social media and apps and do you recommend using social media for marketing?

Ans: I recommend using it and post frequently.

8.3 Burgo Town (Owner as Respondent)

1. Why the use of social media and mobile apps for marketing purposes in restaurant industry is important?

Ans: I'm a small start-up from home, I have no shopfront and aren't on any food apps. My only way of getting customers is through social media and word of mouth.

2. What kind of social media and mobile apps you are using for marketing purposes?

Ans: I use WhatsApp, Instagram, Snapchat and just started using tiktok.

3. Are you using paid ads on social media apps for your restaurant and does that increase your customers? Why?

Ans: I've used paid ads once, and that's because Instagram gave me a £20 voucher.

4. Are you using social media apps for giving new offers promotions and discounts and what the response you get?

Ans: I use social media to give promos, I do everything on social media there is no shopfront so I get all my customer through social media, also I'm only a few weeks in so I can't really say if the promos/discount brings in more business.

5. How do you compare the effectiveness of marketing for your business before and after social media apps adoption? Why do you say that?

Ans: I've only ever used social media there is no before social media for me.

6. Do you think social media posts about food or restaurants by friends and family members impact of customer buying behaviour?

Ans: yes.

7. Do you think social media influencers and food vloggers can help in attracting new customer?

Ans: yes definitely, whenever a blogger reviews my food i see activity on my page go up.

8. In what ways you think current use of social media and mobile apps can be improved for making it more effective in influencing consumer buying behaviour?

Ans: I'm not sure, haven't really thought about it sorry.

9. What recommendations would you make to restaurant business owners on the use of social media and apps and do you recommend using social media for marketing?

Ans: Definitely should use, i only get business through social media atm and it is doing well, I'm still pretty small and not enough people know about me. I've seen other burger pages advertise and do their market properly and the hype around their burgers food has been through the roof. If social media is used properly you can and will do well.

10. Any relationship of pandemic to you starting your business? Are you owner? And when you started your business?

Ans: I'm the owner, I started around a few weeks ago, I've seen a few start-ups from home, having a lot of free time during lockdown has given me an opportunity to start up my own business. So far so good, its profitable, Insha'Allah it can grow and keep growing.